

Circular Economy in corporate practice: How do internal management KPIs align with external reporting requirements?

Master thesis

submitted for the award of the master's degree at

University of Pforzheim

Author: Gero Jung

First supervisor: Prof. Dr. Tobias Viere

Second supervisor: Dr. Juliano Bezerra de Araújo

Executive Summary (Abstract)

In recent years, the implementation of the circular economy (CE), considering the various strategies and principles, has become increasingly important at company level. Mandatory reporting on sustainability issues has also contributed to this, as the companies concerned must disclose numerous qualitative and quantitative data on CE to fulfil the information requirements of external stakeholders. In addition to mandatory external reporting at EU-level, there are numerous other voluntary external and internal frameworks that enable companies to report on their progress in the transformation to CE using several metrics and indicators. However, it is questionable whether the data to be disclosed also reflects the relevant managerial key performance indicators (KPIs) for CE that are used internally or whether the external reporting only represents an additional effort for the companies and does not help to drive the implementation of CE. This research paper is therefore dedicated to the research question of which KPIs are used to manage and measure the CE at company level and to what extent these differ from the data to be disclosed in relevant voluntary and mandatory reporting standards.

It is also unclear which internal functions play an important role in the implementation of CE principles and strategies and should be considered when defining KPIs. The theoretical findings on CE indicators and KPIs obtained from a comprehensive systematic literature review are supplemented by empirical analyses of current practice. An online survey with numerous medium-sized and large German companies from the key sectors defined in the new EU action plan on CE will provide information on which CE KPIs are used by the companies. In addition, supplementary interviews will be conducted with some voluntary companies to deepen the results of the online survey and gain further insights into the implementation of the CE. The research has shown that many of the companies surveyed are still at the very beginning of the transformation to CE and that the definition of suitable management KPIs is still evolving. This is also reflected in the object of measurement of the indicators used, according to which the focus is on CE strategies of lower circularity levels like recycling and the manufacturing phase of the products. Furthermore, the KPIs most frequently used by companies are predominantly contained in mandatory and voluntary external reporting standards, which initially emphasises their practical relevance. The operations function with the categories resource consumption and waste management is currently at the centre of the CE indicators used. The results of the study have shown that the implementation of the external reporting requirements, despite their partially positive effect on the implementation of CE in companies, is currently associated with a great deal of personnel and time expenditure and still contains a large amount of data

that is only collected for the purpose of external reporting. In this context, it will be interesting to see in future whether and how the regulatory easing of reporting requirements, which is currently under development, will further reduce the burden on companies, while at the same time retaining key information on the CE.

Table of content

Executive Summary (Abstract)	II
List of abbreviations	VI
List of figures	VII
List of tables	VIII
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Objectives.....	2
1.2 Limitations.....	2
2 State of knowledge	4
2.1 Circular Economy.....	4
2.1.1 Core concepts and strategies of the CE	5
2.1.2 Micro level perspective	9
2.2 Reporting on CE.....	10
2.2.1 External reporting	12
2.2.2 Promotion of CE through external reporting	18
2.2.3 Internal reporting.....	21
2.3 CE KPIs at micro level	27
2.3.1 Need and objectives for CE indicators	28
2.3.2 Definitions	30
2.3.3 CE indicator taxonomies.....	32
2.3.4 Academical CE indicators and KPIs.....	36
2.3.5 Key research findings on CE indicators	38
2.3.6 Practical use of CE indicators	40
2.4 Affected operational functions of CE	41
3 Approach and research design.....	47
3.1 Research Questions.....	47
3.2 Systematic literature review	48
3.2.1 Data sources and research operators	49
3.2.2 Selection and exclusion criteria	50
3.2.3 Active search	51

3.2.4	Qualitative content analysis	52
3.2.5	Presentation of results	53
3.3	Online survey	53
3.3.1	Planning.....	53
3.3.2	Content and Layout.....	54
3.3.3	Privacy policy.....	55
3.3.4	Selection of participants	55
3.3.5	Testing and Execution.....	56
3.3.6	Evaluation.....	57
3.4	Qualitative Interviews	59
3.4.1	Content and guideline.....	59
3.4.2	Privacy policy.....	60
3.4.3	Execution.....	60
3.4.4	Evaluation.....	61
4	Results.....	62
4.1	Results of the survey.....	62
4.2	Results of the interviews.....	70
5	Discussion.....	74
5.1	Interpretation.....	74
5.2	CE Management tool.....	79
5.3	Limitations.....	81
6	Outlook and conclusion	83
6.1	Conclusion.....	83
6.2	Further research.....	84
	List of annexes.....	VI
	List of references.....	VI

List of abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CTI	Circular Transition Indicators
cVC	Circular Value Chain
DR	Disclosure Requirement
DSGVO	Datenschutzgrundverordnung
EC	European Commission
EMF	Ellen MacArthur Foundation
EoL	End of Life
ESG	Environment, Social, Governance
ESEF	European Single Electronic Format
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
GSSB	Global Sustainability Standards Board
GVA	Gross value added
INEC	Institute for Industrial Ecology
IRO	Impacts, risks and opportunities
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISSB	International Sustainability Standards Board
KPI	Key performance indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NACE	Nomenclature Générale des Activités Économiques dans les Communautés Européennes
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Anal- yses
PVC	Porter's Value Chain
R&D	Research & Development
SASB	Sustainability Accounting Standards Board
SLR	Systematic literature review
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development

List of figures

Figure 1: The butterfly diagram, adapted by (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 6)	7
Figure 2: The 9R Framework, adapted by (Potting et al. 2017: p. 15)	8
Figure 3: CE levels adapted by (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 456).....	9
Figure 4: Overview ESRS Standards.....	14
Figure 5: Classification of ESRS E5 indicators	16
Figure 6: Classification of CE indicators contained in the GRI standards	17
Figure 7: Classification of CE indicators contained in the SASB standards	18
Figure 8: Framework for measuring and assessing circularity (ISO/FDIS 59020)	22
Figure 9: Classification of CE indicators contained in the ISO 59020 standard.....	23
Figure 10: Classification of CE indicators contained in the Circulytics framework	25
Figure 11: Illustration of material flows (WBCSD und KPMG 2023: p. 14)	26
Figure 12: Classification of CE indicators contained in the CTI framework.....	27
Figure 13: Mapping of the 23 cVC categories and the PVC categories, adopted by (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 6)	35
Figure 14: Key CE functions of sustainable business management, adapted by (Barros et al. 2021: p. 4)	42
Figure 15: Relationship between the PVC and the cVC, adopted by (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 7)	44
Figure 16: SLR procedure according to PRISMA, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)	52
Figure 17: Contacted companies vs. returns, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)	57
Figure 18: Sector distribution of participants	63
Figure 19: Distribution of the usage of KPIs across sectors	66
Figure 20: Industry relevance of CE functions	67
Figure 21: Use of CE KPIs based on the taxonomy.....	68
Figure 22: CE standards and frameworks used	69
Figure 23: Overlap of the companies' CE KPIs with the CE standards	70

List of tables

Table 1: CE related reporting frameworks and standards.....	12
Table 2: Classification criteria for CE indicators	13
Table 3: External reporting frameworks and standards	13
Table 4: Internal reporting frameworks and standards	21
Table 5: Overview of the indicator categories	24
Table 6: Relevant academical micro-level CE indicators	37
Table 7: Academical KPIs identified by Janik and Ryszko	38
Table 8: Comparison of the relevant operational functions for the CE	46
Table 9: Search strings of the SLR's	50
Table 10: Exclusion criteria, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)	51
Table 11: Inductive category system, based on (Mayring 2010: p. 609).....	53
Table 12: Criteria for selecting KPIs and questions	55
Table 13: Selection criteria for survey participants.....	55
Table 14: Identification approach for participants.....	56
Table 15: Classification criteria for CE indicators	59
Table 16: Criteria for the selection of questions	60
Table 17: Most frequently used CE KPIs.....	64
Table 18: Least used CE KPIs	65
Table 19: Additional KPIs used by companies	65

1 Introduction

In just four years, from 2016 to 2021, the global economy consumed 582 billion tonnes of materials. That's almost as much as the 740 billion tonnes consumed throughout the entire 20th century (Fraser et al. 2024: p. 18). One driver of this development is the increasing global population growth to more than 8 billion people today. The increase in per capita consumption and significantly more resource-intensive production and consumption patterns are also responsible for that. The World Bank predicts that, due to the time lag in resource consumption, municipal waste will increase to 3.4 billion tonnes by 2050, leading to significant waste accumulation (Kaza et al. 2018: p. 3). This negative development places unsustainable pressure on the earth's ecosystems and biocapacity. With the planet's current economy, 1.7 Earths will already be needed to meet the demand for raw materials by 2024 (Lin und Wackernagel 2024: p. 1 f.). This resource intensive global economy has numerous environmental impacts, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, water- and soil-pollution, resource depletion and excessive land use. According to calculations by the United Nations International Resource Panel, around 50% of all greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and around 90% of global biodiversity losses are already attributable to the production and utilisation of raw materials (Oberle et al. 2019: p. 65 f.).

All these negative developments show that the traditional linear economic model, based on the idea of „take, make, throw“, requires a fundamental paradigm shift towards a CE. The several principles of the CE aim to keep products and materials in their useful life for as long as possible, reduce the environmentally harmful extraction of primary raw materials and thus minimise the generation of waste streams (Wilts 2021: p. 372 f.). It can be divided into three levels: micro, meso and macro. The micro level comprises products, companies and consumers. The meso level comprises networks of companies (e.g. industrial parks or green supply chain management) and the macro level analyses cities, regions and countries (Kraft et al. 2022: p. 13). In this work the focus lies on the characteristics of the CE at the micro-level, especially its implementation and management in companies. The topic of the CE has also received increasing attention at political level in recent years. In 2019, the European Commission (EC) adopted the EU Green Deal as a new, sustainable growth strategy for the EU (European Commission 11.12.2019). Consisting of numerous interlinked measures to promote ambitious environmental and social objectives, such as EU climate neutrality in 2050, the EU Green Deal includes the new Circular Economy Action Plan. It was adopted by the EC in 2020 and represents a comprehensive package of measures aimed at decoupling economic growth from resource use in

the EU. The EC has defined various key sectors that are of particular importance in the transformation to a CE (European Commission 11.03.2020).

In addition to these sector-specific and overarching measures for the gradual transition to a CE, the topic is also reflected in numerous voluntary and mandatory standards for sustainability reporting at company level. According to the various frameworks, companies are required to disclose numerous qualitative and quantitative data relating to the implementation of the CE to external stakeholders. These transparency obligations have the potential to promote the CE in companies, but often also mean an enormous amount of additional bureaucracy. It is questionable whether the disclosure obligations will provide the internal management in companies with additional knowledge to identify, measure and manage potential for the CE or whether completely different company-specific qualitative and quantitative information is decisive for promoting the topic. This discrepancy between external and internal reporting is also reflected in traditional accounting. A distinction is made between regulated external financial reporting and internal, individualised management accounting. The financial reporting addresses the information needs of various external stakeholders, while management accounting serves as an internal basis for strategic business decisions at management level. This analogy between financial and non-financial (sustainability) reporting is intended to illustrate the need to analyse the transformation to CE at company level in terms of the discrepancy between external reporting of certain indicators and the potential internal use of those as key performance indicators (KPIs) relevant to the management of the company.

1.1 Objectives

The relevant internal KPIs for companies to measure, manage and successfully implement the CE can differ from the information provided in external, non-financial reporting in accordance with mandatory and voluntary standards. The aim of this master thesis is therefore to identify the relevant internal CE KPIs for companies and to explain how they differ from the required external non-financial reporting disclosures. By identifying the CE KPIs used in companies, conclusions can be drawn about the relevant internal functions affected, how the transformation to CE is organised and how a suitable management tool could look like.

1.2 Limitations

The scope of this study is limited to CE KPIs at micro level. For this purpose, medium-sized and large companies according to §267 HGB with headquarters in Germany are analysed (German Federal

Ministry of Justice 17.04.2024). In addition, only the key sectors defined in the new EU Circular Economy Action Plan are investigated (European Commission 11.03.2020):

- Electronics and ICT
- Batteries and vehicles
- Packaging
- Plastics
- Textiles
- Construction and buildings
- Food, water and nutrients

Regarding external reporting on the CE, current voluntary and mandatory frameworks at EU and international level are identified and analysed concerning the indicators to be published. The focus of this work is on ecological and financial related CE indicators whereas the social perspective of CE is not considered.

2 State of knowledge

2.1 Circular Economy

Today's economic system is based on the fundamental idea of linearity, in which natural raw materials are extracted in large quantities by companies and processed into products. These are utilised by consumers and ultimately disposed as waste (Michellini et al. 2017: p. 2). The linear economic model can also be broken down into the steps „take, make and dispose“ (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 2). This system requires a transformation, as it produces large amounts of waste, leads to resource depletion, emissions and biodiversity loss and seriously alters natural landscapes (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017: p. 757). As a result, the earth is increasingly approaching its planetary boundaries and is already exceeding them in some dimensions (Steffen et al. 2015: p. 736). Moreover all these negative impacts are causing significant harm on the planet's ability to meet the needs of future generations (ISO/FDIS 59020: p. 6). The strategies and principles of a CE represent a promising approach to tackle some of the challenges mentioned above as it has the potential to decouple economic growth from the negative impacts of resource depletion and environmental degradation (Morseletto 2020: p. 1).

At its core, the idea of CE is about extending the utilisation phase of resources, products and materials and using resources in closed-loop systems (Barros et al. 2021: p. 1). According to various scientists, the concept of CE goes back to its introduction by Pearce and Turner (Ghisellini et al. 2016: p. 14; Su et al. 2013: p. 215). They describe how natural resources influence the economy by providing inputs for production and consumption and serving as a sink for outputs (waste) (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017: p. 759; Pearce und Turner 1989). Today's understanding of CE and its practical application is characterised by features of various concepts, such as industrial ecology (Graedel und Allenby 1996), cradle-to-cradle (McDonough und Braungart 2010), laws of ecology (Commoner 2020), looped an performance economy (Stahel 2010), regenerative design (Lyle 1996), biomimicry (Benyus 1997) and the blue economy (Pauli 2010). They are all linked by the shared idea of closed loops (Geissdoerfer et al. 2017: p. 759). There is still no generally accepted scientific consensus on a definition for CE. Kirchherr et al. formulate a comprehensive definition based on an analysis of 114 definitions for CE from academics and practitioners, which should serve as a theoretical understanding of the concept (Kirchherr et al. 2017: p. 224 f.):

A circular economy describes an economic system that is based on business models which replace the 'end-of-life' concept with reducing, alternatively reusing, recycling and recovering materials in production/distribution and consumption processes, thus operating at the micro level

(products, companies, consumers), meso level (eco-industrial parks) and macro level (city, region, nation and beyond), with the aim to accomplish sustainable development, which implies creating environmental quality, economic prosperity and social equity, to the benefit of current and future generations.

This definition emphasises the complexity and multidimensionality of the topic. CE can therefore be broken down into various operational core strategies, the three system perspectives macro, meso and micro as well as the overarching objective of contributing to sustainable development at the economic, ecological and social levels. In the following subchapters, the scope of the study is therefore further narrowed down and important CE principles, concepts and strategies for this work are presented. The underlying research gap for identifying the research questions will be also explained in more detail.

2.1.1 Core concepts and strategies of the CE

The following subchapter presents the central principles, concepts and strategies of the transition to a CE referred to in the literature. A basic prerequisite for the transition from a linear economy to a CE is thinking in closed cycles. In the corporate context, this includes achieving closed raw material cycles (materials, water, energy) through various technological and biological cycles. Therefore, adopting a CE involves implementing various strategies for resource management, such as linking linear flows, using less resources, extending product or service life, designing for durability and longevity, and minimizing resource degradation. These approaches aim to reduce resource consumption and loss while engaging in value creation and distribution (ISO/FDIS 59004: p. 15 f.). These principles, concepts and strategies should be considered by an organisation in the identification of CE indicators and KPIs at micro level, as they define the object of measurement.

Core principles:

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMF) is one of the leading organizations driving the transition to a CE, promoting sustainable models through research, practical solutions, and global partnerships. By influencing businesses, governments, and education, it plays a key role in making CE principles widely recognized and actionable on a global scale. It defines three core principles of CE, which are referred to by numerous academics. These can be summarised as follows (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 5 ff.):

1. Regenerate natural systems

The first principle aims to dematerialise companies' products and services by sparingly using non-renewable resources, using renewable resources whenever possible and thus reducing the negative

environmental impact on ecosystems so that the earth's natural capital can regenerate (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 5).

2. Keep products and materials in use

Secondly, circular systems aim to optimize resource yields by maintaining products, components, and materials at their highest utility within both technical and biological cycles, emphasizing remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling. These systems prioritize tighter loops, extending product life, enhancing reuse, and safely returning biological nutrients to the biosphere, ultimately maximizing value extraction and system effectiveness without compromising performance (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 7).

3. Design out waste and pollution

Principle 3 emphasizes enhancing system effectiveness by identifying and eliminating negative externalities. This involves reducing harm to sectors like food, mobility, shelter, education, health, and entertainment, while managing externalities such as land use, pollution, and the release of toxic substances (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 7). Figure 1 illustrates the principles and associated strategies based on the biological and technical material cycle. The biological cycle involves the flow of renewable materials, with consumption occurring solely within this cycle, where renewable (biological) nutrients are primarily regenerated. The technical cycle focuses on managing finite material stocks, where use substitutes consumption, and technical materials are primarily recovered and refurbished (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 7 f.).

Figure 1: The butterfly diagram, adapted by (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 6)

The core principles of the CE share the common goal of value retention, which is expressed by the following ideas: The idea of the inner circle highlights that the closer the loop, the greater the value of the strategy, as repairing and maintaining products, such as cars, retains the majority of their value, while reusing or remanufacturing individual components preserves more value than material recycling, thereby maintaining a product's integrity, complexity, and embedded labour and energy. The power of extending cycles involves maximizing the number of consecutive cycles and/or the duration of each cycle for products, e.g. reusing or prolonging product life as each extended cycle reduces the material, energy, and labour required to produce new items. The power of cascaded use involves diversifying reuse throughout the value chain, such as when cotton clothing is initially re-used as second-hand apparel, then repurposed as fibrefill in furniture upholstery and later applied in stone wool insulation for construction, each time replacing the need for virgin materials, before the cotton fibres are safely reintroduced into the biosphere. The power of pure inputs lies in the fact that uncontaminated material streams enhance the efficiency of collection and redistribution while preserving quality, especially for technical materials, thereby extending product lifespan and increasing material productivity (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 8).

Core strategies:

In science, various R-strategies are discussed, which can be seen as an operationalization of the concept of CE (Kirchherr et al. 2017: p. 221). The realisation of the various strategies requires the development and implementation of new circular business models (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 556). The 9R framework developed by Potting et al., shown in figure 2, can be considered the most granular (Potting et al. 2017: p. 15).

Figure 2: The 9R Framework, adapted by (Potting et al. 2017: p. 15)

The framework provides a comprehensive overview of the information required to measure progress in the transition to CE. The individual strategies aim to reduce the consumption of natural resources and materials and minimize the production of waste as they contribute to value retention and recovery (ISO/FDIS 59004: p. 22 f.). In the 9R framework, the individual R-strategies are divided into three categories according to their circularity level. The R-strategies in the „Smarter product use and manufacture” category represent the highest level of circularity and belong to the inner circle of the technological cycle of the butterfly diagram. **Refusing (R0)** strategies are making the current product or service redundant by offering the same function through a completely different approach. Intensifying the use of a product by sharing, leasing or pooling business models belong to the R-strategy **rethink (R1)**. **Reducing (R2)** means increasing efficiency (material, energy, water) of the product through its whole life cycle and consuming fewer natural resources. The R-strategies of the next category „Extend lifespan of product and its parts” aim at extending the use phase of a product and avoiding the extraction of additional raw materials. They are in the middle circles of the technological cycle of the butterfly diagram. **Reusing (R3)** can be explained as the repeated utilization of a

product which is still in a good condition by another customer. **Repairing (R4)** or maintaining means bringing a defective product back in its original condition so it can be used again. **Refurbishing (R5)** can be expressed as the revival of an outdated product through modernisation. The incorporation of components from a discarded product into a new one that serves the same purpose is explained by **remanufacturing (R6)**. When these old components are used in a different product the R-strategy **repurpose (R7)** is used. The strategies in the „Useful application of materials” category are described as the lowest level of circularity and represent the outer cycles of the butterfly diagram. **Recycling (R8)** processes are often material- and energy-intensive and require additional natural resources to counteract reduced product quality. Incineration or energy **recovery (R9)** of products at the end of their life cycle is seen as the last option, as the materials are no longer available for reuse in other products. The general conclusion that can be drawn from this is that a higher level of circularity equates to an increase in environmental benefits (Potting et al. 2017: p. 15 ff.). The individual R-strategies are taken up again when identifying relevant CE indicators and KPIs in chapter 2.3.

2.1.2 Micro level perspective

In this research paper, the focus is on the micro level. To this end, the underlying understanding of the micro level is first defined in order to avoid misunderstandings: In the literature, the micro level is often equated with the company level (Roos Lindgreen et al. 2020: p. 6). This involves a broad perspective that includes the strategic level, e.g. development and adoption of circular business models, and the operational level, e.g. increasing resource and product circulation (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 456). For this reason, Saidani et al. have introduced the nano level, which represents a specification of the micro level and focusses on CE in relation to products, components and materials, see figure 3 (Saidani et al. 2017: p. 5; Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 456).

Figure 3: CE levels adapted by (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 456)

When referring to micro level indicators in this paper, the nano level is also included. In general, companies play a central role in the transformation to CE, as they convert natural resources into goods and services (Roos Lindgreen et al. 2020: p. 1). By developing new circular business models and improving product circularity, they make a decisive contribution to the development of a CE. They also could have some intrinsic reasons to address CE as they want to manage resource scarcity risks, engage with affected stakeholders in the up- and downstream value chain and increase resilience in environmental, economic, and social systems at the same time (ISO/FDIS 59020: p. 6).

2.2 Reporting on CE

As described above, the CE model can be seen as an operationalization of the vague concept of sustainable development at company level and has received increasing attention by several stakeholders involved in that topic. To drive the transformation to CE at company level, it is essential to measure and monitor circularity using suitable frameworks, tools and indicators (Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020: p. 3). In recent years, various public institutions, NGO's, politicians and consulting firms have therefore incorporated some of the core principles and strategies of CE into their work. As a result, numerous frameworks, guidelines and tools have been developed to drive forward the transformation to CE and to report on it (Corona et al. 2019: p. 1 f.). Thereby the individual frameworks differ in their objectives, user group and addressees of the data collected. The topic of CE has also already found its way into EU policy. As part of the EU Green Deal from 2019, the EU adopted the new action plan for CE, which can be seen as a comprehensive package of measures consisting of numerous regulations and directives. These are aimed at implementing a sustainable product policy through a corresponding legal framework and are intended to promote the overall goal of the transformation to the CE. The individual measures initially relate to the central product value chains and economic sectors defined by the EU (European Commission 11.12.2019, 11.03.2020):

- Electronics and ICT
- Batteries and vehicles
- Packaging
- Plastics
- Textiles
- Construction and buildings
- Food, water and nutrients

As already explained in chapter 1.2, this research focuses on the measurement of CE in these key sectors. Within the EU Green Deal, the mandatory external sustainability reporting of companies is

also revised and tightened. According to the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (Directive (EU) 2022/2464) and the associated European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772), companies must publish numerous disclosures on CE in their annual report (EU Parliament and council 14.12.2022; EU Commission 31.07.2023). Not only politicians, but also NGO's, above all the EMF, are helping to drive forward the transformation to CE. Through its work at the interface between companies, governments and science, the organization is helping to establish CE and, by developing Circulytics, has created a framework for measuring the CE performance of companies using suitable indicators (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2022). In addition to the two frameworks and reporting standards mentioned, several others are examined to clarify the research question. The central research project of this thesis is to identify company level CE KPIs used in practice and based on this, to elucidate the discrepancy between those and the indicators required in external sustainability reporting standards on CE.

As the various reporting standards have not yet been adopted by companies, it is not yet clear whether they also contain the KPIs relevant to corporate management or whether they merely represent an additional reporting burden for the companies subject to reporting requirements. In this context, it is also important to clarify whether the external standards have the potential to promote the transformation to CE at company level.

The assumption that there could be a discrepancy between the CE indicators from external reporting and the internal KPIs is based on the discrepancy between internal (management) and external (financial) accounting in traditional financial reporting. Both functions are intended to provide a comprehensive picture of a company's financial situation but differ essentially in their purpose and target group. Internal (management) accounting fulfils the information needs of management, as it provides a basis for operational and strategic decisions by preparing relevant financial information and related indicators. The focus of external (financial) accounting is on the highly regulated preparation of annual financial statements aimed at external stakeholders, such as investors, lenders, authorities and the public (Rechenberg 2023). To confirm or refute this assumption, the contents of the external voluntary and mandatory sustainability reporting standards established in practice are analysed regarding CE data. To obtain a complete picture of which reporting standards and frameworks contain the CE KPIs used by the companies, frameworks with an internal focus on CE measurement are also included. Table 1 provides an overview of the reporting frameworks and standards analysed. In a first step, the individual frameworks are briefly introduced using a standardised grid and then a comprehensive list of the data and indicators to be reported in each case is drawn up. In addition, the

indicators contained in the respective standards are categorised according to the classification criteria in table 2 to elucidate the differences and similarities in comparison with the results of the empirical studies. These steps form the basis for comparing the content with the results of the online survey and the interviews with the companies concerned. The following sub-chapters go into more detail on the content of the frameworks and are divided into external and internal reporting frameworks and standards.

Table 1: CE related reporting frameworks and standards

Editor	Description	Typ of regulation	Legally binding	Primary focus
EU Commission	ESRS E5 - Resource use and circular economy)	Reporting Standard	Mandatory	External
GRI	- GRI 301 Materials - GRI 302 Energy - GRI 303 Water and Effluents - GRI 306 Waste	Reporting Standard	Voluntary	External
SASB	Several sector specific standards	Reporting Standard	Voluntary	External
ISO	ISO 59020 Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance	Framework	Voluntary	Internal
EMF	Circulytics	Framework	Voluntary	Internal
WBCSD	CTI V4.0	Framework	Voluntary	Internal

2.2.1 External reporting

In the following subchapter, the external reporting standards analysed based on CE data and indicators are presented in more detail. In table 2, the most important general information on these is illustrated using various categories. This is followed by an introduction to the individual standards and a brief description of the CE data and indicators identified. A comprehensive list of data points for the individual standards can be found in the supplementary Excel file. In the data point list, the individual CE indicators of the various standards are listed according to different criteria, see table 3. The list of data points serves as a basis for comparison with the results from the survey. A justification for the selection of the comparison criteria can be found in subchapter 2.3.3.

Table 2: Classification criteria for CE indicators

Classification criteria	Explanation
CE strategies	R-strategy on which the indicator is based (intensification of product use, extension of product use, product circulation)
Life Cycle Stage	Phase of the product life cycle to which the indicator contributes
Unit	Qualitative and quantitative indicators
Performance	Indicators measure the progress/transition of actions or the impact/effect
Dimension	Single or multiple dimensional indicators focussing on one or several R-strategies and CE principles
Internal function	Affected stakeholders/functions of the indicator within the company

Table 3: External reporting frameworks and standards

Criteria	Standards and frameworks		
	ESRS E5	GRI	SASB
Editor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Commission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global Sustainability Standards Board (GSSB) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB)
User group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU and some non-EU companies Gradual expansion of the user group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any organization, regardless of size, type, geographic location, or reporting experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Globally applicable to all companies with a focus on ESG communication to investors
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enabling users of the sustainability statement to understand the company's material impacts on people and environment and the material effects of sustainability matters on the undertaking's development, performance and position 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing transparency on how an organization contributes or aims to contribute to sustainable development Enabling an organization to publicly disclose its most significant impacts on the economy, environment, and people, including impacts on their human rights and how the organization manages these impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allowing organizations to disclose industry-specific information regarding sustainability-related risks and opportunities that could reasonably impact the entity's cash flows, access to finance, or cost of capital in the short, medium, or long term. The standards highlight the sustainability-related factors that are most important for investor decision-making in 77 different industries
Disclosure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate section in the management report European Single Electronic Format (ESEF) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronic, e.g. included in sustainability report, annual report GRI content index gives an overview of the reported information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication of the data in the separate or integrated sustainability report

ESRS E5 - Resource use and circular economy

As described above, the EU Commission adopted the CSRD (Directive (EU) 2022/2464) at the end of 2022 (EU Parliament and council 14.12.2022). This obliges numerous EU and partly also non- EU companies to report on sustainability related issues. The directive was originally due to come into force for reporting period 2023 with the publication of the first reports in 2024. The CSRD, including the EU Taxonomy and the European Supply Chain Act, is currently being revised by the EU Commission with the aim of introducing major simplifications in reporting for the companies concerned (EU Parliament and council 18.07.2020, 13.06.2024; Europäischer Rat 08.11.2024). The companies in the first user group include those that have already published a sustainability report in accordance with the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (EU Parliament and council 22.10.2014). However, the obligation is to be extended to numerous other large, medium-sized and small companies over the next few years, regardless of their capital market orientation. Reporting is carried out in accordance with the requirements of the ESRS (Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772). The standards are divided into two general, five environmental, four social and one governance standard, see figure 4.

Figure 4: Overview ESRS Standards

The double materiality analysis described in ESRS 1 defines the scope of the report. Accordingly, the data points of ESRS 2 must be reported as well as relevant data points from the various topic-specific standards. A sustainability topic is material on the one hand if it relates to the company's impact on the environment and people and on the other hand if it has a significant financial impact on the company. A sustainability topic is therefore considered material if the impact materiality (Inside-out) and the financial materiality (Outside-in) are fulfilled. The ESRS data points are highly detailed, meaning that the CSRD can be regarded as the most comprehensive sustainability reporting

currently available. The topic of CE is covered by the environmental standard E5 - Resource use and circular economy. If the topic of CE is material for the company, it must report information on numerous disclosure requirements (DR's). These include qualitative and quantitative data. In the appendix of each standard, the information to be reported according to the DR's is further explained through corresponding application requirements. Firstly, the company's impacts, risks and opportunities (IROs) in relation to CE and resource use must be identified along the value chain. Within the category „Impact, risk and opportunity management” the company must disclose the process of the IRO identification (ESRS 2 IRO-1), policies related to resource use and circular economy (DR E5-1) as well as actions and resources related to resource use and circular economy (DR E5-2). This chapter is followed by the disclosure of numerous „metrics and targets”. These are structured in the disclosure of targets related to resource use and circular economy (DR E5-3) and several metrics related to resource inflows (DR E5-4), resource outflows, including products, materials and waste (DR E5-5) and the anticipated financial effects from material resource use and circular economy-related risks and opportunities (DR E5-6) (EU Commission 31.07.2023). A detailed list of the data points to be published can be found in the supplementary Excel file. Figure 5 shows the classification of the 77 CE indicators contained in the ESRS E5 based on the criteria described in table 2. Regarding the affected internal functions of CE measurement, shown on the far-left column of the diagram („CE function”), only the three largest functions are listed due to space issues. Approx. 36% of the indicators relate to „Resource consumption” which includes energy, water and materials and is largely allocated to ESRS E5 chapter DR E5-4 (Resource inflows). The „Waste management” function includes approx. 27% of the ESRS E5 indicators and is allocated to chapter DR E5-5 (Resource outflows). The remaining indicators are distributed across the internal functions in the following order: „No function, Finance, Ecodesign, Business model, Cooperation & industrial symbiosis, Post-sales services and Reverse logistics”. The next column shows the respective „R-strategy” to which the indicators relate. Almost 60% of the indicators can't be assigned to a specific R-strategy. Around 20% of the indicators include all R-strategies. The remaining 20% are divided between the three circularity levels Product Circulation (Recycle, Recover), Intensification of product use (rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse) and Extension of product use (Repair, Refurbish, and Remanufacture). The column „Dimension” shows that most indicators are single dimensional and relate to only one of the circularity levels and R-strategies mentioned. The next column shows the „Life Cycle stage” to which the indicators relate. A relatively even distribution can be seen, except for the Use- phase of the products, which is only covered by a few indicators (5%). Most of the indicators relate to the „End of Life (EoL)” and „Make”

life cycle phase. Around 77% of the ESRS E5 indicators measure the effect or impact of CE-orientated measures, as can be seen in the „Performance” column. Finally, there is a balanced ratio of qualitative and quantitative indicators, which can be attributed to the numerous policies (DR E5-1), actions (DR E5-2) and targets (DR E5-3) to be described in relation to resource use and CE as can be seen in column „Unit”.

Figure 5: Classification of ESRS E5 indicators

GRI Standards

In addition to mandatory sustainability reporting for companies, there are also voluntary reporting standards. The independent standards of the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), based in Boston, USA, should be mentioned foremost. The first version of the standards was published in 2000 and has been continuously improved and expanded to this day. They can be applied regardless of company size and organisation and are the most widely used voluntary international sustainability reporting standards for companies. A materiality analysis carried out at the beginning defines the scope of reporting. Together with relevant stakeholders the materiality analysis aims to identify the company's material impacts on the economy, the environment and people, including human rights. In addition to the three universal standards, the data points from the relevant topic-specific standards covering environmental, social and governance topics must be reported on. In addition, if applicable, the information from the sector-specific standards must be fulfilled (GRI Initiative 2025). Various environment-related topic standards contain indicators and data points that must be disclosed. Unlike the ESRS, there is no single standard that contains relevant data on CE. These are contained in the various environmental standards (GRI 301- Materials, GRI 302- Energy, GRI 303- Water and effluents, GRI 306- Effluents and Waste). A detailed list of the information to be disclosed can be found in the supplementary Excel file.

Figure 6 shows the classification of the 56 CE indicators contained in the environmental-related GRI standards based on the classification criteria from table 2. Most of the indicators are quantitative and single dimensional, i.e. the indicators only focus on a specific characteristic of the CE as can be

seen in the columns „Unit” and „Dimension”. 96% of the indicators are formulated in general terms and do not refer to any specific R-strategy, as can be seen in the column „R-strategy”. The leftmost column „CE function” shows the relevant internal function of the indicators. These are divided into „Resource consumption” (88%) and „Waste management” (12%). 98% of the CE indicators included in the GRI measure the effect or impact of CE actions and focus less on measuring the transition to a CE as can be seen in column „Performance”. Regarding the life cycle phase of the indicators, there is a somewhat more even distribution, see column „Life Cycle stage”. Most indicators (45%) relate to the manufacturing phase of products (make). 32% of the indicators include all life cycle phases. The remaining indicators are divided between the EoL- and Use- phases or cannot be assigned to any specific life cycle phase. The classification of the indicators is taken up again in chapter 5.1 to compare them with the indicators used by companies in practice.

Figure 6: Classification of CE indicators contained in the GRI standards

SASB Standards

The SASB (Sustainability Accounting Standards Board) is a non-profit organisation and was founded in the USA in 2011. It is concerned with the creation of uniform, industry-oriented standards for the disclosure of sustainability-related information, with a special focus on the information needs of investors. The standards are first published in 2018 and designed to identify the sustainability-related opportunities and risks of companies that can affect its financial results, cash flow, access to funds and borrowing costs. The standards cover 77 different industries and define relevant topics and key figures for each sector. Companies are required to disclose this data, whereby they can decide which information to report depending on the materiality and relevance of the topics. As a result, companies benefit from greater transparency, improved risk management and enhanced performance. The SASB Standards thus provide a clear structure for disclosure that helps investors to better understand the impact of environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors on company performance (Outside-in perspective) (IFRS Foundation 2025).

The spread of the SASB standards has increased steadily since their introduction, especially in recent years. More and more companies and investors are integrating the standards into their reporting and decision-making processes. Since 2022, the ISSB has been responsible for the further development of the SASB Standards with the aim of internationalising them and creating a globally recognised reporting framework (Beiersdorf 2023: p. 3). As the SASB standards are sector-specific standards, all standards that can be assigned to the key sectors defined by the EU for CE are analysed for CE-related data points. A matrix is used for better visualisation, as some data points are used in several standards at the same time. A detailed list of the data collected can be found in the supplementary Excel file. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of the 55 SASB indicators that focus on CE. It is noticeable that the SASB indicators relate to many different internal functions, as can be seen in the left-hand column „CE function”. As with the ESRS and GRI indicators, most of them relate to the „Resource consumption” and „Waste management” category. The remainder are distributed across the categories of „Material sourcing, Business model, Reverse logistics, Ecodesign and Resource recovery”. The „R-strategy” pillar shows that almost 62% of the indicators cannot be assigned to a specific R-strategy. 30% of the SASB indicators measure „Product circulation (recycling, recovery)” and therefore focus on the lowest level of circularity. The classification criterion „Dimension” shows that all indicators analysed are single dimensional. The next pillar, „Life Cycle stage”, shows that all life cycle stages are represented in the indicators, with a particular focus on the manufacturing stage of products (Make) at 60%. Most of the indicators measure the impact of CE actions and only a few focus on measuring the transition to CE (90% vs. 10%), as can be seen in the „Performance” pillar. Finally, the right-hand column „Unit” shows that most indicators are quantitative (87%). The classification of the indicators is taken up again in chapter 5.1 to compare them with the indicators used by companies in practice.

Figure 7: Classification of CE indicators contained in the SASB standards

2.2.2 Promotion of CE through external reporting

This chapter is dedicated to the following sub-research question:

To what extent does the data from main mandatory and voluntary external reporting standards contribute to measure, manage and implement the CE in companies?

Therefore, a systematic literature review (SLR) is carried out to collect existing findings on this issue. This theoretical analysis forms the basis for comparison with the results of the empirical investigations in the discussion section of this thesis. The CRSD, including the associated ESRS, has recently been adopted by the EU Commission and is to be applied for the first time for the financial year 2024, with the reports to be published by the first user group of companies in 2025. Therefore, the assumption that there are only a few scientific sources on this topic can be confirmed. The strengths and weaknesses of sustainability reporting are subject of much controversy. For example, the additional cost burden for companies when implementing the reporting obligations for the first time and the additional auditing costs of the sustainability report are among the points of criticism frequently mentioned (Bannier 2023: p. 162 f.). It is also criticised that the bureaucratic burden of reporting would tie up the capacities required for real sustainability changes (Obst 2024).

In contrast, however, there are also numerous opportunities for companies in the context of reporting. For example, the disclosure of significant opportunities and risks for the company in relation to various sustainability aspects leads to an improved risk assessment for potential investors and can reduce borrowing costs. In addition, a standardised reporting format and the audit obligation ensure better credibility, transparency and comparability of corporate sustainability information.

The increased quality of sustainability information as a result of the introduction of mandatory reporting has been confirmed by numerous scientific studies (Bannier 2023: p. 163 f.). If companies do not view the reporting obligation as a mere compliance issue, but implement the requirements effectively, numerous other advantages and opportunities can arise. Frequently mentioned points here are potential cost savings through improved energy and material efficiency measures, as well as the development of a company-wide understanding of sustainability.

In addition, dealing with CSRD reporting obligations ensures that established business models and routines are scrutinised and innovative, environmentally and socially compatible business models and products are developed. This can increase competitiveness in the long term (Obst 2024). At the latest since the adoption of the CSRD and the associated EU taxonomy, the topic of sustainability reporting by companies has grown enormously in importance. The reporting obligation no longer only applies to large, capital market-oriented companies, but will also be successively extended to large, medium-sized and small companies that are not capital market-oriented in the coming years. However, it is questionable whether external reporting on CE, which is integrated into the ESRS

reporting standards through a separate standard E5 - Circular economy and resource use, also contributes to the internal implementation and promotion of the topic. There are currently hardly any empirical studies on this topic, which is certainly also since no CSRD-compliant sustainability reports have yet been published by companies. In this context, Falkenberg et al. investigate the research question of whether the concept of CE can be promoted by CSRD due to the changed reporting requirements. To this end, they conduct a SLR, analyse 20 sustainability reports from the agri-food sector and conduct individual expert interviews with company representatives. They conclude that external reporting on CE can help to promote the topic internally. The main reason given for this is the intensive discussion of CE and the promotion of company-wide awareness, which is seen as an essential first step. However, according to the experts from the companies, this does not automatically mean that enough will be realised in practice to implement CE. They argue that additional obligations such as a design guideline are necessary.

It is also noted that the implementation of reporting obligations is still at an early stage and that clear benefits for promoting CE are not yet sufficiently evident. In addition, the contribution of reporting to the promotion of CE also depends on the individual level of ambition of the respective companies when it comes to implementation. From the perspective of the companies interviewed, the main strengths and potentials of the disclosure requirements are the promotion of the measurability of CE, the reduction of greenwashing, the inclusion of the value chain and the audit obligation (Falkenberg et al. 2023: p. 6 ff.).

Opferkuch et al. believe that the increased demand from investors for CE information in external reports indirectly leads to more pressure within companies to implement the topic and publish the corresponding data (Opferkuch et al. 2021: p. 4016). However, the identified weaknesses of external reporting also include the fact that certain data points can be omitted for good reason, which reduces the comparability of the reports. To strengthen the contribution of external reporting to the promotion of CE, the experts suggest that more concrete indicators for CE should be introduced and that the EU should provide more guidance and support for their introduction. The sector-specific ESRS currently under development could provide more clarity here. It is also questionable whether the simplifications planned by the EU in sustainability reporting for companies through various omnibus directives will reduce the contribution to promoting the transformation to CE at company level (EU Commission 08.11.2024). In conclusion, it can be stated that the contribution of external reporting on CE can help to promote the topic, but depends on numerous factors such as the level of

ambition of the companies and the accuracy of the auditors of the sustainability report (Falkenberg et al. 2023: p. 10).

2.2.3 Internal reporting

The results of the second SLR on the research question *Which are the relevant internal frameworks for CE reporting at micro level?* are presented in this chapter. The contained CE data and indicators are presented in more detail as well. In table 4, the most important general information on these is illustrated using various categories. This is followed by an introduction to the individual frameworks and a brief description of the CE data and indicators identified. A comprehensive list of data points for the individual frameworks can be found in the supplementary Excel file. In the data point list, the individual CE indicators of the various frameworks are listed according to different criteria, see table 2. An illustration of the results is presented for each framework separately. As already mentioned, the CE KPIs determined by companies from the empirical study are also compared with the indicators from the relevant internal CE performance frameworks. In this way, theory and practice can be compared and it can be determined which framework contains the most CE KPIs used by companies. The several indicators are analysed based on the comparison criteria defined in table 2.

Table 4: Internal reporting frameworks and standards

Criteria	Standards and frameworks		
	ISO 59020	Circulytics	CTI V4.0
Editor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ISO – International Organisation for standardisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EMF – Ellen MacArthur Foundation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) & KPMG
User group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies of all types and sizes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies of all types and sizes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies of all types and sizes
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization of the process of gathering and calculating data using mandatory and optional circularity indicators, ensuring consistent and verifiable results Structured framework for defining system boundaries, selecting suitable indicators, and interpreting data to assess circularity performance at various levels—from regional and inter-organizational to organizational and product-specific levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Framework of indicators to track the CE performance of companies It enables companies to showcase their achievements in the transition process and pinpoint areas that require attention for improvement, all in alignment with the three principles of a circular economy driven by design: eliminating waste and pollution, circulating products and materials, and regenerating nature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Framework of indicators to track the CE performance of companies Helping companies to develop insights into increasing circularity along the value chain and to reduce their impact on climate and nature

ISO 59020

The ISO is crucial for defining international harmonised standards that ensure quality, safety and efficiency for different industries and topics. The newly developed ISO 59000 series of standards provide a relevant framework for companies to integrate the concept of CE holistically into business processes and to manage the transformation to CE. The proposed indicators from the ISO standard are therefore included in the analysis. The ISO standard 59020: Circular Economy - Measuring and assessing circularity performance sets out requirements and guidance for companies to record and measure their CE performance. It was published in May 2024 and is part of the ISO 59000 family of standards, which was designed to harmonise a general understanding of CE and support its implementation. Measurement and evaluation are carried out by collecting and calculating data using mandatory and voluntary CE indicators. The standard can be applied voluntarily by companies of all legal forms, sizes and origins. Essentially, the process that companies go through to determine their CE performance is divided into 3 steps, see figure 8.

Figure 8: Framework for measuring and assessing circularity (ISO/FDIS 59020)

Firstly, the companies concerned need to define the system boundaries for the assessment. These can be the company boundaries, specific departments, product groups and parts of the upstream and downstream value chain. A time frame must also be selected. Within these system boundaries, concrete objectives are defined. The second step consists of circularity measurement and data collection. Here, suitable indicators for measuring the previously defined system boundaries and objectives are identified and the individual variables for calculating these are collected. When selecting the indicators, certain mandatory core circularity indicators must also be used. The final phase consists of the evaluation and reporting of CE performance based on the results from step 2. Circularity performance refers to how closely a set of circularity aspects aligns with the fundamental goals and principles of a CE. Part of the evaluation phase is also to assess the impact of the CE measures taken

by the companies on social, ecological and economic systems using suitable methods such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). This step is very important as it reflects the holistic nature of the measures taken and the contribution of the CE to sustainable development. The assessment of the company's circularity primarily serves internal management purposes, as improvement measures can be identified and evaluated based on the status quo.

The indicators for measuring CE are explained in more detail in Annexes A and B of the standard. They are divided into the categories of resource inflows, resource outflows, energy, water and economic performance (ISO/FDIS 59020). The supplementary Excel file contains a list of all data points of the standard and serves as a basis for comparison with the results of the surveys and interviews. ISO 59020 contains a total of 24 CE indicators. These are shown in figure 9 using the classification criteria from table 2. The „CE function” column on the left shows that the ISO indicators focus on six different internal functions for measuring CE. As with the indicators of the external CE reporting standards, most of them can be assigned to the „Resource consumption” and „Waste management” category, followed by „Material sourcing, Resource recovery, Finance and Ecodesign”. The „R-strategies” in question, which can be seen in the next column, are distributed 17% each across the circularity levels „Product circulation (Recycle, Recover)” and „Intensification of product use (rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse)”. Almost 67% of the indicators cannot be assigned to a specific R-strategy. The third column „Dimension” shows that almost 88% of the indicators are single dimensional and relate to only one of the R-strategies or circularity levels. The „Life Cycle stage” pillar shows that the ISO indicators cover all phases of the life cycle, but primarily the Make- and Take- phases with 42% and 21% respectively. The ISO focusses on measuring the impact or effect of CE measures with almost 80% of the indicators, as can be seen in the „Performance” pillar. The „Unit” category shows that all ISO indicators are quantitative.

Figure 9: Classification of CE indicators contained in the ISO 59020 standard

Circulytics

Circulytics is an assessment tool developed by the EMF and published in 2020 to measure the performance of companies on CE. It provides a comprehensive analysis of a company's resource flows and helps to accurately measure progress and understand how processes and products can be improved to minimise waste and reduce resource consumption. The tool makes it possible to identify concrete measures to optimise the resource strategy and to monitor the effectiveness of CE initiatives using a set of indicators. It is used by over 2000 companies and significantly influences the development of CE measurement. Moreover, it plays a key role in encouraging businesses worldwide to adopt circular practices. It was included in the analysis due to its empirical relevance and the ability to facilitate strategic decisions through the proposal of suitable CE indicators which could potentially be used as a CE KPI as well. It can be used by companies of all sizes and industries.

Circulytics consists of a set of indicators, definitions, case studies and assessment methods. First, some general information about the company is requested and the system boundaries of the reporting and the economic sector are defined. This categorisation determines the number and type of indicators to be calculated in the next step. The indicators are categorised as „enablers” and „outcomes” and describe the prerequisites or decisive aspects for a transformation on the one hand and measure the current circularity of the company on the other. Indicators from the enabler category are to be reported by all companies regardless of the economic sector, while the topic-specific indicators from the outcome category depend on the company's business activities. Table 5 illustrates the individual categories of the indicators.

Table 5: Overview of the indicator categories

Category	No.	Theme
Enabler	1	Strategy and Planning
Enabler	2	Innovation
Enabler	3	People and skills
Enabler	4	Operations
Enabler	5	External engagement
Outcome	6	Products and materials
Outcome	7	Services
Outcome	8	Plant, property, and equipment assets
Outcome	9	Water
Outcome	10	Energy
Outcome	11	Finance

The indicators in the enabler category are qualitative, while those in the outcome category are mostly quantitative. The indicators in the enabler category are not determined by means of calculations, but by means of semi-open questions in which the companies can choose from a range of answers. Each indicator is assigned a weight that reflects its empirical importance in the transition to a CE. The theme score is determined by calculating the weighted average of all indicator scores within a specific theme. The category score is derived by calculating the weighted average of all relevant themes within that category. Finally, both categories contribute equally to the overall score (MacArthur 2022).

A complete list of data points from Circulytics can be found in the supplementary Excel file. A total of 50 CE indicators from the Circulytics framework are analysed using the classification criteria from table 2, see figure 10. It can be seen from the outset that the indicators from Circulytics measure CE in companies holistically and include many different aspects, which are discussed in more detail below. The first pillar, „CE function”, shows the internal functions affected by the indicators. There are 10 different functions in total, but only the four largest are labelled in the chart due to space issues. These correspond to 68% of the indicators. The others are in the following order: „Strategy & Vision, Material sourcing, Finance, Training, Marketing & communication and Resource recovery”. All R-strategies are represented in the Circulytics framework, see „R-strategy” pillar. However, 72% of the indicators cannot be directly assigned to a R-strategy. The „Dimension” column shows that 90% of the indicators are assigned to a specific R-strategy. The indicators from Circulytics affect every phase of the life cycle, above all the Make- phase with 36% of the indicators, see „Life Cycle stage” pillar. The Use- phase is covered the least. Finally, a balanced distribution of transition and effect („Performance”- pillar) as well as qualitative and quantitative („Unit”- pillar) indicators is recognisable.

Figure 10: Classification of CE indicators contained in the Circulytics framework

Circular Transition Indicators (CTI) V4.0

The CTI is a framework for companies of all sizes and industries to measure their CE performance and identify potential for improvement. The framework is developed under the leadership of the WBCSD and the auditing firm KPMG in collaboration with numerous international corporations. It is

currently in its fourth edition and has already attracted thousands of users since its initial introduction. At the core of CTI is a self-assessment that evaluates a company's circularity performance. It primarily examines the flow of both circular and linear materials within the company, with design, procurement, and recovery models serving as key factors in assessing the company's overall performance. By analysing the material flows, potential for improvement can be identified regarding minimising the extraction of raw materials and the generation of waste (WBCSD und KPMG 2023: p. 7 ff.). Figure 11 shows the general logic of CTI as the basis for calculating the indicators.

Figure 11: Illustration of material flows (WBCSD und KPMG 2023: p. 14)

CTI is based on an inward-looking, quantitative, indicator-based approach that enables companies to determine the circularity of products and the entire organisation. The assessment of material flows within the company's boundaries is supplemented by indicators that evaluate resource efficiency, effectiveness, and the added value generated through circular business practices. The framework provides a wide range of indicators, which are divided into the modules „close the loop, optimise the loop, value the loop and impact of the loop“. Firstly, indicators are used to determine the company's ability to close its material, water and energy flows (close the loop). In the next step (optimise the loop), resource efficiency and higher-value circularity strategies are optionally calculated using further indicators. In the value the loop module, indicators are now optionally used to show how CE initiatives generate additional value for the company while minimising the use of raw materials. The fourth optional module (impact the loop) takes a holistic approach and is designed to help companies understand the impact of their circularity strategies on the achievement of sustainability goals (WBCSD und KPMG 2023: p. 15 ff.).

The CTI framework is included in the analysis as it could also contain potential CE KPIs that address CE transformation at strategic management level, particularly due to its internal company

perspective and holistic CE measurement using quantitative indicators. A complete list of the indicators from CTI can be found in the supplementary Excel file and serves as a basis for comparison with the results from the survey and the interviews. Figure 12 illustrates the characteristics of the 16 CE indicators of the CTI framework based on the classification criteria from table 2. The left-hand column „CE function” shows that only four internal functions are covered by the CTI indicators, with the categories „Resource consumption” and „Waste management” accounting for 82% of the indicators. This is also reflected in the pillar „Life Cycle stage”, as the Make- and EoL- phases are most frequently represented. Around 81% of the indicators focus on measuring the effect of CE actions and only a few on the transition to CE (19%), as can be seen in the „Performance” pillar. The „R-strategy” pillar shows that almost 70% of the indicators cannot be assigned to a specific strategy. The remaining indicators relate to the circularity levels of „Product circulation (Recycle, Recover)” and „Extension of product use (Repair, Refurbish, and Remanufacture)”. Finally, all the CTI indicators are single dimensional and quantitative. The characteristics of the indicators of the CTI framework are taken up again in the discussion section when comparing them with the KPIs used by companies in practise.

Figure 12: Classification of CE indicators contained in the CTI framework

2.3 CE KPIs at micro level

The following chapter summarises the current state of knowledge on CE indicators at micro level as a result of the SLR. The focus here is on analysing scientific research papers and review papers by academics regarding potential CE KPIs and classification criteria for CE indicators on micro level. The macro and meso levels of CE measurement are not considered in this research work. Firstly, the need for and objectives of CE indicators are presented. This is followed by a definition of the terms „metric”, „indicator” and „KPI” in relation to CE and criteria for a KPI are explained. The introduction of various taxonomies of CE indicators at micro level presents the current state of research by academics. Special reference is made to the classification criteria that are used to compare the KPIs determined from the empirical study with the indicators from internal and external reporting frameworks

and standards. These should allow conclusions to be drawn about the existence of potential CE KPIs in these. Finally, the most relevant academical CE indicators at micro level are briefly summarised and their practical application is discussed.

2.3.1 Need and objectives for CE indicators

The implementation of the various CE strategies and principles represents a major challenge for companies in the transition to a CE. The use of appropriate CE indicators at micro level therefore plays a crucial role in integrating a deeper understanding of CE into company processes and decisions (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 543; Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 523). There is a global consensus among academics, industry representatives and policymakers on the need for suitable micro level CE indicators to measure and manage the transformation (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 543). Companies play an integral role in the transformation of the linear economic system into a CE so they need to get equipped with suitable indicators that help to track progress and measure the effect of adopted changes (Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020: p. 3; Matos et al. 2023: p. 522). Therefore, indicators are a valuable tool providing strategic decision support in areas such as design, production, and EoL- management.

Indicators address the information needs of different stakeholders and functions within a company and are used at strategic (management) and operational level. Nevertheless, the information obtained from the indicators must be converted into suitable actions for the transformation to CE.

CE indicators can therefore be seen as an enabler of the CE transformation (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 556). In addition to indicators, various methods such as LCA can be used to identify circular improvement potentials along the product life cycle and the company's material flows (Matos et al. 2023: p. 523). In their analysis and classification of numerous micro level CE indicators, Saidani et al. conclude that companies lack concrete objectives, suitable, pragmatic indicators, knowledge of the economic benefits of circular solutions and implementation capacities when it comes to the transformation to CE. One of the core issues of CE is and remains how the transformation can be measured using suitable, practice-orientated indicators (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 543).

A central question in the development and selection of suitable indicators at micro level is which activities, processes, principles and strategies are relevant for measuring CE and whose impact should be covered by indicators. There is no consensus among academics and practitioners on this issue (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 3). This fact is reflected in the large number of indicators, instruments and frameworks developed in recent years to measure and manage CE at company level (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 544). The following considerations are intended to illustrate the complexity of the topic and provide examples of the aspects that need to be considered when measuring CE using indicators

at micro level. No claim is therefore made to completeness. Based on the core principles and strategies of CE presented in chapter 2.1.1, developed by the EMF and Potting et al., various measurement parameters can be identified. The first principle „Regenerate natural systems” by the EMF aims to reduce the consumption of raw materials for the manufacture of products in order to minimise the resulting negative environmental impacts (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 5). This principle can be achieved through various strategies, such as the increased use of renewable raw materials or secondary materials. The use of renewable energies along the entire product life cycle is a basic prerequisite. Dematerialising the usage of the product or service by developing new business models such as product service systems also contributes to this principle (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 5). Through renting, sharing, leasing or pooling business models, the benefits of the product are distributed among a larger group of users in a more demand-orientated way, thus consuming fewer raw materials.

The second principle, „Keep products and materials in use”, also aims to reduce the consumption of raw materials and the associated environmental impact (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 7). This principle can be implemented using the R-strategies, which are frequently referenced in the literature, see figure 2 in subchapter 2.1.1. These strategies are primarily used by product developers and engineers in the design phase, as this is decisive for up to 80% of the environmental impact of the product over its entire life cycle (Koller und Löwe 2010: p. 3). The central focus in the application of R-strategies should be the preservation of the benefit or value of the product or service. Accordingly, strategies with a higher circularity level should be favoured. The longer a product or material circulates in the use-cycle, the more raw materials, energy and labour are saved for the production of new products. The focus should be on the longevity of a product and the ability to reuse materials. The third principle, „Design out waste and pollution”, aims to avoid the generation of waste in all phases of the product life cycle. It is important to use renewable, non-toxic materials that can be separated and reused according to type as far as possible (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 7). Finally, CE should not only be considered within a company's own boundaries but should also include cooperation and collaboration between different players along the value chain in order to ensure the optimal reuse of resources and the avoidance of waste. Numerous indicators for measuring and managing CE activities at company level can be identified in relation to the aspects mentioned as examples and beyond. The taxonomies for CE indicators explained in the remainder of this chapter also show various key topics and provide information on which are considered particularly relevant

among academics. Several classification categories of the CE indicator taxonomies will be used in the evaluation and discussion of the theoretical and empirical results.

2.3.2 Definitions

To clarify the main research question of this thesis, which KPIs are used by companies to measure and manage the transformation to CE, it is first necessary to define the terms metric, indicator and KPI in relation to CE and to illustrate their interaction.

Metric

A metric (count, measurement) generally refers to a method for measuring a quantifiable variable. Metrics enable objectivity through the quantification of observations and are relatively easy to collect due to their one-dimensionality. The quality criteria of a metric are, for example, objectivity, validity, consistency, comparability and reproducibility (Witte 2018: p. 1 ff.). Metrics for measuring CE at micro level are, for example: *amount of waste generated in production, amount of raw materials purchased, percentage of recycled raw materials, total water consumption*. They clearly measure only one issue that could be relevant for the transformation to CE.

Metrics are included in the external reporting standards (ESRS, GRI, SASB) as well as in the inward facing CE performance frameworks (ISO 59020, CTI, Circulytics) as described in chapter 2.2. There is a great deal of uncertainty as to whether some of these metrics are also suitable as KPIs. This uncertainty is aimed at the central research question of which KPIs are used by companies to measure CE at micro level and to what extent these differ from the data of the voluntary and mandatory reporting standards.

Indicator

As Saidani et al. mention the term indicator is defined in numerous ways in the literature and there is no widely agreed definition for an indicator yet (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 545). The OECD defines an indicator as „a quantitative or qualitative factor or variable that provides a simple and reliable means to measure achievement, to reflect changes connected to an intervention, or to help assess the performance of a development actor” (OECD-Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2015). Indicators can be classified not only according to their unit (qualitative, quantitative), but also according to various other characteristics. These are explained in subchapter 2.3.3 based on different taxonomies developed by well recognised academics in that field.

By condensing complex practical issues into a single indicator, an indicator is often complex to calculate and relies on numerous input variables (Singh et al. 2012: p. 281). As with metrics, the quality criteria for indicators are objectivity, validity and reliability (Meyer 2023: p. 149). In addition,

indicators are suitable as a communication and management tool, can form the basis for investment decisions and show the progress of target achievement (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 556). With regard to CE, indicators can play a decisive role, as they are a standardised tool for communication between different actors, facilitate the exchange of information and can thus represent a potential springboard for transformation (Kalmykova et al. 2018: p. 190 f.). In comparison to indicators, metrics represent the finest level of granularity in measuring quantities whereas indicators have a broader focus (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 1). Indicators have very different uses, e.g. as a product label, as a basis for political and regulatory decisions or as a KPI at management level in companies (Linder et al. 2017: p. 547).

The external reporting standards (ESRS, GRI, SASB), internal CE performance management frameworks (ISO 59020, CTI, Circulytics) contain numerous indicators for measuring the transformation to CE. Examples for micro level CE indicators are *circular in- and outflow* from the CTI framework. These indicators are made up of individual quantitative metrics and are intended to provide information about the circularity of material flows that are purchased by the company and leave the company again. The metrics for calculation are *mass of renewable resource in- and outflows*, *mass of non-virgin resource in- and outflows* and the *total mass of resource in- and outflows* (WBCSD und KPMG 2023: p. 16).

KPI

There is no common understanding among academics as to how the term KPI is defined and which criteria should be used to define a KPI (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 545). Dominguez et al. define a KPI as follows (Domínguez et al. 2019: p. 24):

KPIs represent a set of measures focusing on those aspects of organizational performance that are the most critical for the current and future success of the organization.

A KPI is a measurable performance indicator used to review and visualise the success of certain actions as a contribution to the corporate strategy. They represent a central instrument of corporate management and are used by the executives of an organisation to evaluate actions and identify potential for improvement to ensure the achievement of the overall targets (Heintze 2023). According to Bauer, KPIs focus on measuring strategic value drivers instead of merely tracking non-essential business activities and processes (Bauer 2004).

There are several criteria commonly used in practise for selecting KPIs. The consulting company Deloitte has recommended the use of RACER criteria (relevant, acceptable, credible, easy, robust) to evaluate the indicators sustainability (Eisenmenger et al. 2016: p. 2). The frequently used acronyms

SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, time-bound), originally developed to formulate goals clearly and effectively, and CREAM (clear, relevant, economic, adequate, monitorable) are also suitable for determining KPIs (Drucker 1977);(Saidani et al. 2019: p. 556). In the context of the transformation to CE at micro level, there is no consensus among academics and practitioners on which KPIs should be used to measure and manage it. As previously mentioned, some of the existing metrics and indicators from academia, CE performance frameworks and external CE reporting standards could be suitable as KPIs, but currently there is no generally recognised and accepted set of KPIs to measure the transformation to CE at company level (Ciechan-Kujawa et al. 2024: p. 170). The aim of this research is therefore to identify the KPIs used by companies in current practise through an empirical study and to compare them with the data to be disclosed in the mandatory and voluntary CE reporting standards.

2.3.3 CE indicator taxonomies

The following subchapter presents classifications of academical CE indicators at the micro level that are relevant to this research. In recent years, many academics have developed categorisation schemes for CE indicators according to different criteria to make it easier for practitioners to select suitable indicators and to show the focus of the indicators in relation to CE relevant aspects. In the following, only the classification schemes of academics that are of particular importance for this work are presented. Thus, they do not reflect the complete current state of the art in the categorisation of CE indicators. Therefore only the taxonomies of Saidani et al., Janik and Ryszko, de Oliveira et al. and Vinante et al. are explained in more detail below (Saidani et al. 2019; Janik und Ryszko 2019; Vinante et al. 2020; Oliveira et al. 2021).

To begin with, the term taxonomy, which is frequently used by academics, should be briefly explained. The term taxonomy has its origins in biology and is used to categorise the animal and plant species living on the planet into groups based on common and different characteristics. It can also be used in relation to CE indicators at micro level and describes the classification of indicators based on previously defined criteria (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 545).

CE indicator taxonomy of Saidani et al.:

The taxonomy for CE indicators developed by Saidani et al. can be regarded as one of the most comprehensive categorisations. Based on a literature review, 55 C-indicators are first identified and then 10 classification criteria are defined. The criteria are:

1. Levels (micro, meso, macro)
2. Loops (maintain, reuse/remanufacture, recycle)

3. Performance (intrinsic, impact)
4. Perspective (actual, potential)
5. Usages (improvement, benchmarking, communication)
6. Transversality (generic, sector-specific)
7. Dimension (single, multiple)
8. Units (qualitative, quantitative)
9. Format (web-based tool, excel, formulas)
10. Sources (academics, companies, agencies)

Categories 2 „Loops”, 3 „Performance”, 7 „Dimension” and 8 „Units” are particularly relevant for the comparison of the survey results with the CE indicators of the internal and external reporting standards. The implementation or application of CE loops by companies is a central component of the transformation to CE and should therefore be covered by suitable indicators. Saidani et al. refer to the feedback loops according to the technological cycle of the butterfly diagram of the EMF (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 549; Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2025: p. 6).

In this work, the category „Loops” is converted to CE strategy, based on the 9R framework of Potting et al (Potting et al. 2017: p. 15). The CE strategy category therefore includes the 9R strategies divided into the three circularity levels „Intensification of product use, Extension of product use and Product circulation”. Measuring the application and success of the individual CE strategies in companies provides information on their circularity level and possibly also on their degree of maturity in measuring and implementing the CE transformation. The application of higher circularity strategies can be seen as an indication for a higher degree of maturity of the companies. It is particularly relevant at strategic management level to measure the monetary and environmental impact of the application of R-strategies.

The „Performance” category is another central component of circularity measurement and is divided into intrinsic- (transition) and impact- (effect) indicators. Transition indicators measure changes in the state or dynamics of a system over time, while impact indicators show the results or effects of these changes. In relation to the transformation to CE, they record the change process from linear to circular in the application of R-strategies on the one hand and the actual effects of these changes or strategy implementations on the other (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 549 f.). Effect indicators are highly relevant for the management of companies, as they measure the actual results and therefore the success of CE activities.

Furthermore, indicators can be differentiated according to their dimension. Single dimensional indicators measure only one specific aspect of CE, while multidimensional indicators include various aspects. The choice of single- or multidimensional indicators therefore depends heavily on their respective purpose. Single dimensional indicators can form a suitable basis for decision-making for the management of companies, as they are clear and easy to understand so that concrete recommendations for action can be derived quickly. Multidimensional indicators require more specific background knowledge as they include several factors or CE strategies. They can be useful for product designers or engineers as they measure the effects of activities involving several R-strategies or input factors (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 550).

The „Unit” category is also relevant for the comparison of indicators, as they differ in terms of their measurability. Quantitative indicators can be clearly measured and linked to targets, making them well suited for controlling and monitoring CE measures. Qualitative indicators are less precise but can also play an important role as they reveal cultural changes (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 550).

CE indicator taxonomy of Janik and Ryszko:

Janik and Ryszko identified 19 CE indicators at micro level based on a SLR and an analysis of relevant articles, studies and reports and included them in their study. These are compared based on 11 criteria to assess potential advantages and disadvantages as well as their suitability as KPIs from a managerial perspective. The application of the criteria and the associated subjective assessment of the indicators takes place in several individual and joint rounds with experts, including feedback loops.

The criteria are as follows (Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 527):

1. Core 4R framework embracing 4R principles, i.e. reduce, reuse, recycle, recover
2. Sustainable development components, i.e. economic, environmental, social
3. Life cycle perspective (material sourcing, production, consumption/use, end-of-life/disposal)
4. Complexity of analysed aspects, i.e. input and use of natural resources, emission levels, valuable material losses, share of renewable and recyclable resources, product durability
5. Application level, i.e. material, component, product/service
6. Dimensionality, i.e. single indicator, multiple indicators
7. Format, i.e. textual formulas, computational tool, web-based-tool
8. Time consumption of adequate indicator application
9. Scope and detail of the required data
10. Required specialized knowledge and competence to apply indicator
11. Supporting the decision-making process

Some of the criteria used are in line with those of Saidani et al (Saidani et al. 2019; Janik und Ryszko 2019). However, criteria 8-10 were used specifically to assess the suitability of the CE indicators analysed as potential KPIs for companies. This represents an interesting, novel approach to assessment that has not previously been undertaken by academics or practitioners. However, Janik and Ryszko's criteria for identifying CE KPIs at the micro level are not used to compare the results of the empirical study with those of internal and external reporting standards and frameworks, as the assessment is very subjective on the one hand and requires in-depth expertise from both practitioners in companies and researchers on the other. The presentation serves only the purpose of providing a more comprehensive picture of the state of knowledge in relation to the identification of practice-orientated CE KPIs for the management of companies.

CE indicator taxonomy of Vinante et al.:

In their research, Vinante et al. analyse over 130 documents from academics dealing with CE metrics and identify 365 different CE metrics at company level. These are classified and analysed based on the functions and departments (stakeholders) affected by CE assessment within a company. Firstly, relevant stakeholders within the company are identified. The value chain framework (PVC) by Michael Porter is used for this purpose. The various PVC categories are assigned 23 categories relevant to the transformation to CE and a circular value chain framework (cVC) is developed. Figure 13 shows the relationship of the PVC categories and the developed cVC categories.

Circular Value Chain categories	Porters' Value Chain categories
Strategy & vision	Firm infrastructure
Business model	
Environmental management	
Cooperation & industrial symbiosis	HR management
Training	
Employee satisfaction & participation	
Ecodesign	Technology development
Supplier selection & auditing	Procurement
Material sourcing	Inbound & outbound Logistics
Direct logistics	
Reverse logistics	
Resource consumption: energy	Operations
Resource consumption: water	
Resource consumption: materials	
Waste management: solid	
Waste management: liquid	
Waste management: gaseous	
Resource recovery: energy	
Resource recovery: water	Marketing & sales
Resource recovery: materials	
Marketing & communication	
Green products performance	Service
Post-sales services	

Figure 13: Mapping of the 23 cVC categories and the PVC categories, adopted by (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 6)

Metrics that are strongly linked to the management and decision-making processes of an organisation are associated with the firm infrastructure. As the social assessment in CE assessments is almost

exclusively focussed on measuring employee-related metrics, these can be transferred to HR management. The evaluation of the corporate approach to circular design practices falls under the category of ecodesign and can be linked to technology development. Direct logistics, enabled by appropriate procurement practices, is closely linked to reverse logistics to create a closed resource loop. The CE metrics associated with an organisation's production processes, including the consumption and recovery of resources and handling of waste generated, belong to the category of operations. Finally, the activities aimed at conveying added value to customers and generating the resulting economic performance belong to the areas of marketing, sales and service (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 6 f.). The classification of Vinante et al. thus generates valuable insights into the stakeholders and functions that are affected by the measurement of CE performance within a company.

For the evaluation and comparison of the KPIs used by companies from the empirical study with the indicators from relevant internal and external reporting standards and frameworks, the classification is of particular importance, as it provides information about the functions of a company affected by CE measurement. Accordingly, these should be included in centralised corporate management of the CE transition at the strategic level by defining suitable KPIs. This classification is also relevant in terms of answering the research question of which functions are affected by the transformation to CE. This is specifically addressed in subchapter 2.4.

CE indicator taxonomy of de Oliveira et al.:

In their analysis, De Oliveira et al. identified 58 CE indicators at the micro level based on their connection to the three sustainability dimensions (economy, ecology, social) and the phases of the life cycle (take, make, use, recover and EoL). The classification of the CE indicators based on the life cycle phases concerned is of particular importance for this work, as measures to improve the circularity of products and materials have an influence on various phases of the life cycle and their success should be addressed by means of suitable indicators. The classification helps decision-makers in operations and strategic management to understand what impact the individual measures have on the phases of the product life cycle. Accordingly, all product life cycle phases should be covered by indicators in order to provide a holistic picture of circularity (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 461 ff.).

2.3.4 Academical CE indicators and KPIs

This subchapter presents examples of CE indicators at micro level that have been developed by academics and researchers in this field. The presentation is intended to show the CE indicators most frequently mentioned in the literature by academics and classified according to various criteria. In identifying the indicators, 10 review papers on micro level CE indicators are analysed by various

academics and more than 100 indicators are initially identified, see (Matos et al. 2023; Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020; Saidani et al. 2019; Janik und Ryszko 2019; Corona et al. 2019; Oliveira et al. 2021; Pascale et al. 2021; Jerome et al. 2022; Moraga et al. 2019).

The indicators most frequently analysed by the selected academics are then filtered out. Table 6 shows the 20 most relevant CE indicators. In addition to the indicators most frequently analysed by academics, the indicators identified by Janik and Ryszko using their taxonomy for CE KPIs are listed in table 7. All of these are deliberately not analysed and classified further, as they have hardly been used in business practice to date. This is mainly due to their complexity in calculation, data availability and multidimensionality (Matos et al. 2023: p. 522).

The presentation of the indicators is therefore only intended to reflect the current state of knowledge in the field for the sake of completeness. A comparison of these academic indicators with the results of the online survey would not provide any additional insights into which CE indicators are used as KPIs in companies.

Table 6: Relevant academical micro-level CE indicators

Indicator	Abbreviation	Mentions	Source
Circular Economy Index	CEI	7	(Di Maio und Rem 2015)
Circular Economy Indicator Prototype	CEIP	8	(Cayzer et al. 2017)
Circular Economy Performance Indicator	CEPI	7	(Huysman et al. 2017)
Circular Economy Toolkit	CET	5	(Evans und Bocken 2013)
Circular Economy Value	CEV	4	(Fogarassy et al. 2017)
Circular Pathfinder	CP	4	(The ResCoM platform and tools 2017)
Circularity Calculator	CC	6	(The ResCoM platform and tools 2017)
Circularity Index	CI	5	(Cullen 2017)
Disassembly Effort Index	DIE	4	(Das et al. 2000)
Ease of Disassembly Metric	eDIM	5	(Vanegas et al. 2018)
Eco-cost/ value creation	EVR	10	(Scheepens et al. 2016)
End-of-Life Recycling Rates	EoL-RRs	4	(Graedel et al. 2011)
Longevity Indicator	LI	6	(Franklin-Johnson et al. 2016)
Material Circularity Indicator	MCI	9	(MacArthur 2015)
Material Reutilization Score	MRS	6	(McDonough 2016)
Product Level Circularity Metric	PLCM	5	(Linder et al. 2017)
Recycling Desirability Index	RDI	4	(Mohamed Sultan et al. 2017)
Reuse Potential Indicator	RPI	8	(Park und Chertow 2014)
Sustainable Circular Index	SCI	5	(Azevedo et al. 2017)
Value based resource efficiency	VRE	6	(Di Maio et al. 2017)

Table 7: *Academical KPIs identified by Janik and Ryszko*

KPI	Abbreviation	Source
Circular Economy Indicator Prototype	CEIP	(Cayzer et al. 2017)
Circular Economy Toolkit	CET	(Evans und Bocken 2013)
Circular Pathfinder	CP	(The ResCoM platform and tools 2017)
Circularity Calculator	CC	(The ResCoM platform and tools 2017)
Circularity Potential Indicator	CPI	(Saidani et al. 2017)
Closed loop Calculator	CLC	(Kingfisher 2014)
Input-Output Balance Sheet	IOBS	(Capellini 2017)
Material Circularity Indicator	MCI	(MacArthur 2015)

2.3.5 Key research findings on CE indicators

One of the challenges highlighted in the literature is the absence of metrics that measure circularity at the micro-level (individual products and services) (Elia et al. 2017: p. 2741). As a result of their classification of numerous CE indicators at micro level, Saidani et al. conclude that the assertion by Elia et al. only partially corresponds to reality and that numerous indicators have been developed in recent years. However, these are inconsistent in their scope, purpose and possible application and still need to be further developed.

The reasons given for this are a lack of academic and scientific knowledge as well as diverging definitions and understandings of the concept of CE. Therefore, the taxonomy of existing indicators should on the one hand show the progress in relation to CE measurement and its practical use and at the same time facilitate the selection of suitable indicators.

The main findings are that most indicators relate to recycling and remanufacturing strategies. In addition, more than half of the indicators are single dimensional and do not include several of the R-strategies in their measurement (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 551 f.). Janik and Ryszko come to an identical conclusion in their analysis of existing CE indicators (Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 531 f.). Furthermore, only a few indicators measure the impact (effect) of R-strategies and show economic or ecological benefits.

Saidani's findings are consistent with those of Elia et al. in that they claim that there are hardly any indicators that show a holistic picture of the CE transformation and often only focus on a single dimension, such as recycling (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 551; Elia et al. 2017: p. 2746). As a solution, Saidani et al. suggest combining several indicators with methods such as consequential LCA to specifically identify trade-offs in the application of various R-strategies (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 554). In their classification of indicators based on the phases of the product life cycle (take, make, use, recover and

EoL), De Oliveira et al. conclude that most of the indicators analysed include several phases. The take-, make- and use- phases are the least covered in this order. The recover- or EoL- phase is most frequently covered by indicators. The focus of the indicators is therefore on measuring closed resource cycles and material circulation (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 462).

These results are in line with the studies by Saidani and Janik & Ryszko, who identified recycling as the main R-strategy covered by indicators (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 551; Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 531). Other well-known authors in the field of CE indicators also share this assessment. Kristensen & Mosgaard point out that R-strategies of higher circularity levels, such as reuse, are less frequently used in indicators (Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020: p. 13).

Referring to this, Matos et al. state that the reason for the lower relevance of reuse is that it cannot be reconciled with the current, traditional production patterns and strategies of the industry (Matos et al. 2023: p. 522). De Oliveira et al. cite the longer historical debate on various EoL utilisation options as a reason for the dominance of the recycling strategy in the indicators (Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 466). This is also reflected in the waste management hierarchy developed by the EU (EU Parliament and council 19.11.2008).

Ghissellini et al. hypothesise that R-strategies with lower circularity levels are therefore increasingly being used in practice. There is still a need for research into the development of indicators that measure the use of higher circularity strategies (Ghissellini et al. 2016: p. 25). The results of the classification by Vinante et al. show that all categories of the PVC, i.e. all stakeholders within the company, play a role in the CE assessment, but that these vary greatly in their extent. For example, most of the indicators (over 80%) are assigned to the categories of operations, firm infrastructure and technology development. The large number of indicators in these categories is due to their interrelated role.

Business strategy and management are tasked with guiding the value chain towards circular business models, which, fueled by sustainable and innovation-driven technological advancements, direct the production sector towards creating value-adding products. The operations category is the most relevant category with more than 40%. It includes key figures on resource consumption, waste management and resource utilisation. Ecodesign is measured with the most indicators in relation to the cVC categories (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 10). This is in line with the results of Saidani and Janik & Ryszko, as this category contains many indicators relating to the recycling strategy (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 551; Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 531).

The direct & reverse logistics categories are barely covered by metrics, although these are essential enablers for closing material loops. To achieve tangible and lasting results, all areas of the company should be involved in the implementation and evaluation of the level of performance against CE principles (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 12).

Another important finding is that there are sector-specific CE indicators in addition to cross-sector indicators. Indicators of a food processing company, e.g. dairy products company, differ from those of a telecommunications company. A dairy product company depends on material resources, water, energy and packaging materials and will have indicators related to that while these indicators could be irrelevant for a telecommunication company (Patil et al. 2023: p. 77). One of the aims of this work is also to clarify the research question of whether sector-specific or cross-sector indicators can be identified based on the indicators used by the companies surveyed. It will also be interesting to see whether the results of the academics in relation to the different focus areas of the CE indicators can be confirmed by comparing the indicators from the empirical study with those from the internal and external reporting frameworks and standards.

2.3.6 Practical use of CE indicators

The increased interest of scientists and academics in the development and classification of CE indicators is reflected in the large number of indicators published in recent years. This is desirable on the one hand but makes it more difficult for companies to select suitable indicators. As already mentioned, not only the development of CE indicators depends on a subjective understanding of the CE concept, but also their practical application (Kalmykova et al. 2018: p. 190). Their practical application is further hampered by the quite complex calculation which relies on insufficiently available input factors across the value chain (Potting et al. 2017: p. 4) Matos et al. point out that a large number of quantitative indicators at micro level are dependent on external data (Matos et al. 2023: p. 521).

Furthermore, the calculation is time-consuming, requires specialised expertise and ties up valuable resources (Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 532). Small and medium-sized companies in particular lack the expertise and resources to measure CE (Patil et al. 2023: p. 7). The selection of suitable indicators should therefore be orientated towards the needs of the company (Janik und Ryszko 2019: p. 532). It is also important to note that many of the CE indicators examined focus on only one specific CE strategy (single dimensional), so that their application can lead to sub-optimisation when deriving measures (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 554). As long as there is no general, uniform, recognised standard for measuring CE, it is not possible to be sure that measures are going in the right direction and that

the desired effect is being achieved (Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020: p. 16). Companies need to understand the benefits and relevance of CE indicators so that the information gained from them can be incorporated into management decisions (Park und Kremer 2017: p. 804).

In general, despite the taxonomies developed, there is a great deal of disagreement among researchers as to which CE indicators are used in practice and which would be particularly suitable as KPIs at strategic management level. This research work is intended to pick up at this point and provide insights into which KPIs are used in practice based on an empirical study of companies in various sectors.

2.4 Affected operational functions of CE

This subchapter presents the results of the SLR on the internal stakeholders and functions affected by the transformation to CE at micro level. The results are intended to answer the sub-research question 6: *Which functions are affected by the CE at micro level in general?* The results of the SLR represent the theoretical basis and will be confirmed or refuted by the results of the empirical investigations and if necessary, further affected functions will be determined. The identification of the relevant internal stakeholders and functions for measuring and transforming the CE provides information on which of these play a decisive role in the transformation and should be integrated into strategic decision-making processes by defining suitable indicators or KPIs to measure the success or transition of certain activities.

Various stakeholders are involved in the establishment of a CE at company level. They face numerous challenges and hurdles in the transition to a CE that can only be overcome together if all affected stakeholders are involved to fulfil the overall goal of achieving a CE at company level. Identifying the relevant stakeholders and functions and defining associated indicators that measure the transition to CE can also form the basis for a CE management tool or a KPI dashboard that supports decision-making at management level. Two sources were identified as particularly relevant in this context. The results of these are presented and compared below. Through an SLR of 38 CE documents, frameworks and case studies, Barros et al. identified nine internal functions that are most affected by the transformation to CE, see figure 14 (Barros et al. 2021: p. 4).

Figure 14: Key CE functions of sustainable business management, adapted by (Barros et al. 2021: p. 4)

According to Barros et al., „**Strategic planning (SP)**“ plays a central role in the transformation to CE and should be harmonised with the strategies and concepts of CE (Barros et al. 2021: p. 3). By developing new business models based on the principles of CE, such as closed material loops, the profitability and value creation of companies can be secured. Organizations can strategically shape their business models to enhance the circularity of their supply chains by encouraging their suppliers to adopt practices like recycling products and reusing materials/resources, thereby making circular business models fully feasible (Geissdoerfer et al. 2018: p. 764).

„**Cost management (CM)**“ or cost controlling, located in the finance department, represents the second important pillar. The reuse of products at the end of the use- phase and the reuse of production waste to manufacture new products harbours potential cost savings in relation to the purchase of new raw materials. This would also reduce the environmental damage caused by the extraction and processing of primary raw materials and reduce dependencies on price-volatile raw materials markets, which arise, for example, as a result of resource shortages (Barros et al. 2021: p. 3 f.). However, the current relatively low prices on the raw materials markets and initial high investments in adequate processing plants are obstacles to this approach (Barros et al. 2021: p. 3 f.). In addition, the reprocessing and reuse of production waste and discarded products in production can be associated not only with high financial but also ecological burdens. Therefore, when weighting up such actions, a holistic view is necessary, which can be achieved using supporting methods such as LCA.

The next pillar is „**Circular supply chain management (CSCM)**“. Cooperation with the up- and downstream value chain can improve the circularity of products and materials used. Product return

systems at the end of the utilisation phase also promote independence from external raw material flows.

„**Quality management (QM)**” in companies ensures compliance with standards and specifications relating to product quality. It represents the fourth important pillar in the transformation to CE to counteract the negative customer perception that products made from recycled materials are not of the same quality as new goods. It is therefore essential to establish QM- systems and standards for the use of secondary raw materials in products to counteract a negative brand image (Barros et al. 2021: p. 5).

CE principles are obviously strongly linked to a company's „**Environmental management (EM)**”. In general, the implementation of CE oriented actions is not associated with an improved environmental performance of the company, as trade-offs or rebound effects can arise. The reprocessing or recovery of raw materials contained in products for reuse in production to achieve the same quality standards as the primary raw material can be associated with significant environmental impacts (transport, energy, processes etc.). The ecological advantage of the avoided environmental impacts could therefore not outweigh the newly generated ones (Pádua Pieroni et al. 2018: p. 800). As already mentioned, the use of the LCA methodology is particularly suitable for decision-making and deriving measures. It can be described as a key tool in modern environmental management, designed to increase awareness of the potential environmental impacts associated with products. It aims to assess the environmental aspects and possible impacts throughout the entire life cycle of a process, product, or service (Salvador et al. 2021: p. 2).

The sixth pillar, „**Process management (PM)**”, refers to the reinvention of production processes that are intended to promote various R-strategies. For example, products should be produced in such a way that they can be reused or repaired more easily at the end of the use- phase. This can be achieved e.g. through a modular design or by making it easier to disassemble and dismantle the product. The central objective of production processes is also to avoid waste. In this context, the formation of industrial symbioses can be useful, so that the waste produced by one company serves as raw materials for another.

The next pillar, „**Logistics and reverse logistics (L&LR)**” can be seen as an enabler for closed material cycles. Sharing transport services among industries can increase the load factor and avoid unnecessary transport. The formation of partnerships for reverse logistics enables the application of various R-strategies, such as recycling, remanufacturing or repairing, and promotes the cascading of resources. For this to succeed, however, a cultural change and the sensitisation of consumers in dealing

with discarded products and the introduction of product take-back systems is also necessary (Barros et al. 2021: p. 6).

The next category, „**Service management (SM)**”, includes the development of product service systems, such as sharing business models, which are intended to intensify the use of long-lasting products and thus reduce the use of new raw materials. In this way, resource consumption can be decoupled from economic growth and even more people can get access to a wide range of quality products without necessarily owning them (Heyes et al. 2018: p. 626).

The last important internal function for the transition to CE is „**Research and Development (R&D)**”. The application of the various R-strategies plays an important role in the development and design phase of new products. The decisions made here largely determine the circularity and negative environmental impact of a product over its entire life cycle. This phase is also the starting point for product innovations and thus the generation of potential competitive advantages (Barros et al. 2021: p. 7). Vinante et al. took a slightly different approach to identifying the internal functions relevant to the transition to CE. As a result of an SLR of over 130 documents, 365 company-specific CE metrics were identified. These were assigned to the various operational functions. Based on the PVC framework, a new cVC framework with 23 functions important for the transition to CE was developed. Figure 15 illustrates the connection between the PVC categories and those of the cVC framework (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 7).

Figure 15: Relationship between the PVC and the cVC, adopted by (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 7)

The relevance of the individual PVC categories in relation to the CE has already been explained in more detail in subchapter 2.3.3 and will not be discussed further here. When identifying relevant

operational functions for the transformation to the CE, Vinante et al. and Barros et al. arrive at largely similar results despite their different approach and the naming of the functions, see table 8. Almost every function identified by Barros et al. can be assigned to a category of the cVC framework of Vinante et al. despite „Cost management (CM)”, as the finance department is not mentioned in the PVC framework.

However, the cVC framework is much more granular than the categorisation developed by Barros et al. and is based on the interdisciplinary recognised PVC framework, which allows a direct assignment of the functions relevant for CE to the primary and supporting activities of a company, originally developed by Michael Porter (Porter 1985). The great importance of the R&D or Technology Development function with Ecodesign as the associated cVC category is emphasised by both authors. Vinante et al. assign most of the identified CE metrics to this category and stresses that product design optimizes the use of secondary raw materials, simplifies disassembly for disposal, and promotes repairing (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 12). The decisions made in the design phase are decisive for up to 80% of the environmental impact of a product throughout its entire life cycle (Koller und Löwe 2010: p. 3). The product development process should therefore consider the application of the various R-strategies and core principles of CE.

Finally, the assignment of CE indicators from the relevant internal and external reporting standards and performance frameworks to the internal functions in accordance with the cVC framework makes it possible to determine which of these pursues a holistic approach to CE measurement and reporting. Furthermore, by assigning the CE KPIs of companies surveyed to the cVC categories, a statement can be made about the extent to which they integrate the topic of CE holistically into their business processes and cover it with corresponding indicators. In addition, the results of the empirical studies can be used to identify further internal functions that are relevant for the transition to CE and to confirm or refute the academics' findings in relation to the dominance of the R&D category.

Table 8: Comparison of the relevant operational functions for the CE

PVC categories	cVC categories (Vinante et al.)	Key CE functions (Barros et al.)
Firm infrastructure	Strategy & Vision	Strategic Planning (SP)
	Business model	
	Environmental management	Environmental management (EM)
	Cooperation & industrial symbiosis	Circular supply chain management (CSCM)
HR management	Training	-
	Employee satisfaction & participation	-
Technology Development	Ecodesign	Research & Development (R&D)
Procurement	Supplier selection & auditing	-
	Material sourcing	-
Inbound & outbound logistics	Direct logistics	Logistics and reverse logistics (L&RL)
	Reverse logistics	
Operations	Resource Consumption: energy	Process management (PM)
	Resource Consumption: water	
	Resource Consumption: materials	
	Waste management: solid	
	Waste management: liquid	
	Waste management: gaseous	
	Resource recovery: energy	
	Resource recovery: water	
Resource recovery: materials		
Marketing & Sales	Marketing & communication	Quality management (QM)
Service	Post-sales services	Service management (SM)
-	-	Cost management (CM)

3 Approach and research design

This chapter describes the research questions and the methodological approach in more detail. Various scientific methods are used to clarify the research questions. Firstly, a SLR is carried out to collect the already known theoretical findings on the individual topics of the research work. Building on this, an online survey is conducted with selected companies to gain practical knowledge of the use and application of CE KPIs at micro level. Finally, the findings from the online survey are deepened through qualitative interviews with some voluntary companies, which are already dealing with CE in more depth.

3.1 Research Questions

The formulation of the central research questions serves to define the framework for the study with regard to the distinction between the CE data of external non-financial sustainability reporting standards and the CE KPIs used by companies in practice (Tranfield et al. 2003: p. 213; Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 145 ff.). To close the existing research gaps, which is further described throughout chapter 3, the following research questions are developed and analysed:

Main research question:

1. *Which internal KPIs are used in companies to measure, manage and successfully implement the CE and how do these differ from the metrics and processes to be disclosed in external reports?*

To answer the main research question, the following sub-research questions will be addressed:

1. *Which are the current main mandatory and voluntary standards for CE reporting at micro level?*
2. *What kind of metrics on the CE at micro level, are currently reported within the main mandatory and voluntary standards?*
3. *To what extent does the data from main mandatory and voluntary external reporting standards contribute to measure, manage and implement the CE in companies?*
4. *Which internal KPIs for measuring and managing CE at micro level are used?*
5. *Can general internal KPIs on the CE be derived or are these sector- or company-specific?*
6. *Which functions are affected by the CE at micro level in general?*
7. *What lessons can be learned for setting up an internal management tool for the CE on micro level?*

3.2 Systematic literature review

The first step in formulating these research questions consists of a SLR to collect existing knowledge about CE indicators and identify the research gap. In this process, research hypotheses are formulated that need to be confirmed or refuted by the subsequent empirical studies. The relevant external non-financial sustainability reporting standards for companies were identified using an internet search. A SLR was not carried out at this point, as these could be identified quickly and easily and were agreed with the supervisors.

The SLR is organised according to the following subject areas:

1. Potential contribution of external, non-financial sustainability reporting standards to promote and drive the transformation to CE at company level

The identification of relevant external non-financial sustainability reporting standards and the CE indicators respectively potential KPIs contained therein serves as a basis for comparison with the results of the empirical study. In this way, the research question can be answered as to what extent the CE data from the external non-financial sustainability reporting standards differ from the CE KPIs used in practice and whether they contribute to CE transformation at company level.

2. Identification of relevant internal CE performance frameworks and the CE indicators contained therein

The indicators contained in relevant internal CE performance frameworks help companies to measure their CE performance using suitable indicators. A comparison of the indicators contained therein with the results of the empirical study serves to identify potential CE KPIs from these frameworks. This step is completed and agreed with the supervisors to obtain a holistic result on the application of potential CE KPIs at micro level.

3. State of knowledge regarding the development, classification and use of CE indicators and KPIs to measure the transformation to CE at micro level

The presentation of the current state of research on the development, classification and use of CE indicators and KPIs creates the theoretical basis for measuring CE transformation at the micro level. The aim is to sharpen the understanding of the concept of CE and to identify important principles and strategies that need to be measured using suitable indicators. In addition, a taxonomy for CE indicators will be established based on the findings of academics in that field to elucidate the similarities and differences between the KPIs used by companies and those of the relevant internal and external standards and frameworks. The results of the SLR on existing CE indicators and KPIs will be

compared with the results of the empirical study to fill the research gap and to confirm or refute the hypotheses put forward.

4. Identification of internal stakeholders and functions that are affected by the measurement of CE through indicators

The identification of internal stakeholders and functions affected by the transformation to CE serves to define relevant KPIs. Important processes and activities for the transformation can be assigned to these and should therefore be included in the development of potential CE KPIs. The stakeholders and functions identified from the SLR are confirmed or refuted with the findings of the empirical study and if possible, further ones are determined. In addition to formulating the research questions, the following steps are carried out: „Definition of data sources and search operators“, „Definition of selection and exclusion criteria“, „Active search“, „Qualitative content analysis“ and „Presentation of results“ (Denyer und Tranfield 2009: p. 673 ff.; Tranfield et al. 2003: p. 213). These are explained in more detail in the following sections.

3.2.1 Data sources and research operators

The databases "Science Direct" and "Wiley Online Library", which are freely accessible to members of the University of Pforzheim, are used as data sources. In addition, the search engine „Google Scholar“, which accesses numerous databases, is used to identify further scientific literature. The main sources for this work come from scientific journals such as the „Journal of Cleaner Production“ or „Resources, Conservation and Recycling“ and „Sustainable Production and Consumption“. The articles published there undergo a peer-review process, which ensures the quality of the content of the research results.

As there is already a large amount of literature available on the subject of CE, search term combinations are used to narrow down the research (Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 160). In addition, the research is conducted in English, as scientific publications are often written in English and a larger database can therefore be generated (Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 20). An SLR is carried out on four different topics and corresponding search term combinations were defined. The generic term „Circular Economy“ is always used, but the individual SLRs differed in their specific sub-terms. In principle, all SLRs contribute to answering the main research question.

However, the final answer to this question is only possible by comparing the indicators of the respective standards with those of the empirical study. The focus of the first SLR is on answering the question of the extent to which external reporting on CE contributes to driving the transformation to CE within companies. The second SLR serves to identify other relevant CE reporting and

performance measurement frameworks. The third SLR summarises the current state of research in the field of CE indicators including the relevant principles and strategies for measuring CE transformation at the micro level and how a taxonomy for CE indicators could look like. Finally, the fourth SLR serves to identify the internal stakeholders and functions that play an important role in the transformation to CE and should therefore be included in the definition of KPIs.

The various search strings are listed in table 9. These are constantly adapted during the active search. The most relevant results are generated using the search strings shown in table 9. The search is also not limited to Germany to not exclude any relevant articles. During the active search, the decision is made to limit the articles from 2016-2025. This is chosen partly because of the adoption of the first EU Circular Economy Action Plan in 2015 and partly because the interest of academics and practitioners in CE indicators has increased significantly since 2016, as evidenced by the number of publications on micro level CE indicators (Kristensen und Mosgaard 2020: p. 7; EU Commission 2015).

Table 9: Search strings of the SLR's

SLR	Research question	Search string
1	To what extent does the data from main mandatory and voluntary external reporting standards contribute to measure, manage and implement the CE in companies?	Circular Economy AND Reporting AND CSRD AND ESRS AND GRI AND SASB AND Promotion
2	Which are the relevant internal frameworks for CE reporting at micro level?	Circular Economy AND Micro level AND Standards AND Frameworks
3	Which internal KPIs for measuring and managing CE at micro level are used?	Circular Economy AND Micro level AND Indicators AND KPIs
4	Which functions are affected by the CE at micro level in general?	Circular Economy AND Micro level AND Functions

3.2.2 Selection and exclusion criteria

The definition of exclusion criteria is necessary to ensure the appropriate quality of the literature and to exclude irrelevant information (Page et al. 2021: p. 5). The exclusion criteria are listed in table 10.

Table 10: Exclusion criteria, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)

Criteria	Exclusion criterion	Quantity
Scope of publication	Inappropriate scope of research	24
	Too detailed sector focus	10
	Introduction of methods instead of indicators	8
	Focus of the indicators on sustainability dimensions	3
	Focus on individual indicators/tools	14
Access	Access restricted	4
Language	no German or English language	2
Duplications	Duplications	15
Excluded articles		80

3.2.3 Active search

The SLR is divided into five different phases and is based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) scheme (Page et al. 2021: p. 5). The individual phases are listed in figure 16. The first step of the SLR is identifying relevant sources using the search strings for the individual SLR topics in the respective databases. A very large number of potentially relevant sources is identified. These are then further reduced by narrowing down the number of years. The sources are then analysed based on their title, abstract and exclusion criteria, defined in table 2. After these steps, 34 sources are narrowed down as particular relevant for the research work. These are then assigned to the four SLRs, imported into the citation software and analysed in terms of content. These are divided into 3 sources for SLR 1, 3 sources for SLR 2, 26 sources for SLR 3 and 2 sources for SLR 4. As the scientific search engine „Google Scholar” also accesses the „Wiley” and „Science Direct” databases, only a few new relevant sources are identified, as many articles are duplicated.

Figure 16: SLR procedure according to PRISMA, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)

3.2.4 Qualitative content analysis

The final step of the SLRs consist of the qualitative content analysis. The analysis technique is based on Mayring's inductive categorisation (Mayring 2010: p. 602). However, this is only applied to the sources identified in SLR 3. The sources of SLR 1, SLR 2 and SLR 4 could be analysed manually due to their manageable number. The content of the identified sources is first categorised. This approach is particularly suitable for SLR 3, as there are many relevant sources here and only individual text passages are important for answering the research question. Codes are now assigned to these categories to systematically analyse the information from these recurring individual topics. The decision is made in favour of inductive categorisation, as new categories are always identified when reading the articles. Table 11 illustrates the categorisation and coding.

Table 11: Inductive category system, based on (Mayring 2010: p. 609)

Category	Coding
Need for CE indicators	Measuring CE transition
	Decision support
	CE strategies
	CE principles
Definitions	Metric
	Indicator
	KPI
	Criteria for KPIs
CE indicator taxonomies	CE strategy
	Performance
	Dimension
	Unit
	life cycle phases
CE indicators	Academical CE indicators
	Academical CE KPIs
Practical use of CE indicators	Complex calculation
	Data availability
	Dimensionality
	Time consuming
	Specialised knowledge

3.2.5 Presentation of results

The results of the qualitative content analysis are presented throughout chapter 2.

3.3 Online survey

Based on the results of the SLR, an online survey is conducted with companies of specific sectors and sizes. The targeted online survey was chosen because it is particularly suited to reaching a large number of companies and collecting CE KPIs used in practice. The effort for the companies concerned is also manageable. The results of the online survey serve to reflect the theoretical findings from the SLRs and provide insights into corporate practice regarding the use of CE KPIs. The guidelines by Föhl and Friedrich are used for the design and implementation of the online survey (Föhl und Friedrich 2022). The following sections describe the individual working steps and the methodological approach in more detail.

3.3.1 Planning

During the planning phase of the survey, a mixed approach of qualitative and quantitative measurement is chosen (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 3 ff.). The questions are formulated in a way that

participants could choose from pre-defined response options and at the same time make individual additions. This approach allows for a quantitative assessment of the CE KPIs used by the companies and leaves room for explanation through open response options. This approach is necessary to capture the CE KPIs used by the companies as completely as possible. A web-based online questionnaire is chosen because it is a suitable way of reaching a large number of potential participants and makes it easy to answer the questions (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 6 ff.). This type of survey also ensures that the quality criterion of objectivity of the interviewees is met (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 22).

3.3.2 Content and Layout

The second step consists of the content and formal design of the questionnaire. Formally, the questionnaire is divided into an introduction, a body and a conclusion (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 84 ff.). At the beginning, general instructions on how to complete the questionnaire are explained. The introduction section consists of general, easy-to-answer questions to ensure a gentle introduction. The main section focuses on validating, confirming the thesis and identifying CE KPIs relevant to companies based on the previous SLR.

Table 12 provides an overview of the criteria that led to the inclusion of a research question or CE KPI. The final part consists of an acknowledgement and a request for an in-depth expert interview. The structuring and arrangement of the questions and KPIs within the questionnaire is based on the elements of Michael Porter's operational value chain and asks for possible CE-oriented KPIs for each of these elements (Vinante et al. 2020: p. 6). A short explanatory text on each element of the value chain and its relevance to CE introduces participants to the questions. In addition, specific graphics are included to clarify certain issues and avoid misunderstandings. These supporting text and graphic elements are used to increase the reliability of the answers (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 22).

In terms of question formats, a mix of closed, semi-open and open-ended questions is chosen to capture specific information while allowing respondents to provide individual responses that might be relevant to the research findings (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 32 f.). Care is also taken to ensure that the questions are precise and targeted to secure a high level of validity and quality of responses. In addition, specific definitions of terms and explanatory texts in easy-to-understand, non-judgemental language prevent misinterpretations (Föhl und Friedrich 2022: p. 22 f.). The final survey questionnaire can be found in annex 1.

Table 12: Criteria for selecting KPIs and questions

Criteria	Explanation
Validation of results from the SLR	Checking whether indicators taken from scientific articles, external reporting standards and internal performance frameworks also represent CE KPIs
Thesis confirmation	Checking whether indicators from CE reporting standards and frameworks are also used as CE KPIs in companies
Thesis confirmation	Confirmation or refutation of the indicators derived from external reporting standards, internal performance frameworks and scientific articles as CE KPIs
Supplement to the literature	Identification of further operational perspectives and KPIs of the CE, that have not yet been covered in the literature

3.3.3 Privacy policy

The privacy policy information is sent to the contact person of the companies of the target group in the invitation email of the survey. The privacy policy provision contains information on the voluntary nature of participation in the survey, the handling of personal data, the use and anonymisation of the information and results provided as well as the storage of the data. Participants are also informed about their rights and obligations. By clicking on the survey link, participants confirm their agreement with the privacy policy provisions. The invitation email for the survey, including the privacy policy provisions, is listed in annex 2.

3.3.4 Selection of participants

Once the content of the questionnaire is finalised, criteria are defined for the selection of companies in the target group. Table 13 gives an overview on these criteria.

Table 13: Selection criteria for survey participants

Criteria	Explanation
Economic sector	The company covers a key sector defined by the new EU circular economy action plan: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastics - Textiles - Electronics and ICT - Food, water and nutrients - Packaging - Batteries and vehicles - Construction and buildings
Localisation	The company's legal headquarters are in Germany.
Company size	The company is a medium sized and large company according to §267 HGB

The focus is on companies that fall into one of the key sectors of the new EU circular economy action plan. According to the EU, these sectors are central to the implementation of a CE (European Commission 11.03.2020). In addition, only medium-sized and large German companies are selected in accordance with §267 HGB, as they are very likely to have already addressed the issue of CE and will

be subject to the CSRD in the near future (German Federal Ministry of Justice 17.04.2024; EU Parliament and council 14.12.2022). For the final identification of the companies in the target group, a multi-stage process is chosen, as shown in table 14. For the companies filtered out from the Northdata company database, there is only a general email address given and no personal contact with the company is made. Therefore, a very low participation rate is assumed here. In the case of the companies from the personal and INEC network, a specific contact person including an email address is available, so a higher response rate is assumed here.

Table 14: Identification approach for participants

Working Step	Explanation
1	Filtering target companies from the Northdata database
2	Checking personal network for target companies
3	Checking target companies of the network of the Institute for Industrial Ecology (INEC) of the University of Pforzheim

Before the companies in the target group can be filtered out of the Northdata company database in step 1, NACE codes have to be assigned to the key sectors defined in the new EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (Northdata 2024). The term NACE code is derived from the French title 'Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne' and describes a classification of economic sectors (Katrin Schmidt 2018). The allocation of the EU key sectors to the corresponding NACE codes is shown in more detail in annex 3. An example screenshot of the input mask in the Northdata enterprise database can be found in annex 4. Numerous other companies in the target group are identified both from the personal network and from the INEC network at the University of Pforzheim.

3.3.5 Testing and Execution

The online survey is created using the Microsoft Forms application, as it offers a wide range of design, question and evaluation options and is user-friendly (Microsoft Forms). During programming, care is taken to ensure that the questionnaire could be completed within 10-15 minutes. Improvement measures are identified in a pretest with the counsellors of this research work. As a result, the length of the questionnaire is shortened, some wording is adapted and small explanatory texts are added to individual questions to avoid misunderstandings when answering. The questionnaire is also lightened up by displaying the completion progress and targeted graphic elements. Another pretest is carried out with a company from the target group, but no further improvements are identified. The questionnaire is then sent to the contact persons of the companies in the target group in a

standardised email. In this way, it is possible to reach many companies in a short period of time. In the cover letter, it is pointed out that the questionnaire should be forwarded to a specialised employee for answering if necessary.

The invitation email can be found in annex 2. The total field time of the online survey is 74 days. After 33 days, the companies from the INE- and personal network are reminded again by email to participate. A logbook is kept documenting the contact and the response rate. Figure 17 illustrates the origin and number of companies contacted and the feedback received. A total of 4214 companies are invited to take part in the survey by email and 38 finally took part in the survey. The analysis of the results is described in detail in chapter 4.1.

Figure 17: Contacted companies vs. returns, adopted by (Page et al. 2021: p. 5)

3.3.6 Evaluation

To evaluate the online survey, the results are imported from the Microsoft Forms survey tool into Microsoft Excel. The analysis is carried out exclusively with Excel, no other tools are used. The analysis of the survey results forms the basis for comparison and interpretation together with the results of the SLRs. The focus is on identifying the KPIs used by the companies in the target group to measure and manage the transformation to CE at micro level. By applying the following exclusion criteria, the quality of the results is ensured and distortions and sources of error are avoided:

- Double participation
- Lack of industry categorisation
- Participants are not dealing with the topic of CE

To be able to make industry-representative statements of the use of certain CE KPIs, the heterogeneous sector distribution in the survey must be equalised. A weighting factor is calculated for this purpose. In the analysis, the weighting factor is multiplied by the number of CE KPIs used by the respective sector to obtain an undistorted, meaningful result (Gabler 2006: p. 128 ff.). The weighting factor is made up of the sector distribution of the survey participants and the share of the respective sector in the German gross value added (GVA):

$$\textit{Weighting factor industry } X (\%) = \frac{\textit{GVA industry } X (\%)}{\textit{Share industry } X \textit{ in survey } (\%)}$$

The contribution of the sectors to the German GVA is chosen as the reference value, as this directly reflects the economic importance of the sector in the overall economy. This indicator shows how much value an industry contributes to total production of a national economy by calculating the value of its produced goods minus its direct intermediate consumption. For a better visualisation, the results are all standardised by a factor of 10, as the individual sectors only account for a very small percentage of German GVA. The Eurostat database of the statistical office of the EU is used to determine the GVA of the individual sectors (Eurostat 2025). An exact sector classification is possible through the NACE code classification of the individual sectors in Eurostat, as well as the linking of the target group of companies from the online survey with specific NACE codes. This sector classification can be seen in annex 3.

The results of the online survey must also be normalised to make a generally valid, undistorted statement about which of the internal functions are particularly relevant for CE measurement and control using KPIs. This step is necessary because the individual functions (categories) contain different numbers of KPIs and it would not be possible to make a reliable statement simply by determining the frequency of KPI usage. First, the number of KPIs per category and the number of uses of the KPIs per category are determined. The frequency of KPI use per category is then normalised using the following formula:

$$\varnothing \textit{ uses p. KPI and category} = \frac{\textit{Uses p. KPI and category}}{\textit{Number of KPIs p. category}}$$

By normalising the frequency (average of uses per KPI), valid comparisons can be made between the functions (categories) and the most relevant can be determined. To answer the main research question regarding the distinction between the KPIs used by companies in practice and those from voluntary and mandatory CE reporting standards and frameworks, comparison criteria are defined, see table 15. These are based on various taxonomies identified from the SLR for CE indicators at micro level (Saidani et al. 2019: p. 548 ff.; Vinante et al. 2020: p. 6; Oliveira et al. 2021: p. 461 f.).

Table 15: Classification criteria for CE indicators

Classification criteria	Explanation
CE strategy	Brief explanation of the R-strategy on which the indicator is based on (intensification of product use, extension of product use, product circulation)
Life Cycle Stage	Phase of the product life cycle to which the indicator contributes (take, make, use, EoL)
Unit	Qualitative and quantitative indicators
Performance	Indicators measure the progress/transition of measures or the impact/effect of these measures
Dimension	Single or multiple dimensional indicators focussing on one or several R-strategies and CE principles
Affected organisational function	Affected stakeholders/functions of the indicator within the company

3.4 Qualitative Interviews

Interviews are conducted to deepen the findings from the SLR and the online survey and to get specific insights in the practical implementation of the CE. Therefore, the willingness of the contact persons in the companies is queried in the online survey. The aim of the interviews is firstly to verify the information provided by the companies in the online survey and secondly to obtain in-depth information to clarify the research questions. The interviews are prepared, conducted and analysed according to the guidelines of Bortz and Döring.

The interviews are designed as explorative, semi-standardised and qualitative interviews (Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 365). The interviewees can contribute their practical experience in semi-open and open questions. If necessary, more in-depth questions could be asked on individual topics if there is a need for further clarification. The methodological procedure is described in the following sub-chapters.

3.4.1 Content and guideline

A guideline with semi-open and open questions is created for the interviews to determine the structure (Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 365). The questions are arranged in a specific order and build on each other in terms of content. However, it is possible to adjust the order during the interview to maintain the flow of the interviewee's speech. For this purpose, individual questions are brought forward, skipped or deepened. Regarding the content, the interview is divided into two subject areas: „Internal CE KPIs vs. external reporting” and „CE management tool”. This structure is chosen based on the research questions of this thesis.

In the first part, the information provided by the interviewees in the previously conducted online survey is validated. The other questions in the first section are used to gain additional insights into the use of CE KPIs and the influence of mandatory external sustainability reporting. The second section focuses on the organisation of the transition to CE in the companies and the corporate functions affected by it. Table 16 provides an overview of the criteria that lead to the inclusion of a question. When selecting the questions, the results of the SLR and the online survey are considered and an attempt is made to obtain additional information from the literature. Finally, the interview concept is checked using Bortz and Döring's checklist before it was conducted to ensure a smooth process (Bortz und Döring 2016: p. 358). The interview guide is listed in annex 5.

Table 16: Criteria for the selection of questions

Criteria	Explanation
1	Validation of the information in the online survey
2	Validation or refutation of the results of the SLR
3	Validation or refutation of theses based on the SLR
4	Closing knowledge gaps from SLR
5	Gaining specific insights into practical implementation

3.4.2 Privacy policy

A separate privacy policy is sent to the participants of the interviews in the invitation email. This had to be read, signed and returned before the interviews are conducted. The privacy policy contains information on the use and storage of the data provided in the interview as well as an explanation of the rights of the interviewees in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (DSGVO) (EU Commission 2016). It is important to note that neither personal nor company-related data will be visible in the results and that all the information provided will be anonymised. The privacy policy can be found in annex 6.

3.4.3 Execution

Once the content of the interviews had been finalised, the voluntary participants in the online survey are contacted. Based on the information from the online survey, the participants with whom an in-depth interview makes sense in terms of content are filtered out, as they are already intensively involved with CE. Contact is made via email. First the interview guidelines and the privacy policy with a request to return and sign them are sent out to the participants. The invitation link for the online interview is sent in a second email.

The Microsoft Teams application was used to conduct, record and transcribe the interview. The interviewees are experts in the subject area, as they are based in the company's sustainability

department or deal with CE as part of their work. A total of two interviews are conducted based on the willingness of the participants from the online survey. The interviews are designed to last 20 minutes. In practice, they lasted between 20 and 30 minutes.

3.4.4 Evaluation

The two interview transcripts are analysed manually without the use of a separate analysis tool due to the manageable number of transcripts. The summarised interview transcription is presented in annex 7. Care is taken to present only the essential statements relevant to this research work in a summarised form. The interview is divided into two sections: „Internal KPIs vs. external reporting” and „Management tool”. The presentation of the statements is structured accordingly. Care is also taken to present the results in a factual, objective and anonymised manner to protect the identity of the interview participants. To improve readability, the two interview partners are abbreviated as CB for the „Construction and buildings” sector and BV for the „Battery and vehicles” sector.

4 Results

This chapter presents the results of the online survey and the expert interviews as empirical research methods for this research work. None of the companies surveyed and interviewed are mentioned by name to ensure their anonymity. The empirical study is conducted to compare the theoretical results of the SLRs in relation to the use of CE KPIs by companies in practice and thus answer the research questions. As part of the SLRs, the research gap is identified that there is a great level of uncertainty about which CE KPIs are used by companies in practice. Moreover, it has not yet been clarified whether the CE indicators required in the internal and external CE reporting standards and frameworks are also used as CE KPIs in corporate practice and how they differ from those used by the companies. In this context, it is unclear whether the information from the voluntary and mandatory reporting requirements within companies contributes to promoting and advancing CE. Furthermore, the results of the empirical studies should show the internal functions and stakeholders affected by CE measurement and answer the research question of whether there are cross-industry and industry-specific CE indicators or KPIs.

4.1 Results of the survey

As already described in chapter 2.3.4, this survey focusses on medium-sized and large German companies from the core sectors identified in the new EU action plan for the CE, as these play a key role in the transformation due to their economic activities (European Commission 11.03.2020):

- Plastics
- Textiles
- Electronics and ICT
- Food, water and nutrients
- Packaging
- Batteries and vehicles
- Construction and buildings

Of 4214 companies in the target group contacted, 38 took part in the survey. This corresponds to a participation rate of just almost 1%. The average processing time for the survey is estimated at approx. 10 minutes and in practice it takes approx. 22 minutes on average. When analysing the surveys, exclusion criteria are defined to ensure a high quality of the information provided. These include double participation, a lack of industry categorisation and participants stating that they don't deal with the topic of CE. The reasons for not dealing with the topic of CE are heterogeneous. In two

cases, the topic is not significant and in another, a more intensive discussion is planned. It is interesting to note that one company cites the fact that it is bound by regulatory requirements in relation to product packaging, which exclude secondary materials, for example, as a reason for not engaging further with the topic of CE. After applying the exclusion criteria, 5 results are excluded from the analysis, leaving 33 responses for further analysis. Figure 18 provides an overview of the distribution of the companies by sector. The „Construction and buildings” sector, with almost 40% of the responses, is clearly overweight compared to the other sectors.

Figure 18: Sector distribution of participants

To make generally valid, undistorted statements about the use of CE KPIs within the individual sectors, the results are calculated with a weighting factor, which represents the economic relevance of each industry by the contribution to the German GVA as a reference value. A total of 84 different CE KPIs are queried in the survey. These are sorted according to the cVC framework and include all important internal functions for CE measurement and control. Except for the indicator „number of CE-related patents”, each of the proposed KPIs was used at least once. Table 17 shows the indicators that are used by over 50% of the companies and are therefore the most relevant in practice. These are limited to the categories of „Resource consumption” and „Waste management” which can be summarised under the Operations function. Furthermore, each of the KPIs is quantitative, single-dimensional in relation to the relevant R-strategy and can be assigned to the „Make” or „Take” life cycle phase. The identified KPIs are parameters that are easy to determine in most companies and do not require complex calculations.

Table 17: Most frequently used CE KPIs

Subtopic	CE KPI	Usage (%)
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Energy consumption (total or p. product unit)	93,31
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Share of renewable energy (total or p. product unit)	82,82
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Own production of renewable energy	82,82
Waste management	Waste generated (total or p. product unit)	78,08
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Water consumption in production processes (total or p. product unit)	70,17
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Proportion/ total mass of recycled materials purchased (inflow)	64,98
Waste management	Composition of the waste (proportion/ mass of the individual components)	64,81
Waste management	Proportion/ total mass of hazardous waste generated	64,21
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Proportion/ total mass of recyclates in products (outflow)	54,71
Waste management	Recycling rate of waste generated	50,65
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Total mass of products manufactured (outflow)	50,53

Table 18 provides an overview of all CE KPIs that are used by less than 10% of the companies and are therefore only of minor importance in practice. The identified indicators are distributed across almost all internal categories.

Table 18: Least used CE KPIs

Subtopic	CE KPI	Usage (%)
Ecodesign	Number of CE-related patents	0,00
Ecodesign	Average product warranty granted (e.g. years)	3,41
Product marketing & Communication	Revenue from/ number of products sold through CE-related marketing activities/ campaigns	6,17
Ecodesign	Number/ proportion of repairable products	6,46
Ecodesign	Proportion of the budget used for CE-related R&D	6,49
Waste management	Proportion/ total mass of radioactive waste generated	6,78
Resource recovery	Energy recovered/ generated from the utilisation of company waste/ products at the end of the use phase	6,81
Product marketing & Communication	Seats held by company employees in CE-related legislative bodies/ standardisation committees	7,35
Resource consumption (water, energy, materials)	Proportion/ total mass of organic, compostable materials used (inflow)	7,38
Resource recovery	Proportion/ total mass of new materials required for recycling	9,90

Within the survey, companies are asked to add additional KPIs in the respective subject areas, if relevant. The following KPIs are identified:

Table 19: Additional KPIs used by companies

Subtopic	CE KPI
Waste management	Amount of waste in relation to total production
Reverse logistics	Provision of raw materials from return loops
	Cycles of the packaging materials used
Resource recovery	Proportion of utilisation/disposal methods (thermal, recycling, landfill)

The survey results can also be used to answer the sub-research question of whether there are cross-sector and sector-specific KPIs. In general, when defining the KPIs in the survey, care is taken to ensure that they are as general and cross-sectoral as possible, although some sector-specific patterns in the use of KPIs can be recognised.

Figure 19 shows the use of the KPIs from the individual sectors in the survey. The leftmost bar indicates that five specific KPIs are only used by one sector at a time. This is an indication that these KPIs are likely to be sector specific. The rightmost bar indicates that two specific KPIs are used by all sectors. This in turn is an indication that these are cross-sector KPIs. Cross-sector KPIs are those that are used by several sectors, as they contain general characteristics and information about the CE

that are relevant across several sectors. The criterion is defined that a KPI must be used in at least four of the seven sectors analysed, i.e. by approx. 57% of the sectors, to be considered cross-sectoral. A total of 45 KPIs were identified, which corresponds to approx. 53% of all KPIs in the survey. It can therefore be seen that most of the KPIs selected in the survey are important across all sectors. These are distributed across almost all internal company functions, with the categories „Resource consumption” and „Waste management” being the most important. The indicators used are mostly single-dimensional, quantitative and relate to the „Make” phase of the product life cycle. Two KPIs from the „Resource consumption” category are particularly universal, as they are used at least once by all sectors:

- Water consumption in production processes
- Proportion/ total mass of recycled materials purchased (inflow)

Figure 19: Distribution of the usage of KPIs across sectors

Sector-specific KPIs are of relevance for only one or a few sectors with similar characteristics relevant to CE. Due to the small number of usable responses (33) and the very uneven distribution of sectors among the companies participating in the survey, only limited significant statements can be made about sector-specific KPIs. However, it should be noted that five KPIs are particularly relevant for only one industry:

- Turnover or share of total turnover from business models from CE-oriented collaborations with external partners
- Number of improvement measures/ innovations/ business models resulting from external collaborations

- Average product warranty granted (e.g. years)
- Energy recovered/ generated from the utilisation of company waste/ products at the end of the use phase
- Revenue from/ number of products sold through CE-related marketing activities/ campaigns

There is no pattern to these as they are spread across all internal functions. However, the first four KPIs are used exclusively by the „Construction and buildings” sector and the fifth only by companies in the „Plastics” sector. The results of the online survey can also be used to answer the sub-research question of which internal functions are affected by the CE measurement. As the selection of CE KPIs in the online survey is organised according to the internal functions they relate to, the term internal function is equated with the term category in the following.

To be able to make a generally valid, unbiased statement about which internal function is particularly relevant, the frequencies of KPI use per category must be normalised, as each category contains a different number of KPIs to choose from. Figure 20 shows the various internal functions and the relevance of these in relation to the individual economic sectors. It is generally recognisable that the categories of „Resource consumption”, „Waste management” and „Material sourcing” are the most relevant for the participating companies for CE measurement and control through KPIs. The average use of KPIs is highest in these categories.

It can also be seen that different functions are more important for different sectors than others. The „Resource consumption” category plays an important role in all the sectors analysed, as it is always one of the Top 3 categories in terms of average KPI usage. „Ecodesign” is also one of the categories with the lowest relevance for companies alongside „Product marketing & communication”, although the decisions made in the design phase are essential for the circularity and the extent of the environmental impact of a product throughout its entire life cycle.

Figure 20: Industry relevance of CE functions

From the survey results, no other internal company functions can be identified on which the transformation or measurement of CE has an impact. However, one company in the plastics industry states that the implementation of CE in its own company also depends on the willingness of customers in the downstream value chain. For example, the implementation of circularity strategies, such as the increased use of recyclates in production, is still associated with additional costs, which customers are often not willing to bear. The price of products is still the decisive criterion for remaining competitive, alongside quality requirements.

To answer the main research question of the extent to which the CE KPIs used by the companies in practice differ from the indicators and metrics of the voluntary and mandatory internal and external CE reporting standards, classification criteria are defined for the comparison. Based on various taxonomies developed by academics in this field of research, the following criteria are defined:

- Unit (quantitative, qualitative)
- Dimension (single, multiple)
- Life Cycle Stage (Take, Make, Use, EoL)
- CE strategy (product circulation, intensification and extension of product use)
- Performance (transition, effect)

The affected internal function of the respective indicator (KPI) is not listed again as it is already analysed. Figure 21 shows the frequency of use of the CE KPIs by the surveyed companies based on the taxonomy criteria. It is interesting to note the relatively even distribution of the KPIs in the CE strategy and life cycle stage category, whereby most of the indicators have no clear reference to one of the 10 R-strategies and are assigned to the „Make” product life cycle stage. In contrast, it is clearly recognisable that most of the indicators are quantitative and single dimensional as they focus on one specific R-strategy. In terms of performance, only a few indicators exclusively measure the transition to CE, whereas most measure the impact or effect of CE measures or both.

Figure 21: Use of CE KPIs based on the taxonomy

In practice, several voluntary and mandatory external and internal CE reporting frameworks and standards are already in place, which are used to varying degrees by the companies in the survey, see figure 22. Around a third of the companies (34%) currently don't use any CE standard or framework to measure their performance against their targets. The internationally recognised GRI Standards contain some indicators relevant for measuring CE in the various topic-specific standards (GRI 301- Materials, GRI 302- Energy, GRI 303- Water and Effluents, GRI 306- Effluents and Waste). These are used by around 29% of companies. In contrast, the mandatory ESRS E5- Resource use and circular economy, which must be applied as part of sustainability reporting in accordance with CSRD, are only used by 8% of the companies surveyed. The indicators of the internal CE performance frameworks, including ISO 59020, Circulytics and CTI, are only used sporadically by the companies. 18% of the companies use internal measurement methods and various other ISO standards such as 9001, 14001, 14021, which are not suitable for measuring the transformation to CE on micro level.

Figure 22: CE standards and frameworks used

Figure 23 shows the overlap between the CE indicators used by the companies in the survey and those in the voluntary and mandatory external and internal CE reporting standards. A high overlap rate is an indication that the indicators contained in the standards reflect the CE KPIs used by companies in practice and are therefore highly relevant.

Only around 23% of the ESRS E5- Resource use and circular economy indicators are used by companies. In contrast, the overlap rate of information from the two external CE reporting standards SASB and GRI is significantly higher at around 47% and 46% respectively. Almost half of the indicators to be applied voluntarily in the two standards are used by the companies in the survey. The indicators of the recently published ISO 59020 also have a high overlap rate of approx. 46%. The indicators of the CTI and Circulytics framework are used slightly less by the companies surveyed, at 38% and 36%

respectively. The findings from the survey are interpreted in the discussion section and linked to the results of the interviews.

Figure 23: Overlap of the companies' CE KPIs with the CE standards

4.2 Results of the interviews

The interviews are conducted to validate the information provided by the companies regarding the CE KPIs used in the survey and to gain additional insights to clarify the research questions. To this end, the interviews are divided into two subject areas, which are used as a guide when presenting the results in this chapter. In addition to validating the information in the survey, the questions in the category „Internal KPIs vs. external reporting” aim to find out whether and to what extent external reporting on CE in accordance with the various voluntary and mandatory standards helps to promote the topic internally. The use of the internal CE performance frameworks listed in section 2.2.3 and the academic CE indicators from section 2.3.4 will also be discussed. The second category, „Management tool”, aims to gain insights into how the topic of CE is organised within the company to draw conclusions about a possible CE management tool.

Two interviews are conducted, one with a company in the „Construction and buildings” sector and one with a company in the „Batteries and vehicles” sector. In the description of the results, the two companies are abbreviated as „CB” and „BV” for ease of reading. Due to the manageable number of interviews, the evaluation is carried out manually without the use of a separate analysis tool. The surveys are conducted via video chat using Microsoft Teams software and last approximately 20-30 minutes. The interview questions can be found in annex 5, the summarised transcription in annex 7.

Internal KPIs vs. external reporting

The first three questions aim to find out whether the KPIs stated in the survey are really KPIs and used as a basis for decision-making or target monitoring by the company's management. The

answers are heterogeneous. The CB company has not yet collected any dedicated KPIs for CE that are reported to the Management Board. Accordingly, the information from the survey should only be evaluated as CE indicators and not as specific management KPIs.

The topic of CE is currently in the development stage and so far, the focus is only on the collection and improvement of three product-specific indicators. In contrast, the second company BV has a slightly more advanced level of maturity, as the information in the survey relates to KPIs that can be assigned to different products and business units. However, the challenge here is also to define central control KPIs for the CE that can be used across the company to monitor the transformation. The next questions are aimed at gaining more detailed insights into the contribution of external CE reporting standards to the implementation of CE. Both companies confirm that the regulatory pressure, especially through the mandatory application of the CSRD (ESRS E5), ensures that more attention is paid to CE.

They also agree that the transformation to CE is not only driven by external reporting, but depends heavily on the respective leadership, attitude and motivation of the management. CB points out that there are also other drivers in addition to mandatory reporting on CE. These include, above all, customer requirements for circular products, requirements from external product certifications, pressure from suppliers and the company's own economic incentives. In the construction and buildings industry in particular, economic incentives and customer orders are linked to compliance with strict product certifications, which is why the focus is on fulfilling these. Accordingly, the focus to date has only been on achieving the highest possible score in the aspects relevant to CE from the product certifications. Economic benefits (cost savings) resulting from CE-oriented measures are also focussed on (material recovery, resource efficiency).

For both companies, external reporting is seen as an opportunity to identify potential for improvement and achieve holistic integration into the corporate strategy and business processes but is initially viewed primarily as a compliance issue. BV points out that data collection in accordance with CSRD represents a baseline assessment and that a strategy for transformation to CE can be developed on this basis. However, it is also criticised that the increased data transparency is associated with a high level of bureaucracy and data collection effort and that calculation methods are sometimes unclear. Specifically, neither company is yet able to provide a reliable answer to the question of whether the ESRS E5 contains data points that are only collected for reporting purposes and have no relevance for internal management.

The first section of the interview is rounded off with questions on the use of academic CE indicators, internal CE performance frameworks and specific CE objectives. CB states that the topic of CE is not yet strategically relevant and therefore neither concrete objectives nor more complex academic CE indicators are used. BV also does not use any of the academic indicators queried due to the detailed, challenging calculation and cannot provide an answer regarding specific objectives. Academic CE indicators, which are complex to calculate, find little acceptance as their added value is not obvious and they don't induce recommendations for action. However, various indicators of the Circulytics framework are used, whereby the focus is on the development of company-specific indicators, as it appears questionable to BV what effect the individual frameworks will have.

Management tool

The first questions of the second section of the interview are aimed at obtaining information on how the transformation to CE is structured within the company. CB states that the ESG manager, as the person in charge of all sustainability issues, must develop and monitor appropriate KPIs for the targets set by the board of directors. The ESG-manager acts as a cross-product coordinator, while the Chief Technical Officer (CTO) is responsible for compliance with the KPIs as a member of the Executive Board. However, the organisational integration of CE is still in the early stages. The BV company has developed a Sustainability Steering Board to which various members of the Executive Board belong. A corresponding CE strategy is developed by the members and CE KPIs are developed, discussed and monitored. Sustainability officers and other persons responsible for the operational implementation of the strategy through suitable measures and for KPI collection report separately to the Sustainability Steering Board for each business unit. Both companies collect indicators (KPIs) for all internal functions listed in the survey that play a role in the transformation to CE.

The question of whether the companies already use a management tool for the transformation to CE was answered in the negative by CB. BV, on the other hand, states that it uses the recently published ISO standard 59020 to develop key processes for the CE, as this can be used across all companies. A separate tool or software solution for CE data collection, KPI calculation, monitoring or simulation is not used.

The interview is rounded off with a question about the greatest obstacles and challenges companies face in the transformation to CE. CB lists several product and business model-related challenges. The main challenges are the reintegration of products at the end of their life cycle into the production of new products. This includes economical material recycling, separation of product components by type and reprocessing. Product development has a key role to play here to design products in such

a way that current complex recycling processes can be simplified. Up to now, the focus is on enabling product components to be separated by type at the end of their life cycle so that they can be fed into appropriate recycling infrastructures and prevent pure thermal recovery. BV primarily lists challenges in relation to CE KPIs. At an organisational level, there is still a lack of concrete responsibilities for defining CE KPIs.

In addition, data collection, data quality and the calculation of CE indicators often present a difficulty, as these must be collected within the upstream and downstream value chain. Standardised calculation methods by the relevant stakeholders are also crucial to ensure high data quality. The creation of a digital infrastructure can help with these problems. As the transformation to CE affects all the company's business areas equally, all these indicators need to be consolidated. This results in the difficulty of defining a few superior KPIs. In this context, the question is raised as to whether it is even necessary to aggregate indicators to make decisions. The interdependence of companies in the management of CE measures is particularly emphasised, as different players within the value chain must work together. The holistic evaluation of CE measures across the product life cycle is of crucial importance. It is also difficult to assess the impact (financial, ecological) of CE-orientated business models. Moreover, it is crucial that customers are able and willing to pay for ecological product improvements.

5 Discussion

In the following chapter, the main results of the SLRs and the empirical studies are summarised and interpreted to answer the research questions of this thesis. The chapter is subdivided into the interpretation regarding the use of CE KPIs and a presentation of the knowledge gained in relation to the development of a company-specific CE management tool. Finally, the results and the interpretations are critically evaluated by describing the main limitations of this work.

5.1 Interpretation

The results of the online survey show that the companies in the CE key sectors defined by the EU already collect numerous KPIs for the CE and that except for one all the proposed KPIs are used. Figure 23 shows that the ESRS E5 indicators represent the smallest proportion of KPIs used by companies. This could lead to the misinterpretation that the ESRS E5 indicators are not yet of great practical relevance for companies and contain a large amount of information that has not yet been collected or dealt with. However, if considering the most frequently used CE KPIs across all surveyed sectors, see table 17, it is noticeable that all except one are included both in the ESRS E5 and in the various SASB standards. This means that the indicators of these two external CE reporting standards already play a major role in the internally used CE KPIs of the companies, although most of them have not yet dealt with either ESRS E5 or SASB, as illustrated in figure 22.

This is a first indication that these two standards have great practical relevance and potentially contribute to promoting the transformation to CE through suitable KPIs and not just represent an additional reporting burden. However, this does not necessarily mean that the ESRS E5 and SASB indicators measure the transformation to CE holistically and contain all relevant information, as will be further discussed in the following sections. The three most frequently used CE KPIs of the companies in the survey relate to energy consumption and generation. These are not dedicated CE KPIs in the narrower sense, as the amount and type of energy consumption do not relate to the application of core CE principles or strategies.

However, the efficient use of renewable energy contributes indirectly to CE, but the focus of CE is on the circularity of material flows and obtaining the maximum possible benefit or use of a product. It can therefore be assumed that these indicators are not original CE KPIs. In general, it should be noted that none of the companies in the survey use CE indicators developed and analysed by academics and scientists in this field, as was already assumed at the beginning. The reasons given by the academics for the lack of practical application coincide with the assessments of the interviewees, who

primarily cite the complex, time-consuming calculation and data collection as well as the questionable practical benefit of aggregated indicators. They are therefore unsuitable as KPIs for companies. The CE indicators of the selected internal and external reporting standards and frameworks as well as the CE KPIs used by companies show numerous similarities and differences, which need to be analysed in this research work.

On the one hand, these allow conclusions to be drawn about the extent to which the individual standards contribute to promoting CE in the companies concerned and on the other, about the degree of maturity and granularity of CE measurement and control. The similarities and differences between the CE KPIs used by the companies in practice and those of the CE standards and frameworks analysed are shown based on six classification criteria. The vast majority of the KPIs used by the companies and the indicators of the CE standards and frameworks are quantitative. Exceptions are the ESRS E5 and the Circulytics framework, in which qualitative indicators are equally represented.

As qualitative indicators have a limited suitability as KPIs, a large proportion of the data to be collected from the frameworks mentioned can initially be regarded as an additional reporting burden. The qualitative indicators of ESRS E5 include the description of IRO's as well as policies, actions and targets. Depending on the degree of maturity of the company in the transformation to CE, this data is already available. For many companies, however, the initial collection of data is extremely time-consuming and costly and does not initially promote CE, as important resources are tied up. However, the collection of this qualitative data, as described by the interviewees, also represents a baseline assessment and forms the starting point to take a more detailed look at the CE transformation of the company.

This assessment can be confirmed by the results of the SLR. Even if the time-consuming collection of qualitative data is not directly conducive to centralised CE measurement and management, the original objective of the CSRD is fulfilled, as external stakeholders are given a comprehensive understanding of the company in terms of CE and resource use. Another classification criteria is the performance of the indicators. In contrast to the CE indicators analysed by academics, both the CE KPIs of the companies from the survey and the indicators of the CE standards and frameworks are predominantly effect indicators, which are more suitable as KPIs compared to transition indicators. It can therefore initially be assumed that the indicators of the CE standards and frameworks also contain some potential CE KPIs. For holistic measurement and control of the transformation to CE, suitable KPIs should also include all life cycle phases of the product. Some similarities can also be

identified in the CE KPIs of the companies and the indicators of the analysed standards and frameworks. In general, all life cycle stages are considered in the KPIs used by the companies, but KPIs relating to resource utilisation and waste generation during the manufacturing phase (make) of the products within the company are primarily used. KPIs for the use-phase are used very little. The same can be said for the CE indicators of the analysed standards and frameworks. This contradicts the findings from the SLR, according to which the focus of more academic CE indicators is often on the EoL- phase and thus the closing of material loops. Indicators of the Take- and EoL- phase can be found in the standards and frameworks in a relatively balanced ratio, whereby the Take-phase is used to a slightly greater extent in the indicators used by the companies.

In general, it is important that companies evaluate and implement CE measures along the entire life cycle of products. Therefore, suitable CE KPIs should be developed on a company and product-specific basis for particularly relevant life cycle phases and none of these should be neglected. As all the analysed standards and frameworks with a slight focus on the make-phase contain indicators for all life cycle stages, it is not possible to say which of these have a greater contribution to the transformation of CE through suitable CE KPIs.

Another classification criteria is the R-strategy (circularity level) and the associated dimension that affects the indicators. Companies most frequently use single dimensional KPIs that cannot be assigned to a specific R-strategy and KPIs for product circulation (recycle, recovery). This observation is consistent with the findings from the SLR, according to which most indicators analysed by academics in CE research are single dimensional and relate to strategies with a low circularity level, e.g. recycling. Indicators of higher circularity levels do not appear very often in those developed by academics, nor in those used by companies or those included in the CE standards and frameworks. One exception is ISO 59020, which contains some indicators for the highest level of circularity, intensification of product use (Refuse, Reduce, Reuse). Regarding the R-strategy, there are generally no major differences between the indicators used in practice and those of the standards and frameworks. The use of indicators with a higher circularity level, such as selected indicators from ISO 59020, is an indication that companies are already dealing with the topic of CE in more detail.

ISO 59020 therefore makes the greatest contribution to promoting CE in companies regarding this criterion. Based on the predominant use of CE KPIs of lower circularity levels by companies, it can be concluded that their business models, processes and products are not yet being fundamentally scrutinised and rethought based on the CE principles but are instead focussing on the strategies of the outer circles of the EMF butterfly diagram. The following key statements and conclusions can be

summarised regarding the internal functions and categories affected by the transformation to CE: The SLR leads to the conclusion that all categories of the PVC framework play a role in the transformation to CE, but with a different extent.

The categories Operations (Resource consumption, Waste management, Resource recovery) Technology Development (Ecodesign) and Firm Infrastructure (Strategy & Vision, Business model, Cooperation & industrial symbiosis) are particularly emphasised. Indicators for all three main categories can be found in the ESRS E5, SASB and Circulytics framework and are used by the companies in practice. The CE data to be disclosed in all analysed standards and frameworks, as well as the CE KPIs used by the companies, mainly relate to the areas of resource consumption and waste management, which are grouped under the internal Operations function, see figure 20.

All KPIs that are used most frequently by over 50% of the companies can be assigned to these two categories. This is not surprising, as the implementation of CE principles requires the circular organisation of raw material flows based on the various R-strategies with the aim of avoiding waste and preserving the value or maximum benefit of resources for as long as possible. The overlap of theoretical and practical findings in relation to the Operations category suggests that this internal function is of great importance in the development of suitable CE KPIs and that the CE standards and frameworks analysed contain the relevant CE KPIs of companies in this category. However, some differences can be identified regarding the category of Technology Development resp. Ecodesign. Indicators in this area are the second least used by companies in practice and only play a subordinate role so far.

Except for the Circulytics framework, the proportion of Ecodesign indicators in the CE standards and frameworks analysed is very low and this category is not even included in the GRI standards. One could therefore come to the misinterpretation that this category, although it obviously plays a major role in the implementation of the CE, has so far only been given minimal consideration in companies and by the developers of the standards and frameworks. However, the number of indicators to be reported or used alone is not decisive for the relevance of this category. The subjective classification of the indicators used by the companies in the Ecodesign category also has an influence on the overall relevance. Despite the ambiguous results from theory and practice, the Ecodesign category should be considered in the development of suitable KPIs, as decisions made in this phase significantly determine the environmental impact and circularity of products over their entire life cycle. Indicators in the PVC category Firm Infrastructure with the functions Strategy & Vision, Business model and Cooperation & industrial symbiosis associated with CE are the second most frequently

used by companies in practice and therefore play an important role in the identification of CE KPIs, see figure 20.

However, indicators of these three functions play a rather subordinate role based on their number in the CE standards and frameworks analysed. The GRI, ISO 59020 and CTI indicators do not contain any of the indicators in question. The insufficient consideration of these functions in the CE standards and frameworks is an indication that they do not necessarily reflect the KPIs used by companies in practice. The other internal PVC categories (Procurement, Marketing & Sales, Inbound & Outbound logistics, HR management) are of secondary importance both in the CE KPIs used by the companies and in their consideration in the analysed standards and frameworks. This observation is consistent with the results of the SLR, as far fewer KPIs are identified for these functions. Therefore, these functions can be disregarded for the definition of CE KPIs. However, indicators in these categories play an important role as enablers for the transformation to CE, especially regarding the development of take-back logistics systems, product marketing and declaration as well as the development of CE expertise through employee training.

The Finance function should be considered separately at this point, as it was not originally included in the PVC framework. The survey results show that the companies use some financial indicators related to CE, but these can primarily be assigned to other functions. Examples of this are:

- Turnover or share of total turnover from second-hand retailing/reuse business models
- Cost savings through the purchase of secondary materials instead of primary materials.

These indicators can primarily be assigned to the categories Firm infrastructure (Business model) and Procurement (Material sourcing). Hardly any financial indicators can be identified within the CE reporting standards and frameworks analysed. However, the Finance function is fundamental in the transformation to CE, as potential CE-orientated improvement initiatives must always be evaluated in terms of their economic benefit. This is also reflected in the assessment of the two interviewees, who emphasise the trade-off between sustainability and profitability, because ultimately the customer must be willing to pay a premium for the products if necessary. Accordingly, a company should decide whether to define financial CE KPIs based on its CE strategy and objectives.

The use of CE KPIs within the various sectors shows that the majority of these can be categorised as cross-sectoral, with five KPIs being used exclusively by one sector. Of course, individual aspects of CE are more important to consider for different sectors than others, as the findings of the SLR show. However, due to the very heterogeneous distribution of companies in the various sectors in the survey, no distinct sector-specific CE KPIs can be identified. The results of the interviews also show

that not only the respective product/service or business model of the company influences the selection of CE KPIs, but that economic incentives also play a major role. Companies in the Construction and Buildings sector are focussing more on product-specific CE indicators, which are mentioned in frequently used product certifications. Improving circularity in the areas relevant for certification, such as increasing the proportion of biomass or recycled materials in products, ensures higher sales figures as the products of the companies are used more often. This can be problematic under certain circumstances if it causes the company to focus on individual product characteristics, thereby inhibiting fundamental change or rethinking.

The results of the interviews in particular show that the practical benefits for companies of external reporting on CE depend on numerous factors, such as management leadership and willingness to change. Despite the enormous additional reporting effort, especially for medium-sized and smaller companies that are only at the beginning of the transformation to CE, the reporting obligations should be seen as an opportunity for improvement. The results of the survey show that the ESRS E5 and the SASB standards contain some indicators that play an important role for companies in the practical implementation of the CE beyond external reporting and are used as CE KPIs.

Nevertheless, depending on the maturity of the company, most of the data to be collected represents additional reporting effort, which ties up financial and human resources in companies. However, the objective of the CSRD or the SASB is not to reflect the company's internal KPIs relevant to the management and measurement of CE, but rather to provide external stakeholders, especially lenders, with a comprehensive understanding of the impacts, opportunities and risks associated with CE and resource utilisation. The omnibus directives currently being developed by the EU Commission are intended to counteract the unintended enormous reporting effort, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises, which will result in considerable simplifications in external sustainability reporting. It remains unclear at present to what extent there will be reductions in the scope of the data points to be reported.

5.2 CE Management tool

Based on the results of the SLRs, the online survey and the interviews, the findings on the development of a company-related management tool for the transformation to CE is presented. Such a management tool could be designed as a software that enables collaboration between key stakeholders both internally and externally, calculates relevant KPIs and provides decision-making aids for various corporate functions. The software solution could consist of the following elements:

Data consolidation and KPI calculation:

The results of the SLR and the empirical studies show that a successful transformation to CE requires the involvement of various central and supporting internal functions/ departments. Based on the strategy & vision as well as the company's targets, various control KPIs are defined to monitor progress in achieving these and to derive adjustment actions if necessary. A central function of the software should therefore be the calculation and visualization of these KPIs in a dashboard suitable for the company's decision-making committee regarding CE. The calculation methods for the KPIs should also be integrated in the software and be carried out both internally and externally in accordance with recognized uniform standards.

The KPIs relate to various company-specific operational functions. KPIs that relate to resource consumption (material, energy, water) and waste management in production processes and R&D are usually central to this. The calculation of these KPIs is partly based on input factors that can be retrieved internally via suitable interfaces, e.g. to the ERP-system of procurement, but also on external data from the upstream and downstream value chain. The software tool should therefore consolidate the input factors used to calculate the KPIs defined for each area. Relevant external data can, for example, relate to various reuse or recycling options, including the resulting environmental and financial impacts. In addition to the quantitative recording of the various types of materials purchased, the software should also include the option of supplier evaluation based on circular principles.

The R&D function is particularly important, as various design options, R-strategies and materials are evaluated based on their environmental impact and benefits for the CE. This requires a holistic assessment of the effects over the entire product life cycle (LCA) through the integration of emission factors and, e.g., country-specific recycling methods. A separate module should be dedicated to the software to present these complex interrelations. The financial assessment is closely linked to the ecological evaluation of CE-oriented product innovations. The finance department should therefore also have access to the software. In this way, the holistic ecological and economic evaluation can result in the derivation of various recommendations for action, which can be presented to the decision-making committee for the CE together with the central CE KPIs.

Technological requirements:

A cloud-based software application is suitable for ensuring smooth access and therefore collaboration between the various internal and external stakeholders, as it enables scalability and data integration in real time. Integration into the company's existing ERP systems via appropriate interfaces is also crucial for linking procurement, production and finance-specific data.

Compliance Tracking:

Another important function would be the monitoring of regulatory requirements and standards in CE. The tool should track the status of compliance with country- and product-specific standards and regulations, such as the EU CE strategy, local recycling requirements or lists of banned materials. It could also help to prepare the company for future regulatory requirements, such as the CSRD, by calculating the required data and providing the required reporting format. Industry-specific requirements resulting from various product certifications could also be incorporated to take compliance with these into account when developing products. Such a software tool for managing the transition to CE would help companies to achieve their goals efficiently by integrating the entire production and value chain processes. The combination of data-driven recommendations for action and the involvement of all relevant departments and external partners creates a comprehensive platform and enables coordinated collaboration.

5.3 Limitations

The conclusions derived from the results of this research work are subject to several limitations that need to be considered. Firstly, the results are limited to the selected core sectors for the transformation to CE according to the EU Commission. Additional CE KPIs may therefore arise for other sectors. Despite the weighting of the results, the very heterogeneous sector distribution within the participating companies in the survey does not allow any representative statements to be made regarding sector-specific KPIs. This applies to the „Packaging“, „Food, water and nutrients“ and „Textiles“ sectors, as only very small samples with 1 or 2 participants are available. The similarities and differences between the KPIs used by the companies to manage the CE and the indicators of the analysed standards and frameworks based on the classification criteria are also subject to limitations.

The classification of these is based on a subjective interpretation and is not always trivial in some cases, especially when assigning the life cycle phase, as several phases are addressed simultaneously. This applies especially to the Make- or Take-phase. Probably the greatest limitation is the assumption that not all the KPIs selected by the companies in the survey are used as KPIs, but that some of them are only indicators, even though the survey specifically asked for KPIs. The reason for this is that an average of 23 KPIs were selected per company in the survey. This number appears somewhat large for KPIs that only relate to CE in companies. This assumption is further confirmed by the two statements made by the interview participants, according to which the development of CE KPIs is currently underway and, in both cases, no central KPIs have yet been defined. The interviewed companies are currently in the development phase of coordinated, centralised

implementation and management of CE measures. This suggests that the companies may not yet fully realise that some of the selected indicators also represent a KPI. There is also a lack of responsibility for defining and adhering to central CE KPIs. Based on the research results, a clear recommendation can be made to adapt the research design of the study by focussing on one industry and only conducting interviews. This would avoid any misunderstandings and allow more targeted questions to be asked about CE KPIs and challenges in the definition and implementation. In this way more reliable statements concerning the use of CE KPIs in the specific sector can be made.

6 Outlook and conclusion

The following chapter is divided into a summary of the most important results of this research work to answer the research questions and a brief description of the need for further research.

6.1 Conclusion

In general, the survey results show that the companies in the relevant economic sectors already collect numerous indicators (KPIs) to measure the transformation to CE, although they differ in their degree of maturity. The KPIs most frequently used by companies are contained in the external CE reporting standards ESRS E5 and the industry-specific SASB standards. This is a clear indication that although most companies have not yet dealt with one of these two standards, the indicators of these already have great practical relevance and cannot just be seen as additional bureaucracy or reporting effort. It is also clearly recognisable that the complex, multidimensional CE indicators developed by academics are not used as CE KPIs in practice, as has already been assumed. The CE KPIs used by the companies show numerous differences and similarities compared to the indicators of the analysed standards and frameworks, which are presented based on six classification criteria. The results show that all standards and frameworks contain potential CE KPIs and therefore contribute to different degrees to driving CE in companies.

There is no doubt, however, that the application of these also represents an additional effort for the organisation. The extent depends on the company's level of maturity and leadership regarding CE. Not all the indicators included are suitable as CE KPIs in companies; the collection of qualitative data in particular aims to provide external stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of the company's impacts, opportunities and risks in relation to CE and resource use. None of the analysed standards and frameworks contain indicators that include all life cycle phases, R-strategies and relevant internal functions and measure CE holistically against the background of the classification criteria. The definition of CE KPIs in companies also depends on the respective strategy, objectives, business model and economic activities and is very individual. The results of the online survey revealed several industry-specific and overarching indicators, although their informative value is very limited due to the very heterogeneous distribution of industries.

A general statement about which of the analysed standards and frameworks is most suitable for companies to measure and manage the transformation to CE holistically using KPIs is therefore only possible to a limited extent. The findings of the interviews and the large average number of KPIs selected by the companies in the online survey give reason to assume that not all the selected KPIs

are really KPIs, but rather decentralised CE indicators. Against the background of this main limitation, the main research question on the use of CE KPIs in practice cannot be answered clearly and satisfactorily.

However, clear conclusions can be drawn regarding the relevant internal functions that are affected by the CE. Both the SLRs and the indicators of the standards and frameworks as well as the KPIs used by the companies in practice show that the Operations function with the categories of resource consumption and waste management plays a central role in the definition of CE KPIs for measuring and controlling the transformation to CE. Based on the results of the SLRs and the empirical studies, numerous suggestions for a CE management tool can be derived. In addition to data collection and the calculation of KPIs, central functions include the economic and ecological evaluation of circular improvement measures. Furthermore, the integration of all relevant internal functions and relevant external partners via suitable interfaces should be made possible to drive CE forward in a holistic, efficient and collaborative manner.

6.2 Further research

Finally, further research needs can be derived from the results of this scientific work. In particular, the results of the interviews suggest that most of the analysed companies are in the development phase of implementing CE and defining associated KPIs. It remains to be seen to what extent the simplifications of the EU Commission regarding mandatory sustainability reporting in accordance with the ESRS will help to reduce the additional reporting burden for companies and focus on material information and KPIs in relation to the CE. In particular, the planned reduction in the number of data points to be disclosed has the potential to require companies to disclose only material information and at the same time meet the information needs of external stakeholders. The remaining indicators relating to the CE should be analysed in terms of their application and suitability as CE KPIs. In addition, it should be checked whether the remaining disclosure requirements provide a holistic picture of the transformation to CE and whether all relevant life cycle phases, R-strategies and internal functions are included. The suggestions made regarding the components and functions of the CE management tool can also be further concretised with the involvement of relevant stakeholders and departments of the company. Interviews can be a very productive method for finding out the requirements and needs of the people responsible in the companies.

List of references

- Azevedo, Susana; Godina, Radu; Matias, João (2017): Proposal of a Sustainable Circular Index for Manufacturing Companies. In: *Resources* 6 (4), S. 63. DOI: 10.3390/resources6040063.
- Bannier, Christina (2023): Nachhaltigkeitsberichterstattung – Aktuelle Herausforderungen und Chancen für Großunternehmen und Mittelständler. In: Yvonne Zwick und Kristina Jeromin (Hg.): *Mit Sustainable Finance die Transformation dynamisieren. Wie Finanzwirtschaft nachhaltiges Wirtschaften ermöglicht*. 1. Aufl. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler, S. 159–170, zuletzt geprüft am 20.03.2025.
- Barros, Murillo Vetroni; Salvador, Rodrigo; do Prado, Guilherme Francisco; Francisco, Antonio Carlos de; Piekarski, Cassiano Moro (2021): Circular economy as a driver to sustainable businesses. In: *Cleaner Environmental Systems* 2, S. 100006. DOI: 10.1016/j.cesys.2020.100006.
- Bauer, Kent (2004): KPIs - The Metrics That Drive Performance Management. In: *DM Review* 09.2004, 2004 (9), S. 63. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.proquest.com/openview/dc6ab764896a552c4a38fc7dca106792/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=51938>, zuletzt geprüft am 11.02.2025.
- Beiersdorf, Kati (2023): ISSB-Internationalisierung der SASB Standards. Hg. v. Deutsches Rechnungslegungs Standards Committee e.V. (DRSC). Berlin. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.drsc.de/projekte/62222/>, zuletzt aktualisiert am 04.02.2025.
- Benyus, Janine M. (1997): *Biomimicry: Innovation inspired by nature*. New York, zuletzt geprüft am 25.01.2025.
- Bortz, Jürgen; Döring, Nicola (2016): *Forschungsmethoden Forschungsmethoden und Evaluation für Human- und Sozialwissenschaftler*. 5. Aufl. Heidelberg: Springer Verlag. Online verfügbar unter DOI 10.1007/978-3-642-41089-5, zuletzt geprüft am 18.02.2025.
- Capellini, M. (2017): Measure the circularity of a public lighting system. Hg. v. Marco Capellini, Sustainable Design & Consulting. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.capcon.it/en/measure-the-circularity-of-a-public-lighting-system/>, zuletzt geprüft am 15.02.2025.
- Cayzer, Steve; Griffiths, Percy; Beghetto, Valentina (2017): Design of indicators for measuring product performance in the circular economy. In: *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering* 10 (4-5), S. 289–298. DOI: 10.1080/19397038.2017.1333543.
- Ciechan-Kujawa, Marlena; Zarzycka, Ewelina; Krasodomska, Joanna (2024): On the way to a circular economy: the use of Key Performance Indicators in measuring and reporting organisations progress. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781035314225.00018>, zuletzt geprüft am 17.02.2025.
- ISO/FDIS 59020, 05.2024: Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity performance. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.iso.org/standard/80650.html>, zuletzt geprüft am 04.02.2025.

ISO/FDIS 59004, 05.2024: Circular economy — Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.iso.org/standard/80648.html>, zuletzt geprüft am 17.02.2025.

Commoner, Barry (2020): *The closing circle: nature, man, and technology*. New York: Courier Dover Publications. Online verfügbar unter https://books.google.de/books?hl=de&lr=&id=F2DRDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&ots=XZwrF4pMtR&sig=PYRWwHzRbQmtAFGVZWuABsmt9mk&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false, zuletzt geprüft am 24.01.2025.

Corona, Blanca; Shen, Li; Reike, Denise; Rosales Carreón, Jesús; Worrell, Ernst (2019): Towards sustainable development through the circular economy—A review and critical assessment on current circularity metrics. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 151, S. 104498. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104498.

Cullen, Jonathan M. (2017): Circular Economy: Theoretical Benchmark or Perpetual Motion Machine? In: *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 21 (3), S. 483–486. DOI: 10.1111/jiec.12599.

Das, Sanchoy K.; Yedlarajiah, Pradeep; Narendra, Raj (2000): An approach for estimating the end-of-life product disassembly effort and cost. In: *International Journal of Production Research* 38 (3), S. 657–673. DOI: 10.1080/002075400189356.

Denyer, D.; Tranfield, D. (2009): Producing a systematic review. In: D. Buchanan und A. Bryman (Hg.): *The Sage handbook of organizational research methods*: Sage Publications Ltd., S. 671-689. Online verfügbar unter <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2010-00924-039>, zuletzt geprüft am 17.02.2025.

Di Maio, Francesco; Rem, Peter Carlo (2015): A Robust Indicator for Promoting Circular Economy through Recycling. In: *JEP* 06 (10), S. 1095–1104. DOI: 10.4236/jep.2015.610096.

Di Maio, Francesco; Rem, Peter Carlo; Baldé, Kees; Polder, Michael (2017): Measuring resource efficiency and circular economy: A market value approach. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 122, S. 163–171. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.02.009.

Domínguez, Eladio; Pérez, Beatriz; Rubio, Ángel L.; Zapata, María A. (2019): A taxonomy for key performance indicators management. In: *Computer Standards & Interfaces* 64, S. 24–40. DOI: 10.1016/j.csi.2018.12.001.

Drucker, Peter F. (1977): *People and Performance: The Best of Peter Drucker on Management.*: Harper's College Press. Online verfügbar unter https://scholar.google.de/scholar?hl=de&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Peter+F.+Drucker%3A+People+and+Performance%3A+The+Best+of+Peter+Drucker+on+Management.+Harper%E2%80%99s+College+Press%2C+1977%2C&btnG=, zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

Eisenmenger, Nina; Giljum, Stefan; Lutter, Stephan; Marques, Alexandra; Theurl, Michaela; Pereira, Henrique; Tukker, Arnold (2016): Towards a Conceptual Framework for Social-Ecological Systems Integrating Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services with Resource Efficiency Indicators. In: *Sustainability* 8 (3), S. 201. DOI: 10.3390/su8030201.

Elia, Valerio; Gnoni, Maria Grazia; Tornese, Fabiana (2017): Measuring circular economy strategies through index methods: A critical analysis. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 142, S. 2741–2751. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.196.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation (Hg.) (2022): Circulytics: Measuring circular economy performance. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/resources/circulytics/resources>, zuletzt aktualisiert am 28.01.2025, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2025): Towards a circular economy: Business rationale for an accelerated transition. Hg. v. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Online verfügbar unter https://emf.thirdlight.com/file/24/_A-BkCs_h7gfln_Am1g_JKe2t9/Towards%20a%20circular%20economy%3A%20Business%20rationale%20for%20an%20accelerated%20transition.pdf, zuletzt geprüft am 21.01.2025.

EU Commission (2015): Den Kreislauf schließen - Ein Aktionsplan der EU für die Kreislaufwirtschaft. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/TodayOJ/>, zuletzt geprüft am 18.02.2025.

EU Commission (2016): Verordnung (EU) 2016/679 des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 27. April 2016 zum Schutz natürlicher Personen bei der Verarbeitung personenbezogener Daten, zum freien Datenverkehr und zur Aufhebung der Richtlinie 95/46/EG (Datenschutz-Grundverordnung). (EU) 2016/679. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj?locale=de>, zuletzt geprüft am 20.03.2025.

EU Commission (31.07.2023): Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards. (EU) 2023/2772. Online verfügbar unter https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2023/2772/oj/eng, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

EU Commission (08.11.2024): Opening remarks by President von der Leyen at the joint press conference with President Michel and Hungarian Prime Minister Orbán following the informal meeting of Heads of State or Government of 8 November 2024. Budapest, Ungarn. Mamer, Eric, eric.mamer@ec.europa.eu. Online verfügbar unter https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/statement_24_5742, zuletzt geprüft am 07.02.2025.

EU Parliament and council (19.11.2008): Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives. Directive 2008/98/EC. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/98/oj/eng>, zuletzt geprüft am 16.02.2025.

EU Parliament and council (22.10.2014): Directive 2014/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 amending Directive 2013/34/EU as regards disclosure of non-financial and diversity information by certain large undertakings and groups. Directive 2014/95/EU. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/95/oj/eng>, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

EU Parliament and council (18.07.2020): Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088. Regulation (EU) 2020/852. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj/eng>, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

EU Parliament and council (14.12.2022): Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 537/2014, Directive 2004/109/EC, Directive 2006/43/EC and Directive 2013/34/EU, as regards corporate sustainability reporting. Directive (EU) 2022/2464. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2464/oj/eng>, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

EU Parliament and council (13.06.2024): Directive (EU) 2024/1760 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Regulation (EU) 2023/2859. Directive (EU) 2024/1760. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1760/oj/eng>, zuletzt geprüft am 28.01.2025.

Europäischer Rat (08.11.2024): Informal meeting of heads of state or government, Budapest, 7-8 November 2024. Budapest. Ecaterina Casinge. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/meetings/european-council/2024/11/07-08/>, zuletzt geprüft am 04.02.2025.

European Commission (11.12.2019): The European Green Deal. COM(2019) 640 final. Fundstelle: EUR-Lex Document 52019DC0640. Online verfügbar unter https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0021.02/DOC_1&format=PDF.

European Commission (11.03.2020): A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe. COM/2020/98 final. Fundstelle: EUR-Lex Document 52020DC0098. Online verfügbar unter <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>.

Eurostat (2025): Eurostat. EU Commission. Luxemburg. Online verfügbar unter https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10_a64__custom_15537567/default/table?lang=en, zuletzt aktualisiert am 25.02.2025.

Evans, J.; Bocken, N. (2013): The Circular Economy Toolkit. Online verfügbar unter <http://circulareconomytoolkit.org/>, zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

Falkenberg, Christof; Schneeberger, Carina; Pöchtrager, Siegfried (2023): Is Sustainability Reporting Promoting a Circular Economy? Analysis of Companies' Sustainability Reports in the Agri-Food Sector in the Scope of Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive and EU Taxonomy Regulation. Hg. v. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). Department of Economics and Social Sciences, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences. Basel. Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097498>, zuletzt geprüft am 07.02.2025.

Fogarassy, Cs.; Kovacs, A.; Horvath, B.; Borocz, M. (2017): THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CIRCULAR EVALUATION (CEV) TOOL – CASE STUDY FOR THE 2024 BUDAPEST OLYMPICS. Hungarian Agricultural Engineering. Ungarn. Online verfügbar unter

[https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=The%20development%20of%20a%20circular%20evaluation%20\(CEV\)%20tool&author=C.%20Fogarassy&publication_year=2017&pages=10-20](https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=The%20development%20of%20a%20circular%20evaluation%20(CEV)%20tool&author=C.%20Fogarassy&publication_year=2017&pages=10-20), zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

Föhl, Ulrich; Friedrich, Christine (2022): Quick Guide Onlinefragebogen. Wie Sie Ihre Zielgruppe professionell im Web befragen. 1. Aufl. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler. Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-36291-1>.

Franklin-Johnson, Elizabeth; Figge, Frank; Canning, Louise (2016): Resource duration as a managerial indicator for Circular Economy performance. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 133, S. 589–598. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.05.023.

Gabler, Siegfried (2006): Gewichtungprobleme in der Datenanalyse. In: Andreas Diekmann (Hg.): Methoden der Sozialforschung. Köln: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, S. 128–147. Online verfügbar unter https://kzfss.uni-koeln.de/sites/kzfss/pdf/SH_44-2004.pdf#page=214, zuletzt geprüft am 07.03.2025.

Geissdoerfer, Martin; Morioka, Sandra Naomi; Carvalho, Marly Monteiro de; Evans, Steve (2018): Business models and supply chains for the circular economy. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 190, S. 712–721. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.04.159.

Geissdoerfer, Martin; Savaget, Paulo; Bocken, Nancy M.P.; Hultink, Erik Jan (2017): The Circular Economy – A new sustainability paradigm? In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 143, S. 757–768. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.048.

German Federal Ministry of Justice (17.04.2024): Handelsgesetzbuch. HGB. Online verfügbar unter https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/hgb/_267.html.

Ghisellini, Patrizia; Cialani, Catia; Ulgiati, Sergio (2016): A review on circular economy: the expected transition to a balanced interplay of environmental and economic systems. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 114, S. 11–32. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.09.007.

Graedel, T. E.; Allwood, Julian; Birat, Jean-Pierre; Buchert, Matthias; Hagelüken, Christian; Reck, Barbara K. et al. (2011): What Do We Know About Metal Recycling Rates? In: *J of Industrial Ecology* 15 (3), S. 355–366. DOI: 10.1111/j.1530-9290.2011.00342.x.

Graedel, Thomas E.; Allenby, B. R. (1996): ON THE CONCEPT OF INDUSTRIAL ECOLOGY. *Annual Review of Energy and the Environment* 21.1. Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.21.1.69>, zuletzt geprüft am 25.01.2025.

GRI Initiative (2025): How to use the GRI standards. Hg. v. GRI Initiative. Boston. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.globalreporting.org/how-to-use-the-gri-standards/>, zuletzt geprüft am 02.02.2025.

Heintze, Robin (2023): KPI vs Metrik – Unterschiedliche Definitionen von KPIs und Metriken. Köln. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.more-fire.com/blog/kpi-vs-metrik-unterschiedliche-definitionen-von-kpis-und-metriken/>, zuletzt geprüft am 11.02.2025.

Heyes, Graeme; Sharmina, Maria; Mendoza, Joan Manuel F.; Gallego-Schmid, Alejandro; Azapagic, Adisa (2018): Developing and implementing circular economy business models in service-oriented technology companies. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 177, S. 621–632. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.168.

Huysman, Sofie; Schaepmeester, Jonas de; Ragaert, Kim; Dewulf, Jo; Meester, Steven de (2017): Performance indicators for a circular economy: A case study on post-industrial plastic waste. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 120, S. 46–54. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.01.013.

IFRS Foundation (2025): Using the SASB Standards. Hg. v. IFRS Foundation. Delaware. Online verfügbar unter <https://sasb.ifrs.org/company-use/>, zuletzt geprüft am 02.02.2025.

Janik, Agnieszka; Ryszek, Adam (2019): Circular economy in companies: an analysis of selected indicators from a managerial perspective. In: *Multidisciplinary Aspects of Production Engineering* 2 (1), S. 523–535. DOI: 10.2478/mape-2019-0053.

Jerome, Adeline; Helander, Harald; Ljunggren, Maria; Janssen, Matty (2022): Mapping and testing circular economy product-level indicators: A critical review. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 178, S. 106080. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106080.

Kalmykova, Yuliya; Sadagopan, Madumita; Rosado, Leonardo (2018): Circular economy – From review of theories and practices to development of implementation tools. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 135, S. 190–201. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.10.034.

Katrin Schmidt (2018): NACE. Ausführliche Definition im Online-Lexikon. Hg. v. Gabler Wirtschaftslexikon. Online verfügbar unter <https://wirtschaftslexikon.gabler.de/definition/nace-41654/version-265015>, zuletzt geprüft am 19.01.2025.

Kaza, Silpa; Yao, Lisa; Bhada-Tata, Perinaz; van Woerden, Frank (Hg.) (2018): What a waste 2.0. A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050. World Bank Group. Washington D.C.

Kingfisher (2014): The business opportunity of closed loop innovation. Westminster, UK. Online verfügbar unter https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=The%20Business%20Opportunity%20of%20Closed%20Loop%20Innovation%20-%20Closed%20Loop%20Innovation%20Booklet&author=Kingfisher&publication_year=2014#d=gs_cit&t=1739633048577&u=%2Fscholar%3Fq%3Dinfo%3AvkHu5bPOI-kJ%3Ascholar.google.com%2F%26output%3Dcite%26scirp%3D0%26hl%3Dde, zuletzt aktualisiert am 15.02.2025.

Kirchherr, Julian; Reike, Denise; Hekkert, Marko (2017): Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 127, S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005.

Koller, Matthias; Löwe, Christian (2010): Ökodesign von Produkten. Gestaltungsauftrag für mehr Umweltschutz und Innovation. Hg. v. Bundesumweltministerium Umweltbundesamt. Online verfügbar unter

<https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/3154.pdf>, zuletzt geprüft am 20.03.2025.

Kraft, Michael Hans Gino; Christ, Oliver; Scherer, Lukas (2022): Management der Kreislaufwirtschaft. Positionierung und Gestaltung zirkulärer Unternehmen. 1. Aufl. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler. Online verfügbar unter <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-658-39225-3>.

Kristensen, Heidi Simone; Mosgaard, Mette Alberg (2020): A review of micro level indicators for a circular economy – moving away from the three dimensions of sustainability? In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 243, S. 118531. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118531.

Lin, David; Wackernagel, Mathis (2024): Nowcasting the World's Footprint & Biocapacity for 2024. Hg. v. Global Footprint Network. Online verfügbar unter <https://overshoot.footprintnetwork.org/content/uploads/2024/06/2024-Nowcast-explained.pdf>.

Linder, Marcus; Sarasini, Steven; van Loon, Patricia (2017): A Metric for Quantifying Product-Level Circularity. In: *J of Industrial Ecology* 21 (3), S. 545–558. DOI: 10.1111/jiec.12552.

Lyle, John Tillman (1996): Regenerative design for sustainable development. New York: John Wiley & Sons. Online verfügbar unter https://books.google.de/books?hl=de&lr=&id=qB3v3gYofSUC&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&ots=Debkom7Ngg&sig=8s-v0P25XmhnKJoYSMrslfRjpE4&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false, zuletzt geprüft am 24.01.2025.

MacArthur, Ellen (2015): Circularity indicators: An approach to measuring circularity. Hg. v. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Online verfügbar unter https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=Circularity%20Indicators%20-%20an%20Approach%20to%20Measure%20Circularity&author=EMF-Ellen%20MacArthur%20Foundation&publication_year=2015#d=gs_cit&t=1739203647662&u=%2Fscholar%3Fq%3Dinfo%3A5_KZs5ID8EQJ%3Ascholar.google.com%2F%26output%3Dcite%26scirp%3D0%26hl%3Dde, zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

MacArthur, Ellen (2022): Circulytics. Weighting and scoring approach. Hg. v. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Isle of Wight, United Kingdom. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/resources/circulytics/resources>, zuletzt geprüft am 04.02.2025.

Matos, Joana; Martins, Carla; Simões, Carla L.; Simoes, Ricardo (2023): Comparative analysis of micro level indicators for evaluating the progress towards a circular economy. In: *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 39, S. 521–533. DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2023.06.002.

Mayring, Philipp (2010): Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. In: Günther Mey und Katja Mruck (Hg.): Handbuch Qualitative Forschung in der Psychologie. 1. Aufl. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag, S. 601–613. Online verfügbar unter <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-3-531-92052-8.pdf>, zuletzt geprüft am 18.02.2025.

McDonough, Braungart (2016): Material Reutilization Cycles Across Industries and Production Lines. Cham, Schweiz: Springer Open. Online verfügbar unter

<https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12657/27791/1002214.pdf?sequence=1#page=170>, zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

McDonough, William; Braungart, Michael (2010): *Cradle to cradle: Remaking the way we make things*. 1. Aufl. New York: North point press. Online verfügbar unter https://books.google.de/books?hl=de&lr=&id=KFX5RprPGQ0C&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&ots=itFoA-riEi&sig=m4X4ii_GBpbG4XnSu3PwJujF6Kg&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false, zuletzt geprüft am 24.01.2025.

Meyer, Wolfgang (2023): Schlaglicht: Gütekriterien für Indikatoren: Validität, Reliabilität, Objektivität. In: *Indikatoren in Entscheidungsprozessen*: Springer VS, Wiesbaden, S. 149–151. Online verfügbar unter https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-658-40638-7_21.

Microsoft Forms: Microsoft. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.microsoft.com/de-de/microsoft-365/online-surveys-polls-quizzes>, zuletzt geprüft am 23.02.2025.

Mohamed Sultan, Al Amin; Lou, Eric; Mativenga, Paul Tarisai (2017): What should be recycled: An integrated model for product recycling desirability. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 154, S. 51–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.03.201.

Moraga, Gustavo; Huysveld, Sophie; Mathieux, Fabrice; Blengini, Gian Andrea; Alaerts, Luc; van Acker, Karel et al. (2019): Circular economy indicators: What do they measure? In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 146, S. 452–461. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.03.045.

Morseletto, Piero (2020): Targets for a circular economy. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 2020 (153). Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104553>.

Northdata (2024): Northdata. Hg. v. Northdata. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.northdata.de/>, zuletzt geprüft am 17.12.2024.

Oberle, Bruno; Bringezu, Stefan; Hatfield-Dodds, Steve; Hellweg, Stefanie; Schandl, Heinz; Clement, Jessica (2019): *Global Resources Outlook 2019: Natural Resources for the Future We Want*. Hg. v. International Resource Panel. United Nations Environment Programme. Nairobi, Kenya. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.resourcepanel.org/reports/global-resources-outlook-2019>.

Obst, Daniel (2024): Die Chancen der CSRD: Zehn Vorteile für Unternehmen – und einer für uns alle. Hg. v. Haufe-Lexware GmbH & Co. KG. Freiburg. Online verfügbar unter https://www.haufe.de/sustainability/debatte/chancen-der-csrd-zehn-vorteile-fuer-unternehmen_575768_623830.html, zuletzt geprüft am 07.02.2025.

OECD-Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2015): *Measuring and managing results in development co-operation*: <bound method Organization.get_name_with_acronym of <Organization: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Online verfügbar unter <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/4117623/measuring-and-managing-results-in-development-co-operation/4925847/>, zuletzt geprüft am 11.02.2025.

Oliveira, Carla Tognato de; Dantas, Thales Eduardo Tavares; Soares, Sebastião Roberto (2021): Nano and micro level circular economy indicators: Assisting decision-makers in circularity assessments. In: *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 26, S. 455–468. DOI: 10.1016/j.spc.2020.11.024.

Opferkuch, Katelin; Caeiro, Sandra; Salomone, Roberta; Ramos, Tomás B. (2021): Circular economy in corporate sustainability reporting: A review of organisational approaches. In: *Bus Strat Env* 30 (8), S. 4015–4036. DOI: 10.1002/bse.2854.

Pádua Pieroni, Marina de; Pigosso, Daniela C.A.; McAlloone, Tim C. (2018): Sustainable Qualifying Criteria for Designing Circular Business Models. In: *Procedia CIRP* 69, S. 799–804. DOI: 10.1016/j.procir.2017.11.014.

Page, M. J.; McKenzie, J. E.; Bossuyt, P. M.; Boutron, I.; Hoffmann, T. C.; Mulrow, C. D. et al. (2021): The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.bmj.com/content/bmj/372/bmj.n71.full.pdf>, zuletzt geprüft am 18.02.2025.

Park, Joo Young; Chertow, Marian R. (2014): Establishing and testing the "reuse potential" indicator for managing wastes as resources. In: *Journal of Environmental Management* 137, S. 45–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.11.053.

Park, Kijung; Kremer, Gül E.Okudan (2017): Text mining-based categorization and user perspective analysis of environmental sustainability indicators for manufacturing and service systems. In: *Ecological Indicators* 72, S. 803–820. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.08.027.

Pascale, Angelina de; Arbolino, Roberta; Szopik-Depczyńska, Katarzyna; Limosani, Michele; Ioppolo, Giuseppe (2021): A systematic review for measuring circular economy: The 61 indicators. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 281, S. 124942. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124942.

Patil, Rashmi Anoop; van Langen, Sven Kevin; Ramakrishna, Seeram (2023): Circularity at Micro Level: A Business Perspective. In: *Circularity Assessment: Macro to Nano*: Springer, Singapore, S. 75–86. Online verfügbar unter https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-19-9700-6_5.

Pauli, Gunter A. (2010): *The Blue Economy: 10 Years, 100 Innovations, 100 Million Jobs*. Taos, New Mexico: Paradigm Publications. Online verfügbar unter https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=The%20Blue%20Economy%3A%2010%20Years%2C%20100%20Innovations%2C%20100%20Million%20Jobs&author=G.A.%20Pauli&publication_year=2010, zuletzt geprüft am 25.01.2025.

Pearce, David W.; Turner, R. Kerry (1989): *Economics of natural resources and the environment*. 1. Aufl.: Johns Hopkins University Press.

Porter, Michael E. (1985): *Competitive Advantage*. New York: The Free Press. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.ifm.eng.cam.ac.uk/research/dstools/value-chain-/>, zuletzt geprüft am 23.02.2025.

Potting, Jose; Hekkert, Marko; Worrell, Ernst; Hanemaaijer, Aldert (2017): CIRCULAR ECONOMY: MEASURING INNOVATION IN THE PRODUCT CHAIN. In: *PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency*. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.pbl.nl/uploads/default/downloads/pbl-2016-circular-economy-measuring-innovation-in-product-chains-2544.pdf>, zuletzt geprüft am 25.01.2025.

Rechenberg, Wolff von (2023): *Rechnungswesen - internes und externes Rechnungswesen*. Hg. v. Reimus.NET GmbH. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.rechnungswesen->

portal.de/Fachinfo/Grundlagen/Rechnungswesen-internes-und-externes-Rechnungswesen.html, zuletzt geprüft am 20.03.2025.

Roos Lindgreen, Erik; Salomone, Roberta; Reyes, Tatiana (2020): A Critical Review of Academic Approaches, Methods and Tools to Assess Circular Economy at the Micro Level. In: *Sustainability* 12 (12), S. 4973. DOI: 10.3390/su12124973.

Saidani, Michael; Yannou, Bernard; Leroy, Yann; Cluzel, François (2017): How to Assess Product Performance in the Circular Economy? Proposed Requirements for the Design of a Circularity Measurement Framework. In: *Recycling* 2 (1), S. 6. DOI: 10.3390/recycling2010006.

Saidani, Michael; Yannou, Bernard; Leroy, Yann; Cluzel, François; Kendall, Alissa (2019): A taxonomy of circular economy indicators. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 207, S. 542–559. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.10.014.

Salvador, Rodrigo; Barros, Murillo Vetroni; dos Santos, Giovani Elias Tagliaferro; van Mierlo, Karen Godoi; Piekarski, Cassiano Moro; Francisco, Antonio Carlos de (2021): Towards a green and fast production system: Integrating life cycle assessment and value stream mapping for decision making. In: *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 87, S. 106519. DOI: 10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106519.

Scheepens, A. E.; Vogtländer, J. G.; Brezet, J. C. (2016): Two life cycle assessment (LCA) based methods to analyse and design complex (regional) circular economy systems. Case: making water tourism more sustainable. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 114, S. 257–268. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.05.075.

Singh, Rajesh Kumar; Murty, H. R.; Gupta, S. K.; Dikshit, A. K. (2012): An overview of sustainability assessment methodologies. In: *Ecological Indicators* 15 (1), S. 281–299. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.01.007.

Stahel, Walter R. (2010): *The performance economy*. 2. Aufl. New York: Palgrave Macmillan Basingstoke. Online verfügbar unter https://books.google.de/books?hl=de&lr=&id=Oh5-DAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&ots=-3tIroY7gl&sig=cK9hsvBYlqOuoG9rPU2r5dlCOlw&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false, zuletzt geprüft am 24.01.2025.

Steffen, Will; Richardson, Katherine; Rockström, Johan; Cornell, Sarah E.; Fetzer, Ingo; Bennett, Elena M. et al. (2015): Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. In: *American Association for the Advancement of Science*, 15.01.2015. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.science.org/doi/full/10.1126/science.1259855>, zuletzt geprüft am 21.01.2025.

Su, Biwei; Heshmati, Almas; Geng, Yong; Yu, Xiaoman (2013): A review of the circular economy in China: moving from rhetoric to implementation. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 42, S. 215–227. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.11.020.

The ResCoM platform and tools (Hg.) (2017): ResCoM. Resource Conservative Manufacturing Project. ResCoM. Online verfügbar unter <http://www.rescoms.eu/platform-and-tools>, zuletzt geprüft am 10.02.2025.

Tranfield, D.; Denyer, D.; Smart, P. (Hg.) (2003): Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review: *British Journal of Management*. Online verfügbar unter <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1467-8551.00375>, zuletzt geprüft am 17.02.2025.

Vanegas, Paul; Peeters, Jef R.; Cattrysse, Dirk; Tecchio, Paolo; Ardente, Fulvio; Mathieux, Fabrice et al. (2018): Ease of disassembly of products to support circular economy strategies. In: *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 135, S. 323–334. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.06.022.

Vinante, Christian; Sacco, Pasqualina; Orzes, Guido; Borgianni, Yuri (2020): Circular economy metrics: Literature review and company-level classification framework. In: *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2021 (288). Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125090>, zuletzt geprüft am 19.01.2025.

WBCSD; KPMG (2023): Circular Transition Indicators V4.0. Metrics for business, by business. Hg. v. World Business Council for Sustainable Development. World Business Council for Sustainable Development. Genf, Schweiz. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.wbcsd.org/resources/circular-transition-indicators-v4/>, zuletzt aktualisiert am 30.05.2023.

Wilts, Henning (2021): Kreislaufwirtschaft als gesellschaftspolitische Herausforderung. In: *Gesellschaft • Wirtschaft • Politik (GWP)* 70. Jahrgang (3), S. 371–382. Online verfügbar unter <https://doi.org/10.3224/gwp.v70i3.06>.

Witte, Frank (2018): Definition, Historie und Nutzen von Metriken. In: *Metriken für das Testreporting*: Springer Vieweg, Wiesbaden, S. 1–6. Online verfügbar unter https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-658-19845-9_1.

List of annexes

Annex 1: Survey questionnaire	XVIII
Annex 2: Survey invitation and data protection	XXVIII
Annex 3: Mapping of EU sectors and NACE-Codes	XXX
Annex 4: Input screen North data database	XXXI
Annex 5: Interview questionnaire	XXXII
Annex 6: Data protection and conditions of participation.....	XXXIV
Annex 7: Interview transcription.....	XXXVI

Annex 1: Survey questionnaire

Survey questionnaire	
No.	Question
Introduction	
<p>Thank you for taking part in my survey. First of all, a few general notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular economy is abbreviated to 'CE' throughout the survey. - The survey mainly contains tick box questions. If you have to provide additional information, please be very precise. - Have fun completing the survey! 	
1	Please enter the name of the company for which the survey is being conducted:
2	<p>Which of the following economic sectors most closely reflects your business activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastics and synthetics - Textiles - Electronics and ICT - Food, water and nutrients - Packaging - Batteries and vehicles - Construction and buildings
3	<p>Do you deal with the topic of circular economy (CE) as part of your corporate sustainability efforts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No
4	<p>Please select from the following options why you are not addressing CE as part of your sustainability efforts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE not considered a material topic - Lack of expertise - Lack of time - Lack of budget - There are plans to look more closely at CE in the future - Other, please explain briefly
Main part	
Identification of CE KPIs	
<p>As CE relates to different perspectives and functions within an organisation, it is important to take a holistic view in order to implement, measure and manage the topic. This includes identifying and recording relevant key figures and calculating management KPIs at the various levels. The following questions relate to internal KPIs on CE, divided into the functions of a company according to Michael Porter's value chain. The focus here is clearly on the identification of CE-related management KPIs that are internally relevant for your company in order to promote and implement CE.</p>	

Value Chain ebd. Michael Porter

Firm infrastructure

The Firm Infrastructure category includes the following relevant perspectives for CE:

- 1 Strategy & vision
- 2 Business model
- 3 Cooperation & industrial symbiosis

1 Strategy & Vision

A company's Strategy & Vision are of crucial importance for the transformation to a CE, as they form the basis for systematic and long-term change.

4

Do you deal with the topic of CE in relation to your company-wide strategy and vision?

- Yes
- CE does not play a role in your company's strategy and vision.
- No, but planned in the near future.

5

Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for the CE-related Strategy & Vision:

- A clear Strategy & Vision for the transformation to CE is in place
- Extent to which a CE strategy is integrated into the general corporate strategy (proportion of corporate objectives related to CE)
- Extent to which the company has committed to CE initiatives and allocated resources (share of budget for CE-related measures)
- Other, please specify

2 Business model

A circular business model is characterised by the systematic integration of CE principles, e.g. repair, restoration, refurbishment, reuse and recycling, in order to optimise material and energy flows in closed loops, minimise resource consumption and reduce the environmental impact along the entire value chain.

6	<p>Do you deal with the topic of CE in relation to your business model(s)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - The issue of CE does not play a role in your company's business models. - No, but planned in the near future.
7	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for circular business models (The following illustration is intended to help you answer the questions and does not have to be read in full):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Turnover or share of total turnover from sharing/rental/leasing business models (Rethink) - Turnover or share of total turnover from business models from CE-oriented collaborations with external partners - Value or share of material, water, energy and waste disposal costs in operating costs (Reduce) - Turnover or share of total turnover from refurbishment business models - Revenue or share of total revenue from remanufacturing business models - Turnover or share of total turnover from second-hand retailing/reuse business models - Turnover or share of total turnover from repurposing business models - Turnover or share of total turnover from repairing business models - Turnover or share of total turnover from 'recycling' business models - Turnover or share of total turnover from CE-orientated business models - Other, please specify

Circular economy		Strategies	
	<i>Smart product use and manufacture</i>	R0 Refuse	Make product redundant by abandoning its function or by offering the same function with a radically different product
		R1 Rethink	Make product use more intensive (e.g. by sharing product)
		R2 Reduce	Increase efficiency in product manufacture or use by consuming fewer natural resources and materials
	<i>Extend lifespan of products and its parts</i>	R3 Reuse	Reuse by another consumer of discarded product which is still in good condition and fulfils its original function
		R4 Repair	Repair and maintenance of defective product so it can be used with its original function
		R5 Refurbish	Restore an old product and bring it up to date
		R6 Remanufacture	Use parts of discarded product in a new product with the same function
		R7 Repurpose	Use discarded product or its parts in a new product with a different function
	<i>Useful application of materials</i>	R8 Recycle	Process materials to obtain the same (high grade) or lower (low grade) quality
R9 Recover		Incineration of material with energy recovery	
Linear economy			

3 Cooperation & industrial symbiosis

Cooperations with external partners play a decisive role in the transformation to a CE, e.g. research projects for improved product circularity, closing material cycles, utilisation/ sourcing of secondary materials and the development of recycling solutions. Industrial symbiosis between companies ensures that waste streams from one company become raw materials for another company.

8

Does your company deal with CE-orientated cooperations & industrial symbioses?

- Yes
- Cooperations & industrial symbioses play no role in your company for the transformation to CE
- No, but planned in the near future.

9

Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated cooperation:

- Number of collaborations with external partners/ stakeholders
- Number of improvement measures/ innovations/ business models resulting from external collaborations
- Reduction of waste disposal costs and waste streams through industrial symbiosis
- Reduction of material costs for primary raw materials through industrial symbiosis
- Other, please specify

Human Resource Management

The personnel management category includes the following relevant perspectives for CE:

- 1 Employee training
- 2 Employee satisfaction and participation

1 Employee training

Employee training on CE provides the relevant business areas and individuals (e.g. product engineers) with the knowledge and skills to develop products and services holistically, taking into account circular principles.

10

Does your company deal with employee training on CE?

- Yes
- Employee training does not play a role in the transformation to CE in your company
- No, but planned in the near future.

11

Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated employee training:

- Number of internally developed employee training courses to improve knowledge and skills on CE
- Internal employee training courses completed (number/ hours/ ratio)
- External employee training courses completed (number/ hours/ ratio)
- Other, please specify

2 Employee satisfaction & participation

The active involvement of employees in the implementation of CE encourages innovative ideas, contributes to the achievement of objectives and promotes cross-company acceptance.

12	<p>Does your company deal with employee satisfaction and participation in relation to the CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Employee satisfaction and participation do not play a role in the transformation to CE in your company - No, but planned in the near future.
----	--

13	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated employee satisfaction and participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of suggestions for improvement submitted by employees - Number of CE-related initiatives in the company - Other, please specify
----	--

Technology development
 The technological development category includes the following relevant perspective, for CE:
 1 Ecodesign

1 Ecodesign
 Ecodesign in the context of CE refers to the holistic design of products with the aim of minimising their environmental impact over their entire life cycle by systematically integrating aspects of the 9R framework. It is of central importance as it lays the foundation for closed material cycles and thus enables both ecological and economic benefits. The following illustration is intended to help you answer the questions and does not need to be read in full.

14	<p>Does your company deal with ecodesign in relation to the CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Ecodesign plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
15	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated ecodesign:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of users/ utilisation cycles p. product - Average duration of ownership p. product (e.g. years) - Average service life of the product (e.g. years) - Average product warranty granted (e.g. years) - Number of CE-related patents - Proportion of the budget used for CE-related R&D - Number/ proportion of repaired products - Number/ proportion of repairable products - Number/ proportion of refurbished products ('refurbish') - Number/ proportion of remanufactured product components ('remanufacture') - Product recyclability (%) - Product material variety - Dismantling time of a product (e.g. in h) - Other, please specify
<p>Procurement</p> <p>The Procurement category includes the following relevant perspectives for CE:</p> <p>1 Supplier selection & auditing</p> <p>2 Material sourcing</p>	
<p><u>1 Supplier selection & auditing</u></p> <p>Careful supplier selection & auditing ensures compliance with CE-related (product) standards. This helps to ensure resource-conserving processes along the entire value chain.</p>	
16	<p>Does your company deal with supplier selection & auditing in relation to the CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Supplier selection & auditing plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
17	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated supplier selection & auditing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existence of a policy for CE-orientated supplier evaluation and selection - Proportion of CE-related assessment criteria (e.g. in questionnaires/ checklists) in supplier audits - Percentage/ number of suppliers that comply with your company's CE guidelines - Other, please specify
<p><u>2 Material sourcing</u></p> <p>CE-oriented material sourcing refers to the targeted selection and use of renewable, reusable or recycled materials to minimise the consumption of resources and promote closed material cycles.</p>	

18	<p>Does your company deal with supplier selection & auditing in relation to the CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Material sourcing plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
----	--

19	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated material sourcing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existence of concepts/ guidelines for CE-orientated sourcing - Number/ mass of purchased products with CE-orientated product certifications (e.g. cradle-to-cradle etc.) - Proportion/ mass of purchased secondary materials - Proportion/ mass of renewable materials purchased - Cost savings through the purchase of secondary materials instead of primary materials - Other, please specify
----	---

Inbound & Outbound Logistics

The logistics category includes the following relevant perspectives for CE:

1 Reverse logistics

1 Reverse logistics

Reverse logistics involves organising the return of products and materials after use in order to reprocess, recycle and much more. This enables closed material cycles to conserve valuable raw materials and avoid waste.

20	<p>Does your company deal with reverse logistics in relation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Reverse logistics plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
----	--

21	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated reverse logistics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number/ proportion of products with take-back policies - Number/ proportion of products that are returned to the manufacturer at the end of their useful life - Other, please specify
----	---

Operations

The Operations category includes the following relevant perspectives for the CE:

1 Resource consumption (energy, water, materials)

2 Waste management

3 Resource recovery

1 Resource consumption (energy, water, materials)

When implementing CE principles in the company, it is important to utilise the resources used (water, energy and materials) as efficiently as possible and to intensify their use.

22	<p>Does your company deal with resource consumption in relation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Resource consumption does not play a role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
23	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated resource consumption:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proportion of recycled/ reused/ recycled water (total or p. product unit) - Water consumption in production processes (total or p. product unit) - Share of rainwater utilisation in total water consumption - Energy consumption (total or p. product unit) - Share of renewable energy (total or p. product unit) - Own production of renewable energy - Self-consumption rate of self-generated renewable energy - Total mass of products manufactured (outflow) - Total mass of technical materials purchased (inflow) - Proportion/ total mass of recycled materials purchased (inflow) - Proportion/ total mass of recyclates in products (outflow) - Proportion/ total mass of renewable materials purchased (inflow) - Proportion/ total mass of renewable materials in products (outflow) - Proportion/ total mass of organic, compostable materials used (inflow) - Proportion/ total mass of compostable, biological materials in products (outflow) - Proportion/ total mass of reused products or product components (outflow) - Proportion/ total mass of recycled packaging material used - Proportion/ total mass of renewable packaging material used - Proportion/ total mass of compostable, organic packaging material used - Other, please specify
<p><u>2 Waste management</u> CE-orientated waste management describes the systematic handling of waste in order to return it as fully as possible as a resource to production and value creation processes.</p>	
24	<p>Does your company deal with waste management in relation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - Waste management plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE - No, but planned in the near future.
25	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated waste management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Volume of wastewater discharge - Waste generated (total or p. product unit) - Composition of the waste (proportion/ mass of the individual components) - Proportion/ total mass of hazardous waste generated - Proportion/ total mass of radioactive waste generated - Recycling rate of waste generated - Proportion/ total mass of new materials required for recycling - Waste diverted from disposal - Waste directed to disposal - Other, please specify

3 Resource recovery

Resource recovery describes the residual utilisation of waste streams, e.g. for energy generation in waste incineration plants.

26

Does your company deal with resource recovery in relation to CE?

- Yes
- Resource recovery does not play a role in your company for the transformation to CE
- No, but planned in the near future.

27

Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for resource recovery:

- Proportion/ total mass of waste used for energy recovery
- Proportion/ total mass of hazardous and non-hazardous waste used for energy recovery
- Proportion/ total mass of products that are sent for energy recovery at the end of the utilisation phase
- Proportion/ total mass of new materials required for recycling
- Energy recovered/ generated from the utilisation of company waste/ products at the end of the use phase
- Proportion/ total mass of corporate waste/ products sent to landfill at the end of the utilisation phase
- Other, please specify

Marketing & Sales

The Marketing & Sales category includes the following relevant perspectives for CE:

1 Product marketing and communication

1 Product marketing and communication

Product marketing and communication in the context of CE aim to credibly communicate the added value of circular products in order to strengthen customer awareness, build trust and promote market acceptance.

28

Does your company deal with product marketing & communication in relation to the CE?

- Yes
- Product marketing & communication plays no role in your company for the transformation to CE
- No, but planned in the near future.

29

Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs for CE-orientated product marketing & communication:

- Number of CE-related marketing activities /campaigns
- Revenue from/ number of products sold through CE-related marketing activities/ campaigns
- Proportion/ number of products with information on recycling/ disposal/ treatment at the end of the use phase
- Seats held by company employees in CE-related legislative bodies/ standardisation committees
- Other, please specify

Finance

CE-orientated measures can have both positive and negative financial effects on a company. In this respect, risks and opportunities arise from the external environment.

30	<p>Please select from the following sample indicators those that you use in your company as KPIs in the financial area with reference to CE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantification of the anticipated financial effects of material risks arising from resource use and CE- related impacts on your company - Quantification of the anticipated financial effects of material opportunities arising from resource use and CE- related impacts on your company - No KPIs are currently available for this, but are planned for the future - Irrelevant for your company - Other, please specify
31	<p>If applicable, please name other levels/perspectives in your company that are affected by the transformation to CE. Please also state the KPIs that you use to control and monitor targets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ...
32	<p>There are already numerous standards and multidimensional indicators for measuring CE at company level. Please make a selection of those that you already use in your company:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO 59020 - Circulytics - Circular Transition Indicators (WBCSD, KPMG) - GRI 301/ 302/ 303/ 306/ 307 - Other, please specify

Conclusion

Dear participant! Thank you very much for taking part in my survey on CE KPIs at company level! With such an extensive topic, there is often not enough time and space for a questionnaire. I would therefore be very pleased if you would agree to take part in a short online interview. Please answer the following question:

33	<p>If you are willing to answer further questions about CE KPIs at company level in a personal, 20-minute online interview, please enter your contact details here so that I can contact you to arrange an appointment.</p>
34	<p>If you are interested in the anonymised results of this survey, please leave your e-mail address and name here:</p>

Annex 3: Mapping of EU sectors and NACE-Codes

Allocation of the sectors to the NACE codes		
EU-sector	NACE Codes	NACE description
Plastics	C-19	Coking plant and mineral oil processing
	C-20	Manufacture of chemical products
	C-22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic goods
Textiles	C-13	Manufacture of textiles
	C-14	Manufacture of clothing
	C-15	Manufacture of leather, leather goods and shoes
Electronics and ICT	C-26	Manufacture of computers, electronic and optical products
	C-27	Manufacture of electrical equipment
	J-61	Telecommunications
Food, water and nutrients	A-01	Agriculture, hunting and related activities
	C-10	Production of food and animal feed
	C-11	Beverage production
	C-21	Manufacture of pharmaceutical products
	E-36	Water supply
E-37	Wastewater disposal	
Packaging	C-17	Manufacture of paper, cardboard and articles thereof
Batteries and vehicles	C-29	Manufacture of motor vehicles and parts
	C-30	Other vehicle construction
Construction and buildings	F-42	Civil engineering
	F-41	Building construction
	F-43	Preparatory construction site work, construction installation and other finishing trades
	L-68	Real estate and housing

Annex 4: Input screen North data database

NORTH DATA PREMIUM SERVICE DATA SERVICE MEIN KONTO

RECHERCHIERE FIRMENBEKANNTMACHUNGEN UND FINANZIELLE KENNZAHLEN

EINFACHE SUCHE POWER-SUCHE

Land *i* Deutschland x Ort *i* Ort oder Adresse Umkreis Radius km

Rechtsform Alle Rechtsformen Status *i* Aktiv x Suchbegriffe *i* Stichwörter

Branche *i* 13 Herstellung von Textilien x Standard *i* NACE

Kennzahlen *i*

Bilanzsumme	6000001	€	-	max.	€	🗑️
Mitarbeiterzahl	51		-	max.		🗑️
Umsatz	12000001	€	-	max.	€	🗑️

+ Kennzahlenfilter + Ereignisfilter **Jetzt suchen**

Annex 5: Interview questionnaire

Interview questionnaire	
No	Question
Internal KPIs vs. external reporting	
1	Are the CE indicators you have listed in the survey KPIs (relevant for management to monitor target achievement) or are they merely indicators?
2	Which of the indicators mentioned is also a KPI? What are the relevant KPIs for monitoring the management's objectives for the CE? Is there even one KPI?
3	Is the topic of CE even brought up to the management through KPIs and integrated into strategic business decisions?
4	Was the topic of CE only addressed due to the mandatory compliance with external reporting standards (ESRS E5) or is the motivation intrinsic?
5	Is CE seen as an opportunity or driver of transformation, e.g. through the development of new circular business models/products, or rather as compliance with mandatory external reporting standards?
6	Does external reporting on CE contribute to the transformation of your organisation towards circular products and business models? -If yes, specify which frameworks/standards (GRI, ESRS E5) contribute positively and to what extent?
7	Do the external standards (ESRS E5, GRI) contain data points that are not relevant for CE in your company or that you only collect for external reporting and are of little importance internally? - If yes, please specify which data is only collected for reporting purposes.
8	Academics have developed numerous indicators for measuring CE at company level. These often include several dimensions (ecological, social, economic) and CE strategies (9R framework) and are complex to calculate. Have such rather "theoretical" indicators already been analysed and, if necessary, calculated? e.g: - MCI - Material Circularity Indicator - CTI - Circular Transition Indicators - Circulytics - Are there any other CE KPIs in addition to the ones you have specified that you use in your company? If not, why? - Complexity of the indicators -> not suitable as a KPI - Gaps in data availability for calculation - Lack of expertise/capacity - More detailed analysis planned
9	Does your company set itself specific, strategic objectives in relation to the transformation to CE?

Managementtool	
10	<p>How is the transformation to CE structured in your company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there responsible persons? - Vision, Goals, Action Plan, Roles & Responsibilities
11	<p>Which departments/ functions/ perspectives in the company are affected by the transformation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&D (implementation of CE strategies to improve product circularity) - Production (reduction of resource consumption and utilisation, waste management) - Purchasing (supplier selection, auditing) - Cooperation with external partners (industry, science, etc.) - Management (strategy, vision, objectives, business models) - Marketing & Com. (product marketing, ext. CE com.) - Employees (training, satisfaction, participation) - Customer perspective (satisfaction with CE products) - Finance (budgeting, controlling, KPI reporting and monitoring) - Logistics (reverse logistics)
12	<p>Who is responsible for setting and maintaining CE KPIs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COO (Chief Operations Officer) - CTO (Chief Technical Officer) - Business unit director - Product Owner - ...
13	<p>Is there a tool, method, ISO standard/ framework etc. that you use in your company for the transformation to CE? e.g:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE- Balanced Scorecard (financial, customer, process and development perspective) - ISO 59010/59020/59004 - Eco-Design Tools (for implementing and comparing CE strategies in the design and product development phase) - CEBR (Circular Economy Business Readiness) - CSCM (Circular Supply Chain Management Tools) -&gt; CE Supply Chain, Purchasing - Circelligence (tool from Boston Consulting Group) - Circle Assessment
14	<p>What do you currently see as the biggest obstacles or challenges in your company's transformation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What would help you the most in the transformation to CE?

Annex 7: Interview transcription

Interview 1:

Interview questionnaire		
No	Question	Answer
Part 1: Internal KPIs vs. external reporting		
1	Are the CE indicators you have listed in the survey KPIs (relevant for management to monitor target achievement) or are they merely indicators?	Yes, but the challenge lies in defining control KPIs, as CE can be measured at many different levels (product life cycle, departments, etc.)
2	Which of the indicators mentioned is also a KPI? What are the relevant KPIs for monitoring the management's objectives for the CE? Is there even one KPI?	Indikator- bottom up view KPI- Top down view KPIs Status most immature
3	Is the topic of CE even brought up to the management through KPIs and integrated into strategic business decisions?	Sustainability Board: Steering and monitoring of KPIs from different business units
4	Was the topic of CE only addressed due to the mandatory compliance with external reporting standards (ESRS E5) or is the motivation intrinsic?	No, it had already been dealt with before, there was no dedicated trigger point
5	Is CE seen as an opportunity or driver of transformation, e.g. through the development of new circular business models/products, or rather as compliance with mandatory external reporting standards?	In terms of external reporting, CE is perceived both as compliance with regulatory requirements and as an opportunity for change. The leadership style and support of executive management determine the characteristics
6	Does external reporting on CE contribute to the transformation of your organisation towards circular products and business models? -If yes, specify which frameworks/standards (GRI, ESRS E5) contribute positively and to what extent?	The CSRD requires a baseline assessment based on the type of data to be collected. This should lead to more data transparency for external stakeholders. It will depend on how the sector-specific standards are designed and whether this results in relevant KPIs/data for us.
7	Do the external standards (ESRS E5, GRI) contain data points that are not relevant for CE in your company or that you only collect for external reporting and are of little importance internally? - If yes, please specify which data is only collected for reporting purposes.	External reporting, especially CSRD, is a lot of bureaucracy and data collection involves enormous effort. However, this also makes an important contribution to improving data transparency on CE between companies. In some cases, the criteria for calculating individual indicators are rather unclear (durability, reparability). As this is a baseline assessment, the extent to which data collection represents additional effort depends on the company's level of maturity.

8	<p>Academics have developed numerous indicators for measuring CE at company level. These often include several dimensions (ecological, social, economic) and CE strategies (9R framework) and are complex to calculate. Have such rather "theoretical" indicators already been analysed and, if necessary, calculated? e.g:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MCI - Material Circularity Indicator - CTI - Circular Transition Indicators - Circulytics <p>- Are there any other CE KPIs in addition to the ones you have specified that you use in your company? If not, why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexity of the indicators -&gt; not suitable as a KPI - Gaps in data availability for calculation - Lack of expertise/capacity - More detailed analysis planned 	<p>Circulytics is used, all others not</p> <p>It will be interesting to see what innovations the development of the GCP Global Circularity Protocol will bring and what role it will play in CE in companies. With all these frameworks and aggregated indicators, it is questionable what effect they will have in the long term. The calculation of individual indicators is based on selected standards. The business divisions also develop their own indicators. These frameworks/standards are all very extensive, detailed and challenging to calculate. Significance of aggregated Indicators (complex calculation) -> do not induce concrete recommendations for action, very sector/product-specific. Acceptance for scientific indicators only limited, as added value not apparent</p>
---	--	---

9	<p>Does your company set itself specific, strategic objectives in relation to the transformation to CE?</p>	
---	---	--

Part 2: Managementtool

10	<p>How is the transformation to CE structured in your company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there responsible persons? - Vision, Goals, Action Plan, Roles & Responsibilities 	
----	---	--

11	<p>Which departments/ functions/ perspectives in the company are affected by the transformation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&D (implementation of CE strategies to improve product circularity) - Production (reduction of resource consumption and utilisation, waste management) - Purchasing (supplier selection, auditing) - Cooperation with external partners (industry, science, etc.) - Management (strategy, vision, objectives, business models) - Marketing & Com. (product marketing, ext. CE com.) - Employees (training, satisfaction, participation) - Customer perspective (satisfaction with CE products) - Finance (budgeting, controlling, KPI reporting and monitoring) - Logistics (reverse logistics) 	<p>All of them play a role. Employee awareness has been developed.</p>
----	--	--

12	<p>Who is responsible for setting and maintaining CE KPIs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COO (Chief Operations Officer) - CTO (Chief Technical Officer) - Business unit director - Product Owner 	<p>CE KPIs are managed in the Sustainability Steering Board. Subordinate to this are various sustainability officers for each business unit. Below them are the sustainability teams in the individual business units. These develop measures and implement them</p>
13	<p>Is there a tool, method, ISO standard/ framework etc. that you use in your company for the transformation to CE? e.g:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE- Balanced Scorecard (financial, customer, process and development perspective) - ISO 59010/59020/59004 - Eco-Design Tools (for implementing and comparing CE strategies in the design and product development phase) - CEBR (Circular Economy Business Readiness) 	<p>ISO standard is most generally valid for various companies. Processes are developed according to the ISO standard</p>
14	<p>What do you currently see as the biggest obstacles or challenges in your company's transformation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What would help you the most in the transformation to CE? 	<p>The challenge of defining responsibility for KPI compliance. Calculation of Indicators, as data often has to be collected across the value chain (upstream and downstream). Data availability and quality (data transparency). Digital infrastructure for the consolidation of CE data from different areas. Transparency in the calculation of indicators -> standardized calculation procedures and methods. Development of sector-specific standards for CE. Challenges in the evaluation of business models (outflow). CE affects all areas in a company -> each area needs indicators that must be consolidated. Conversion of business models must be financially viable and affordable for customers. Companies are interdependent in the management of CE measures (cooperation extremely important). Holistic evaluation and management of CE measures/ effectiveness (-> upstream and downstream). Aggregation of indicators is not absolutely necessary to make decisions</p>

Interview 2:

Interview questionnaire		
No	Question	Answer
Part 1: Internal KPIs vs. external reporting		
1	Are the CE indicators you have listed in the survey KPIs (relevant for management to monitor target achievement) or are they merely indicators?	The KPIs selected in the survey does only represent indicators and no KPIs
2	Which of the indicators mentioned is also a KPI? What are the relevant KPIs for monitoring the management's objectives for the CE? Is there even one KPI?	Actually there are no KPIs for CE, which are reviewed/ collected by the executive management/ ESG managers Indicators classified as relevant on the basis of product certifications: - Proportion of biomass in products - Proportion of recycled material in the product - Proportion of renewable material components in the product
3	Is the topic of CE even brought up to the management through KPIs and integrated into strategic business decisions?	Not yet, will develop over the next few years when sustainability is more strongly integrated into business strategy and processes at company level, so far only Indicators which are relevant for certifications are tracked
4	Was the topic of CE only addressed due to the mandatory compliance with external reporting standards (ESRS E5) or is the motivation intrinsic?	Topic driven by customer requirements (craftsmen, builders, project drivers) want to use sustainable materials in buildings, but in turn must also report on sustainability and the use of certain materias. Lead certification requirements as a driver (indicators in this certification, aim is a high score in certification and corresponding improvement measures are included in R&D -> economic incentive, as customers are inclined to buy such products (the building receives a score in an ESG certification, e.g. DGNB Gold, based on the materials used, which then increases the value of the building). kfw subsidies also linked to product certifications, i.e. customers focus on such materials. CSRD brings regulatory pressure to deal with it. CEO as a general driver for sustainability issues, willingness to invest money and take actions beyond legal requirements, but customer must pay for this additional effort, which is reflected in the price of the product, or be willing to pay for it. Suppliers have driven the issue by integrating biomass into the product. Downcycling of production waste (reused in other products) -> economic motivation
5	Is CE seen as an opportunity or driver of transformation, e.g. through the development of new circular business models/products, or rather as compliance with mandatory external reporting standards?	Partly yes, it is seen as an opportunity to identify further material sustainability issues. Significant driver for the formation of an ESG team in the company. Regulatory pressure for the company to act and proceed with CE

6	<p>Does external reporting on CE contribute to the transformation of your organisation towards circular products and business models?</p> <p>-If yes, specify which frameworks/standards (GRI, ESRS E5) contribute positively and to what extent?</p>	<p>An attempt is made to achieve an improvement in these areas on the basis of externally required indicators, but the focus is on economic efficiency, i.e. if, for example, recycling/biomass content in the product is increased, even beyond legal requirements/certification requirements, the customer must still be willing and able to pay for the product.</p>
7	<p>Do the external standards (ESRS E5, GRI) contain data points that are not relevant for CE in your company or that you only collect for external reporting and are of little importance internally?</p> <p>- If yes, please specify which data is only collected for reporting purposes.</p>	
8	<p>Academics have developed numerous indicators for measuring CE at company level. These often include several dimensions (ecological, social, economic) and CE strategies (9R framework) and are complex to calculate. Have such rather "theoretical" indicators already been analysed and, if necessary, calculated?</p> <p>e.g:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MCI - Material Circularity Indicator - CTI - Circular Transition Indicators - Circulytics <p>- Are there any other CE KPIs in addition to the ones you have specified that you use in your company?</p>	<p>Only indicators available at product level. KPIs are currently driven by external requirements from customers, suppliers and regulators. CE is not yet strategically relevant. Indicators are developed on the basis of the CSRD</p>
9	<p>Does your company set itself specific, strategic objectives in relation to the transformation to CE?</p>	<p>No specific targets yet available for CE. Targets are set on the basis of the sustainability topics identified in the materiality analysis of the CSRD.</p>
Part 2: Managementtool		
10	<p>How is the transformation to CE structured in your company?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there responsible persons? - Vision, Goals, Action Plan, Roles & Responsibilities 	<p>ESG Manager is responsible for target achievements set by executive management and must develop and monitor KPIs</p>

<p>11</p>	<p>Which departments/ functions/ perspectives in the company are affected by the transformation to CE?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - R&D (implementation of CE strategies to improve product circularity) - Production (reduction of resource consumption and utilisation, waste management) - Purchasing (supplier selection, auditing) - Cooperation with external partners (industry, science, etc.) - Management (strategy, vision, objectives, business models) - Marketing & Com. (product marketing, ext. CE com.) - Employees (training, satisfaction, participation) - Customer perspective (satisfaction with CE products) - Finance (budgeting, controlling, KPI reporting and monitoring) - Logistics (reverse logistics) 	<p>The organizational anchoring and targeted integration of various departments is still in its infancy. R&D does not explicitly pursue application of 9R strategies in products, but commitment driven by product certifications.</p>
<p>12</p>	<p>Who is responsible for setting and maintaining CE KPIs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COO (Chief Operations Officer) - CTO (Chief Technical Officer) - Business unit director - Product Owner - ... 	<p>ESG manager as coordinator, product owner, but on higher-level CTO responsible for compliance</p>
<p>13</p>	<p>Is there a tool, method, ISO standard/ framework etc. that you use in your company for the transformation to CE? e.g:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CE- Balanced Scorecard (financial, customer, process and development perspective) - ISO 59010/59020/59004 - Eco-Design Tools (for implementing and comparing CE strategies in the design and product development phase) - CEBR (Circular Economy Business Readiness) 	

14	<p>What do you currently see as the biggest obstacles or challenges in your company's transformation to CE? - What would help you the most in the transformation to CE?</p>	<p>Recycling or reuse of products/components at the end of their life cycle is difficult for companies to realize themselves, as they are used in small quantities around the world and it would be uneconomical to return them to their own production facilities. Products are currently not yet designed in such a way that they can be easily integrated into production again after their useful life. Currently complex recycling processes to separate the product by type -> technical feasibility, quality of recycling decreases. Bureaucratic hurdles in waste transportation through various countries countries. R&D is striving to design products in such a way that they can be separated by type on site and fed into the appropriate recycling infrastructure/recycling options. The aim would be to reuse products at the end of their life cycle for the production of new products in order to achieve a closed material cycle. So far, mainly thermal recycling as an EoL measure, as it is not possible to separate by type and contains substances that are currently prohibited, but high electricity generation, as petroleum-based products</p>
----	---	---